

The first annotated checklist of Costa Rican fungi

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Abstract: By this work, the first comprehensive checklist of fungi documented in Costa Rica is presented, developed through collaboration between local and international mycological experts. It is based on 866 publications documenting over 170 years of mycological research in the country, including approximately 9753 records and 5676 species and subspecific taxa across 1648 genera. The checklist provides detailed information on supraspecific taxonomic ranks, accepted species names with authors, synonyms with authors, and corresponding literature references. The list is available in two formats: a full taxonomic list organized hierarchically and a searchable Excel database. We expect this checklist to be a valuable resource for advancing mycology research in Costa Rica and the Neotropics.

Keywords: biodiversity, hotspot, neotropical fungi, regional distribution.

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Introduction

Costa Rica harbors a remarkable diversity of fungi, driven by its wide range of habitats and ecosystems, particularly in cloud forests, tropical rainforests, and Atlantic and Pacific coastal regions. Situated within the Mesoamerican biodiversity hotspot (CEPF 2024) and serving as a bridge between North and South America, the country's biodiversity is enriched by flora and fauna immigration and the exchange of fungal species from both regions. This biogeographical positioning, coupled with Costa Rica's robust conservation policies and extensive network of protected areas, further contributes to the richness of its fungal biodiversity. These factors facilitate Costa Rica's importance as a key region for mycological research and conservation efforts.

Fungi, along with plants and animals, are one of Earth's three primary eukaryotic kingdoms (Burki *et al.*, 2019). Although fungi currently rank third in terms of known species, with almost 156000 described species (Catalog of Life 2024a), this number is far lower than those of Animalia, which includes 1.51 million species (Catalog of Life 2024b), and Viridiplantae, with at least 380000 species (Catalog of Life 2024c). However, fungi are vastly underexplored, with estimates suggesting that the actual number of species lies between 1.5 and 6.3 million (Hawksworth and Lücking, 2017, Baldrian *et al.* 2022). A significant portion of this undiscovered fungal diversity is anticipated to be in tropical regions, including biodiversity-rich areas such as Costa Rica.

Species checklists are essential for documenting and understanding biodiversity, a priority highlighted by the 1992 Rio Convention on Biological Diversity. In Costa Rica, comprehensive checklists already exist for major vertebrate groups—such as amphibians, birds, fish, mammals, and reptiles—as well as for plants and several invertebrate groups. However, no such checklist has been available for fungi until now. The aim of this work is to present the first complete checklist of all fungal species recorded in Costa Rica. Previously, only specific fungal groups had been catalogued, such as anamorphic fungi (Granados-Montero *et al.* 2018), polypores (Carranza and Ruiz-Boyer 2005), rust fungi (Berndt 2004), and smut fungi (Piepenbring 1996). This new checklist is expected to encourage further research in Costa Rica and Central America, advancing our knowledge of fungal diversity in the region and becoming a catalyst for new, more intensive investigations.

Materials and methods

Geographic coverage

Costa Rica (51100 km²) is located in Central America, bordered by Nicaragua to the north, Panama to the southeast, the Pacific Ocean to the west, and the Caribbean Sea to the northeast. The country's diverse geography includes coastal plains, rolling hills, and several mountain ranges, with the highest point at 3821 m. The climate is tropical, with a distinct wet season from May to November and a dry season from December to April. Average annual precipitation ranges from 1500 mm in the drier Pacific regions to over 4000 mm in the Caribbean lowlands. The mean annual temperature is around 25°C, with moderate seasonal variation, especially in the higher elevations (Coen 1991).

Data Collection and Digitization

The elaboration of the checklist began with identifying and compiling relevant datasets and literature, carried out over the course of this project (January 2021–May 2024). Only data from peer-reviewed scientific journals and officially published books with ISBN numbers were included in the final compilation. Additionally, two databases—Cybertruffle (Minter 2024) and Macrofungi of Costa Rica (Halling and Mueller 2019)—were included. A preliminary fungal checklist for Costa Rica was created and later refined by mycological experts forming part of the present team. Each expert was responsible for performing a thorough taxonomic and nomenclatural review, incorporating new records, and updating previous entries considering the latest scientific knowledge within their area of expertise. See Supplementary Material 1 for the taxonomic specialists and the fungal groups they reviewed for this work.

Nomenclatural and taxonomic revision and the name reconciliation

Index Fungorum (2024) was utilized to retrieve information on higher taxonomic ranks (kingdom, phylum, subphylum, class, order, and family) and to verify the correct spelling of species names and authors. Species Fungorum (2024) was consulted to obtain information on accepted species names and synonyms; each mycological expert cross-checked this information. In some cases, taxonomic revisions were required for genera or groups. The taxonomic update, following Index Fungorum or Species Fungorum, was completed up to July 2023; any taxonomic changes after that date are not included in this work.

Results

Data on the diversity of fungal species known for Costa Rica were retrieved from 866 publications documenting over 170 years of mycological research from Fries (1851) to the present (see Supplementary Material 2 for the complete list of references). The compiled checklist includes 9753 records, some representing duplicate reports extracted from different sources. After a thorough standardization process, the final checklist comprises 5534 species. The checklist also includes infraspecific categories, listing five subspecies, 114 varieties, and 23 forms for a total of 5676 taxa. Invalidly published names lacking formal descriptions were excluded from the checklist (see Supplementary Material 3 for a list of excluded taxa). According to the literature, 1145 taxa are associated with type specimens collected in Costa Rica. A full taxonomic list of species and infraspecific taxa, structured hierarchically, is presented herein. The present checklist is also available as a searchable Excel database at The Knowledge Network for Biocomplexity website [<https://knb.ecoinformatics.org/>] under doi:10.5063/F1Q23XRT (Mardones *et al.* 2024). This database includes the complete species list and associated metadata such as higher taxonomic ranks, species authors, literature references, and synonyms.

Species count of higher taxa

The checklist reveals a diverse assemblage of fungi comprising seven phyla, 34 classes, 137 orders, 419 families, and 1648 genera, summarized here (Fig. 1) The majority of registered species belong to the phyla Ascomycota and Basidiomycota (Fig. 2a), with the most highly diverse classes being Lecanoromycetes, Sordariomycetes, and Dothideomycetes, and the dominant orders including Ostropales, Agaricales, Lecanorales, and Pucciniales (Fig. 2b).

The number of species and infraspecific taxa listed for each higher taxon is as follows:

Phyla: Ascomycota (3888), Basidiomycota (1710), Blastocladiomycota (2), Chytridiomycota (4), Entomophthoromycota (1), Glomeromycota (60), Mucoromycota (28).

Classes: Agaricomycetes (1269), Arthoniomycetes (104), Atractiellomycetes (3), Blastocladiomycetes (2), Candelariomycetes (2), Chytridiomycetes (3), Coniocybomycetes (10), Cryptomycocolacomycetes (1), Cystobasidiomycetes (2), Dacrymycetes (7), Dothideomycetes (815), Entomophthoromycetes (1), Entorrhizomycetes (2), Eurotiomycetes (206), Exobasidiomycetes (46), Glomeromycetes (60), Kickxellomycetes (22), Laboulbeniomycetes (21), Lecanoromycetes (1567), Leotiomycetes (78), Lichinomycetes (5), Microbotryomycetes (6), Mucoromycetes (5), Orbiliomycetes (6), Pezizomycetes (87), Pucciniomycetes (318), Rhizophydiomycetes (1), Saccharomycetes (36), Sordariomycetes (842),

Figure 1. Some fungal diversity from Costa Rica. a. *Wickerhamomyces anomalus* isolated from strawberry (*Fragaria* × *ananassa*). b. *Aspergillus terreus* isolated from a solitary bee. c. *Daldinia concentrica*. d. *Morchella esculenta*. e. *Cookeina tricholoma*. f. *Telimena balansae* on *Cedrela odorata*. g. *Telimena hydrangeae* on *Hydrangea* sp. h. *Cordyceps* sp. on a beetle larva i. *Hypotrachyna caraccensis*. j. *Sticta weigelii*. k. *Candelaria concolor*. l. *Graphis litoralis* m. *Austropuccinia psidii* on Guayaba (*Psidium guajava*). n. *Exsudoporus frostii*. o. *Lentinus crinitus*. p. *Rigidoporus microsporus*. q. *Amanita pantherina*. r. *Ganoderma parvulum*. s. *Clathrus chrysomycelinus*. t. *Campanophyllum proboscideum*. u. *Aseroë rubra*. v. *Chlorophyllum molybdites*. w. *Calostoma cinnabarinum*. x. *Clavulina* cf. *amethystina*. y. *Lactifluus indigo*. (Photographs by authors except a: K. Rojas, b: V. Nuñez, h: A. Vincent, j: A. Estrada).

Taphrinomycetes (2), Tremellomycetes (17), Umbelopsidomycetes (1), Ustilaginomycetes (39), Class Incertae sedis (107).

Orders: Acrospermales (3), Agaricales (526), Amphisphaeriales (32), Amplistromatales (2), Amylocorticiales (1), Annulatascales (9), Archaeosporales (2), Arthoniales (104), Asterinales (58), Asterotexales (1), Atheliales (1), Atractiellales (3), Auriculariales (29), Baeomycetales (9), Blastocladias (2), Boletales (107), Boliniales (1), Botryosphaeriales (56), Caliciales (90), Candelariales (2), Cantharellales (15), Capnodiaceae (10), Chaetomellales (2), Chaetosphaeriales (35), Chaetothyriales (26), Chytridiales (3), Cladosporiales (11), Coniochaetales (1), Coniocybales (10), Cordanales (2), Coronophorales (9), Corticiales (2), Cryptomycocolacales (1), Cyphobasidiales (1), Cystobasidiales (1), Dacrymycetales (6), Diaporthales (36), Diversisporales (29), Doassansiales (1), Dothideales (9), Entomophthorales (1), Entorrhizales (2), Entrophosporales (3), Entylomatales (20), Eremithallales (4), Eurotiales (74), Exobasidiales (20), Geastrales (25), Gloeophyllales (3), Glomerales (25), Glomerellales (39), Gomphales (8), Graphidales (147), Harpellales (22), Helicobasidiales (1), Helotiales (67), Herpomycetales (1), Hymenochaetales (128), Hypocreales (274), Hysterangiales (3), Hysteriales (3), Jahnulales (5), Jobellisiales (2), Laboulbeniales (20), Lecanorales (487), Lecideales (9), Leotiales (2), Lepidostromatales (1), Lichinales (5), Magnaporthales (11), Marthamycetales (1), Melanosporales (2), Meliolales (105), Microascales (12), Microbotryales (3), Microstromatales (2), Microthyriales (19), Monoblastiales (29), Mucorales (5), Muyocopronales (1), Mycocaliciales (4), Mycosphaerellales (170), Myriangiales (8), Myrmecridiales (1), Natipusillales (1), Onygenales (8), Ophiostomatales (7), Orbiliales (6), Ostropales (599), Paraglomerales (1), Parasymphodiellales (1), Patellariales (1), Peltigerales (162), Pertusariales (32), Pezizales (86), Phacidiales (2), Phaeomoniellales (3), Phallales (19), Phyllophorales (115), Pleosporales (164), Pleurotheciales (1), Polyporales (267), Pucciniales (315), Pyrenulales (70), Rhizocarpaceae (3), Rhizophydiales (1), Rhytismatales (4), Russulales (100), Saccharomycetales (36), Sebaciniales (6), Septodasidiales (2), Sordariales (32), Sporidiobolales (3), Stereopsidales (3), Strigulales (43), Taphrinales (2), Teloschistales (25), Thelephorales (2), Thelocarpales (1), Tilletiales (3), Togniniales (2), Trechisporales (22), Tremellales (17), Tremellodendropsidales (1), Trichosphaeriales (2), Trypetheliales (105), Tubeufiales (16), Umbelopsidales (1), Umbilicariales (3), Urocystidales (7), Ustilaginales (32), Venturiales (7), Vermiculariopsiellales (1), Verrucariales (19), Wiesneriomycetales (1), Xylariales (80), Order Incertae sedis (229).

Families: Acaulosporaceae (18), Acrospermaceae (3), Agaricaceae (32), Albatrellaceae (1), Aliquandostipitaceae (5), Amanitaceae (26), Ambisporaceae (2), Amphisphaeriaceae (7), Amplistromataceae (2), Amylocorticaceae (1), Ancylistaceae (1), Annulatasceae (9), Anthracoideaceae (14), Aphelariaceae (1), Apiosporaceae (4), Aplosporellaceae (1), Apoharknessiaceae (1), Arthoniaceae (53), Arthrodermataceae (8), Arthrorhaphidaceae (1), Ascobolaceae (4), Ascodesmidaceae (1), Aspergillaceae (72), Asterinaceae (50), Asterotexaceae (1), Astrosphaeriellaceae (2), Atheliaceae (1), Auriculariaceae (16), Auriscalpiaceae (8), Baeomycetaceae (5), Bankeraceae (1), Beltraniaceae (5), Bertiaceae (3), Biatoraceae (1), Bionectriaceae (29), Blastocladiaceae (2), Bloxamiaceae (1), Boletaceae (81), Boletinellaceae (3), Boliniaceae (1), Bondarzewiaceae (6), Botryobasidiaceae (2), Botryosphaeriaceae (20), Brachybasidiaceae (2), Brigantiaeaceae (1), Bulleribasidiaceae (3), Byssolomataceae (107), Cainiaceae (2), Caliciaceae (45), Callistosporiaceae (2), Calostomataceae (3), Camarosporiaceae (1), Candelariaceae (2), Capnodiaceae (4), Catillariaceae (4), Celotheliaceae (3), Cenangiaceae (1), Ceratobasidiaceae (1), Ceratocystidaceae (5), Ceratostomataceae (2), Cerenaceae (3), Chaconiaceae (5), Chaetomellaceae (2), Chaetomiaceae (2), Chaetosphaerellaceae (2),

Chaetosphaeriaceae (35), Chaetothyriaceae (8), Chlorociboriaceae (2), Choanephoraceae (1), Chorioactidaceae (1), Chrysotrichaceae (2), Chytridiaceae (1), Cladoniaceae (57), Cladosporiaceae (11), Claroideoglomeraceae (1), Clavariaceae (8), Clavariadelphaceae (2), Clavicipitaceae (42), Clitocybaceae (5), Coccocarpiaceae (18), Coccotremataceae (1), Coenogoniaceae (55), Coleosporiaceae (9), Collemataceae (50), Coniochaetaceae (1), Coniocybaceae (10), Coniothyriaceae (5), Cookellaceae (4), Cordanaceae (2), Cordycipitaceae (8), Corticiaceae (2), Cortinariaceae (29), Corynesporascaceae (3), Crepidotaceae (3), Cronartiaceae (3), Crossosporaceae (1), Cryphonectriaceae (1), Cryptobasidiaceae (4), Cryptomyocolacaceae (1), Cunninghamellaceae (2), Cyphellaceae (1), Cyphobasidiaceae (1), Cystobasidiaceae (1), Cystostereaceae (2), Dacrymycetaceae (6), Dacrybolaceae (4), Dacryonaemataceae (1), Dactylosporaceae (1), Debaryomycetaceae (1), Dermateaceae (1), Diademaceae (1), Diaporthaceae (21), Diatrypaceae (13), Dictyosporiaceae (3), Didymellaceae (47), Didymosphaeriaceae (4), Diplocystidiaceae (1), Dipodascaceae (2), Discinaceae (3), Diversisporaceae (1), Doassansiopsidaceae (2), Dothideaceae (4), Dothioraceae (1), Drepanopezizaceae (1), Echinodontiaceae (1), Elsinoaceae (8), Englerulaceae (5), Entolomataceae (19), Entorrhizaceae (2), Entrophosporaceae (3), Entylomataceae (20), Epibryaceae (5), Eremotheciaceae (1), Erysiphaceae (20), Erythroglloeaceae (1), Euantennariaceae (1), Exobasidiaceae (14), Fibroporiaceae (2), Fomitopsidaceae (17), Fuscideaceae (1), Galeropsidaceae (4), Ganodermataceae (2), Geastraceae (25), Gelatinodiscaceae (1), Gelatoporiaceae (2), Gigasporaceae (10), Glaziellaceae (1), Gloeophyllaceae (3), Glomeraceae (24), Glomerellaceae (37), Glomosporiaceae (3), Gnomoniaceae (3), Gomphaceae (4), Gomphillaceae (147), Graphidaceae (431), Graphostromataceae (7), Grifolaceae (1), Gyrosporaceae (4), Haematommataceae (16), Halosphaeriaceae (4), Harpellaceae (5), Helicobasidiaceae (1), Helicogoniaceae (1), Helminthosphaeriaceae (4), Helotiaceae (2), Helvellaceae (9), Hericiaceae (2), Hermatomycetaceae (1), Herpomycetaceae (1), Herpotrichiellaceae (7), Hyaloriaceae (3), Hyaloscyphaceae (2), Hydnaceae (11), Hydangiaceae (6), Hydodontaceae (22), Hygrophoraceae (49), Hygrophoropsidaceae (2), Hymenochaetaceae (100), Hymenogastraceae (29), Hyphodermataceae (1), Hyphodontiaceae (3), Hypocreaceae (42), Hypoxylaceae (15), Hypsostromataceae (1), Hysteriaceae (3), Icmadophilaceae (11), Ijuhyaceae (1), Incrustoporiaceae (13), Inocybaceae (6), Irpicaceae (22), Ischnodermataceae (1), Jobellisiaceae (2), Johansoniiaceae (2), Kathistaceae (1), Laboulbeniaceae (19), Lachnaceae (4), Laetiporaceae (4), Lasiosphaeriaceae (4), Lasiosphaeridaceae (1), Lecanographaceae (2), Lecanoraceae (23), Lecideaceae (9), Legeriomycetaceae (17), Lentariaceae (2), Lentomitellaceae (1), Leotiaceae (1), Lepidostromataceae (1), Leptosphaeriaceae (5), Leptosporaceae (1), Letrouitiaceae (4), Lichinaceae (5), Lipomycetaceae (1), Lizoniaceae (1), Lobariaceae (48), Lycoperdaceae (46), Lyophyllaceae (7), Lyrommataceae (3), Magnaporthaceae (4), Malmideaceae (6), Marasmiaceae (40), Marthamycetaceae (1), Massariaceae (1), Massarinaceae (7), Megalosporaceae (6), Melampsoraceae (1), Melanconidaceae (1), Melanommataceae (2), Melaspileaceae (4), Meliolaceae (105), Meripilaceae (8), Meruliaceae (11), Metacapnodiaceae (3), Metschnikowiaceae (9), Microascaceae (3), Microbotryaceae (1), Microdochiaceae (3), Micropeltidaceae (9), Microstromataceae (2), Microtheliopsidaceae (3), Microthyriaceae (8), Mikronegeriaceae (1), Milesinaceae (3), Mollisiaceae (1), Monoblastiaceae (29), Morchellaceae (4), Mucoraceae (2), Muyocopronaceae (1), Mycenaceae (33), Mycocaliciaceae (3), Mycoporaceae (5), Mycosphaerellaceae (170), Mycosyringaceae (1), Natipusillaceae (1), Nectriaceae (97), Neophysopellaceae (3), Neoschizotheciaceae (6), Nephromataceae (1), Niessliaceae (1), Nigrofomitaceae (2), Nitschkiaceae (3), Ochrolechiaceae (2), Omphalotaceae (49), Opegraphaceae (17), Ophioceraceae (2), Ophiocordycipitaceae (16), Ophioparmaceae (1), Ophiostomataceae (5), Orbiliaceae (6), Otideaceae (3), Oxyporaceae (3), Palawaniaceae (1), Panaceae (3), Pannariaceae (33), Paraglomeraceae (1), Paranectriellaceae (3),

Figure 2. Species registered in the Fungi of Costa Rica Checklist. a. Distribution of species according to phyla. One dot corresponds to 1%. The group indicated as Other basal fungi refer to phyla Blastocladiomycota, Chytridiomycota, Entomophthoromycota, and Mucoromycota. b. Relative number of species, by assigned order; only orders representing relative abundances greater than 2.5% of all registered species within each phyla are shown.

Parasymphodiellaceae (1), Parmeliaceae (175), Parmulariaceae (8), Parodiellaceae (3), Parodiopsidaceae (13), Patellariaceae (1), Paxillaceae (2), Peltigeraceae (11), Perisporiopsidaceae (10), Pertusariaceae (15), Pestalotiopsidaceae (24), Pezizaceae (4), Pezizellaceae (2), Phacidiaceae (1), Phaeosphaeriaceae (6), Phakopsoraceae (14), Phallaceae (19), Phallogastraceae (3), Phanerochaetaceae (8), Phleogenaceae (3), Phlyctidaceae (4), Phragmidiaceae (5), Phyllachoraceae (96), Phyllostictaceae (33), Phyllostictaceae (1), Physalacriaceae (13), Physciaceae (45), Placynthiaceae (1), Planistromellaceae (2), Plectosphaerellaceae (2), Pleosporaceae (56), Pleurotaceae (13), Pleurotheciaceae (1), Ploettnerulaceae (3), Pluteaceae (12), Podoscyphaceae (1), Podosporaceae (1), Polyporaceae (129), Polystomellaceae (2), Porinaceae (95), Protomycetaceae (1), Protoscyphaceae (1), Psathyrellaceae (8), Pseudohalonectriaceae (1), Pseudombrophilaceae (1), Pseudoperisporiaceae (14), Psilolechiaceae (1), Pterulaceae (1), Pucciniaceae (218), Pucciniastraceae (3), Puccinosiraceae (7), Pyrenulaceae (70), Pyriculariaceae (5), Pyronemataceae (29), Ramalinaceae (72), Ramboldiaceae (3), Raveneliaceae (19), Rhamphosporaceae (1), Rhizocarpaceae (3), Rhynchogastremaceae (2), Rhynchostomataceae (2), Rhytismataceae (4), Rickenellaceae (3), Roccellaceae (26), Russulaceae (77), Saccharomycetaceae (4), Saccotheciaceae (4), Sarcoporiaceae (1), Sarcoscyphaceae (20), Sarcosomataceae (2), Schizophyllaceae (2), Schizoporaceae (6), Schizothyriaceae (7), Sclerodermataceae (10), Sclerotiniaceae (8), Scortechiniaceae (1), Sebacinaceae (6), Septobasidiaceae (2), Serpulaceae (1), Seuratiaceae (2), Skierkaceae (1), Sordariaceae (4), Sphaerophoraceae (1), Sphaerophragmiaceae (1), Sphinctrinaceae (1), Sporidiobolaceae (3), Sporocadaceae (1), Stachybotryaceae (13), Steccheriaceae (24), Stephanosporaceae (1), Stereaceae (4), Stereocaulaceae (18), Stereopsidaceae (3), Stictidaceae (2), Strigulaceae (43), Strophariaceae (7), Synchronytriacae (2), Taphrinaceae (1), Telimenaceae (19), Teloschistaceae (13), Tephromelataceae (2), Tetraplosporiaceae (1), Thelenellaceae (12), Thelephoraceae (1), Thelocarpaceae (1), Tilletiaceae (3), Togniniaceae (2), Toroaceae (1), Torulaceae (3), Tranzscheliaceae (1), Trapeliaceae (4), Tremellaceae (10),

Tremellodendropsidaceae (1), Trichocomaceae (1), Tricholomataceae (18), Trichomonascaceae (1), Trichosphaeriaceae (2), Trichothyriaceae (2), Trigonopsidaceae (2), Trimorphomycetaceae (1), Trypetheliaceae (105), Tubariaceae (2), Tubeufiaceae (16), Tympanidaceae (1), Typhulaceae (2), Umbelopsidaceae (1), Umbilicariaceae (1), Urocystidaceae (1), Uropyxidaceae (15), Ustilaginaceae (18), Ustilentylomataceae (2), Valsaceae (1), Varicellariaceae (3), Venturiaceae (7), Vermiculariopsiellaceae (1), Verrucariaceae (19), Vezdaeaceae (1), Vibrisseaceae (1), Wicklowiaceae (1), Wiesneriomycetaceae (1), Wynneaceae (2), Xylariaceae (37), Zygosporiaceae (2), Family Incertae sedis (329).

Checklist of species and infraspecific taxa of Costa Rican fungi. Higher taxonomic ranks are based on Index Fungorum and taxonomic names on Species Fungorum. Taxa are listed alphabetically by phylum, class, order, and family. Names based on type specimens from Costa Rica are indicated by a single asterisk (*) before the name. Authors are excluded for brevity; see the Excel file for a complete list of authors.

ASCOMYCOTA**Arthoniomycetes****Arthoniales****Arthoniaceae**

**Amazonomyces farkasiae*
Arthonia accolens
Arthonia aciniformis
Arthonia antillarum
Arthonia complanata
Arthonia costaricensis
 **Arthonia cyanea* var. *cocosensis*
Arthonia cyanea var. *cyanea*
Arthonia farinulenta
Arthonia gregaria var. *adpersa*
 **Arthonia isidiata*
Arthonia lecythidicola
Arthonia leptosperma
Arthonia meisneri
Arthonia mira
Arthonia nigratula
Arthonia ochrodiscodes
Arthonia ochropsila
Arthonia opegraphina
 **Arthonia orbygniae*
Arthonia palmulacea
Arthonia platygraphidea
Arthonia polymorpha
Arthonia rubella
Arthonia somaliensis
Arthonia subnecta
Arthonia trilocularis
Arthothelium abnorme
Arthothelium cingulatum
Arthothelium macrothecum
Arthothelium mirabilis
Arthothelium taediosum
Arthothelium xanthocarpum
Coniarthonia pyrnhula
Coniarthonia wilmsiana
Coniocarpon cinnabarinum
Crypthonia albida
Cryptothecia effusa
Cryptothecia subnidulans
Eremothecella calamicola
Eremothecella cingulata
Helicobolomyces cinnabarinula
 **Herpothallon echinatum*
 **Herpothallon fertile*
 **Herpothallon minimum*

*Herpothallon rubrocinctum**Myriostigma candidum**Myriostigma filicinum**Myriostigma miniatum***Stirtonia punctiformis***Tylophoron crassiusculum**Tylophoron moderatum**Tylophoron protrudens***Chrysotrichaceae***Byssocaulon pannosum**Chrysothrix candelaris***Lecanographaceae***Alyxoria varia**Zwackhia bonplandii***Opegraphaceae***Cresponia leprieurii**Fouragea filicina**Fouragea puiggarii***Opegrapha alba**Opegrapha bonplandii* var. *bonplandii**Opegrapha bonplandii* var. *conglomerans**Opegrapha dibbenii***Opegrapha fuscothallina**Opegrapha lambinonii**Opegrapha phylloporinae**Opegrapha serustauxii**Opegrapha simplicior**Opegrapha sporopodiae**Opegrapha strigulae**Opegrapha vegae**Opegrapha velata**Opegrapha virescens***Roccellaceae***Chiodecton heterotropoides**Chiodecton sterile**Dichosporidium nigrocinctum**Enterographa angustissima***Enterographa byssoidea***Enterographa foliicola**Enterographa sipmanii**Lecanactis epileuca**Mazosia bambusae**Mazosia conica**Mazosia dispersa***Mazosia longispora**Mazosia melanophthalma**Mazosia paupercula**Mazosia phyllosema**Mazosia pilosa**Mazosia praemorsa**Mazosia pseudobambusae**Mazosia rotula**Mazosia rubropunctata***Mazosia sorediifera***Mazosia tenuissima**Mazosia tumidula**Syncesia farinacea**Syncesia leprobola**Syncesia psaroleuca***Family Incertae sedis***Cyrtographa irregularis***Synarthonia bicolor**Synarthonia inconspicua***Synarthothelium cerebriforme***Candelariomycetes****Candelariales****Candelariaceae***Candelariella vitellina**Candelina mexicana***Coniocybomycetes****Coniocybales****Coniocybaceae***Chaenotheca brunneola**Chaenotheca chlorella**Chaenotheca chrysocephala**Chaenotheca ferruginea**Chaenotheca gracillima**Chaenotheca hispidula**Chaenotheca hygrophila**Chaenotheca olivaceorufa**Chaenotheca trichialis***Sclerophora sanguinea***Dothideomycetes****Acrospermales****Acrospermaceae***Acrospermum compressum***Acrospermum leucocephalum**Acrospermum maxonii***Asterinales****Asterinaceae***Acarella costaricensis***Anariste poliothea***Asterina acalyphae***Asterina advenula***Asterina aemula**Asterina capparicola**Asterina combreti***Asterina confertissima*

- *Asterina consobrina*
Asterina coriacea
**Asterina costaricensis*
Asterina crotonicola
**Asterina cupheae*
Asterina delicata
**Asterina diplopoda*
**Asterina dorsteniae*
Asterina elegans
**Asterina erebia*
Asterina guaranitica
**Asterina hamata*
**Asterina indecora*
**Asterina isothea*
Asterina megalospora
Asterina nodulosa
**Asterina phenaxis*
**Asterina phoebes*
**Asterina phoebes-costaricanae*
Asterina pittieri
**Asterina ramonensis*
**Asterina schlechteriana*
Asterina scolopiae
Asterina sphaerotheca
**Asterina styracina*
**Asterina tabernaemontanae*
Asterina tonduzi
**Asterina tropicalis*
Asterina vagans
**Asterostomella acalyphae*
**Asterostomella dorsteniae*
**Asterostomella indecora*
**Asterostomella isothea*
**Asterostomella tonduzi*
Dimerosporium pellicula
Lembosia coccolobae
Lembosia melastomatum
Lembosia philodendri
**Lembosia poasensis*
**Neostomella ditissima*
Parasterina indecora
**Prillieuxina cinchonae*
Parmulariaceae
**Hysterostomella callista*
**Hysterostomella phoebes*
**Hysterostomella polyadelpa*
**Hysterostomina costaricensis*
**Inocyclus blechni*
Parmularia styracis
Polycyclus andinus
**Protothyrium trichiliae*
Asterotexales
Asterotexaceae
Asterotexis cucurbitacearum
Botryosphaerales
Aplosporellaceae
**Epicyta ampliata*
Botryosphaeriaceae
Botryosphaeria agaves
Botryosphaeria cyanospora
**Botryosphaeria simplex*
Botryosphaeria stevensii
Cophinforma tunefaciens
Diplodia anomala
Dothiorella erumpens
**Lasiodiplodia pseudotheobromae*
Lasiodiplodia theobromae
**Leptodothiorella concinna*
**Leptodothiorella cyathea*
Macrophoma mangiferae
Macrophoma sacchari
Macrophoma theicola
Macrophoma zeae
Macrophomina phaseolina
Neofusicoccum parvum
Neofusicoccum ribis
Neoscytalidium dimidiatum
Sphaeropsis begoniicola
Phyllostictaceae
**Guignardia concinna*
Phyllosticta apii
Phyllosticta batatas
Phyllosticta begoniae
**Phyllosticta begoniicola*
Phyllosticta bixina
Phyllosticta cajani
Phyllosticta capitalensis
**Phyllosticta chelonanthi*
Phyllosticta chrysanthemi
Phyllosticta citricarpa
**Phyllosticta coffeicola*
Phyllosticta concentrica
Phyllosticta fragariicola
Phyllosticta gladioli
Phyllosticta gossypina
Phyllosticta hesperidearum
Phyllosticta hibiscina
Phyllosticta manihoticola
Phyllosticta marantaceae
Phyllosticta musarum
Phyllosticta nicotianae
Phyllosticta oncidii-sphacelati
Phyllosticta oryzina
Phyllosticta petroselini
Phyllosticta petuniae
Phyllosticta phaseolina
Phyllosticta rosae
Phyllosticta solani
Phyllosticta statices
**Phyllosticta tonduzi*
Phyllosticta zingiberis
**Phyllostictina concinna*
Planistromellaceae
Microcyclus stuebelii
Planistromella cattleyae
Capnodiales
Capnodiaceae
Capnodium citri
Capnodium coffeae
Fumiglobus glabroides
Polychaeton tabebuiae
Johansoniaceae
**Johansonia amadelpa*
**Johansonia consociata*
Metacapnodiaceae
**Antennaria aequatorialis*
**Antennaria tropicicola*
Antennularia robinsonii
Family Incertae sedis
Scolecostigmina mangiferae
Cladosporiales
Cladosporiaceae
Cladosporium allii-cepae
Cladosporium angustisporum
Cladosporium cladosporioides
Cladosporium colocasiae
Cladosporium cucumerinum
Cladosporium fulvum
Cladosporium herbarum
Cladosporium sphaerospermum
Cladosporium tenuissimum
Cladosporium vignae
**Hormodendrum nectandrae*
Dothideales
Dothideaceae
Dothidea maculicola
Lucidasocarpa pulchella
**Phyllachorella schistocarphae*
**Vestergrenia cestri*
Dothioraceae
Sydowia polyspora
Sacotheciaceae
Aureobasidium pullulans
**Metasphaeria bifoveolata*
**Metasphaeria occulta*
**Pleosphaerulina cassiae*
Eremithallales
Melaspileaceae
**Eremithallus costaricensis*
Melaspilea acuta
Melaspilea opegraphoides
Hysteriales
Hysteriaceae
**Gloniella gracilis*
**Hysterium asymmetricum*
**Oedohysterium pulchrum*
Jahnulales
Aliquandostipitaceae
Aliquandostipite crystallinus
Aliquandostipite khaoyaiensis
Ascagilis bipolaris
Ascagilis seychellensis
Pseudojahnula potamophila
Microthyriales
Micropeltidaceae
**Chaetothyria costaricensis*
**Chaetothyria phoebes*
Micropeltidium tonduzi
Micropeltis applanata
Micropeltis bakeri
Micropeltis maxima
**Micropeltis phoebes*
**Parapeltella mediocris*
**Stomopeltis heteromeris*
Microthyriaceae
**Asterinema glabratae*
**Calopeltis acnisti*
**Calothyriopsis roupalae*
Caudella psidii
Lichenopeltella setifera
Microthyrium mangiferae
Scolecopeltidium mayteni
**Synostomella costaricensis*
Trichothyriaceae
Trichothyrium dubiosum
Trichothyrium reptans
Monoblastiales
Monoblastiaceae
Acrocordia endobrya
Anisomeridium albisedum
Anisomeridium ambiguum
Anisomeridium americanum
Anisomeridium anisolobum
Anisomeridium bifforme
Anisomeridium foliicola
Anisomeridium leucochlorum
Anisomeridium polycarpum
Anisomeridium polypori
Anisomeridium subprostans
Anisomeridium tamarindi
Capretia amazonensis
**Capretia neotropica*
Megalotremis biocellata
**Megalotremis cauliflora*
Megalotremis flavovulcana
Megalotremis infernalis

- *Megalotremis lateralis*
Megalotremis nemorosa
Megalotremis verrucosa
Microthelia albidella
**Microthelia flavicans*
**Microthelia intercedens*
Monoblastia palmicola
**Monoblastia subsquamulosa*
Trypetheliopsis gigas
**Trypetheliopsis kalbii*
Trypetheliopsis kassamensis
Muyocoproneas
Muyocoproneaceae
Arxiella terrestris
Mycosphaerellales
Mycosphaerellaceae
Achorodopsis poasensis
Asperisporium caricae
Catenulocercospora fusimaculans
Cercospora alabamensis
Cercospora anacardii
Cercospora apii
Cercospora arachidicola
Cercospora asparagi
Cercospora begoniae
Cercospora beticola
Cercospora brassicicola
Cercospora canescens
Cercospora capsici
Cercospora carotae
Cercospora cassavae
Cercospora chrysanthemi
Cercospora cruciferarum
Cercospora epipactidis
Cercospora erechthitis
Cercospora fragariae
Cercospora fukushiana
Cercospora gerberae
Cercospora gigantea
Cercospora hayi
Cercospora hederiae
Cercospora heliconiae
Cercospora hydrangeae
**Cercospora hymenocallidis*
Cercospora insulana
Cercospora jansseana
Cercospora kikuchii
**Cercospora leonuri*
Cercospora longipes
Cercospora longissima
Cercospora manihotis
Cercospora medicaginis
Cercospora melongenae
Cercospora nicotianae
Cercospora papayae
Cercospora passiflorae
Cercospora petroselini
Cercospora petuniae
**Cercospora porophylli*
Cercospora portoricensis
Cercospora pulcherrima
Cercospora ricinella
Cercospora rigospora
Cercospora sagittariae
**Cercospora sambuci*
**Cercospora sarachae*
Cercospora sechii
Cercospora sesami
Cercospora sojina
Cercospora sorghi
Cercospora tosensis
Cercospora zingibericola
Cercospora zonata
**Cercospora donnell-smithii*
Cercospora penniseti
Cercospora zae-maydis
Cercospora elvirae
Cercospora rubi
Cercospora coffeicola
Dothistroma septosporum
Mycosphaerella berkeleyi
Mycosphaerella cassiae
**Mycosphaerella castillae*
Mycosphaerella cerasella
Mycosphaerella cruenta
Mycosphaerella deightonii
Mycosphaerella dianthi
Mycosphaerella erythrinae
Mycosphaerella gibsonii
Mycosphaerella gossypina
Mycosphaerella henningsii
**Mycosphaerella miconiae*
Mycosphaerella pyri
Mycosphaerella verecunda
Mycovellosiella cucurbiticola
Mycovellosiella phaseoli
Neopenidiella nectandrae
Neopseudocercospora brassicae
Passalora bambusae
Passalora colcasiae
**Passalora consimilis*
**Passalora costaricensis*
Passalora diffusa
Passalora fulva
Passalora gliricidiae
**Passalora gonatoclada*
**Passalora grecciana*
**Passalora josensis*
Passalora koepkei
Passalora manihotis
**Passalora poasensis*
Passalora simulata
Passalora vaginae
**Periconiella cestri*
**Phleospora verbesinae*
Pluripassalora bougainvilleae
Pseudocercospora abelmoschi
Pseudocercospora atromarginalis
Pseudocercospora bixae
Pseudocercospora cochlospermi
**Pseudocercospora cupaniae*
Pseudocercospora dendrobii
Pseudocercospora depazeoides
Pseudocercospora fici
Pseudocercospora fijiensis
Pseudocercospora fuliginea
Pseudocercospora griseola
Pseudocercospora mali
**Pseudocercospora modesta*
Pseudocercospora musae
Pseudocercospora odontoglossi
Pseudocercospora opuli
Pseudocercospora pancratii
Pseudocercospora piperis
Pseudocercospora psidii
Pseudocercospora purpurea
Pseudocercospora ranjita
Pseudocercospora sapiicola
**Pseudocercospora trichophila* var. *trichophila*
**Pseudocercospora vismiae*
Pseudocercospora vitis
Pseudocercospora bradburyae
Pseudocercospora puerariae
Pseudocercospora sesami-indici
Ramularia grevilleana
Ramularia necator
Ramularia taraxaci
Ramulispora sorghi
Rosisphaerella rosicola
Septoria anthurii
Septoria apiicola
Septoria bataticola
Septoria betae
**Septoria cavendishiae*
Septoria chrysanthemella
**Septoria costaricensis*
Septoria cucurbitacearum
Septoria dianthi
Septoria erigerontis
Septoria expansa
Septoria fragariae
Septoria gossypina
Septoria heterochroa
Septoria lactucae
Septoria lobeliae
Septoria malvicola
Septoria passiflorae
Septoria pisi
**Septoria ramonensis*
Septoria selenophomoides
Septoria smilacis
Septoria yuccae
**Sphaerulina concinna*
Sphaerulina oryzina
Sphaerulina plantaginea
Sphaerulina sacchari
Sphaerulina westendorpii
Stigmia carpophila
Uwemyces elaeidis
Zasmidium biverticillatum
Zasmidium canavaliae
Zasmidium citri
Zasmidium citrigriseum
Zasmidium musigenum
**Zasmidium praelongum*
Myriangiales
Elsinoaceae
Elsinoe ampelina
Elsinoe anacardii
Elsinoe arachidis
Elsinoe fawcettii
Elsinoe perseae
Elsinoe poinsettiae
Elsinoe psidii
**Elsinoe erythrinae*
Natipusillales
Natipusillaceae
**Natipusilla limonensis*
Patellariales
Patellariaceae
Rhytidhysterium rufulum
Pleosporales
Astrosphaeriellaceae
**Astrosphaeriella longispora*
**Pithomyces cupaniae*
Camarosporiaceae
Camarosporium orchidicola
Coniothyriaceae
Coniothyrium concentricum
Coniothyrium fuckelii
**Coniothyrium insuetum*
Coniothyrium olivaceum
Coniothyrium phyllachorae
Corynesporascaceae
Corynespora cassiicola
**Corynespora inornata*

- Corynespora torulosa*
Diademaceae
 **Graphyllum panduratum*
Dictyosporiaceae
Dictyocheirospora heptaspora
Dictyocheirospora subramaniani
Dictyosporium prolificum
Didymellaceae
Allophoma piperis
Ascochyta boltshauseri
Ascochyta dianthi
Ascochyta abelmoschi
Ascochyta asparagina
Ascochyta boltshauseri
Ascochyta caricae
Ascochyta carthaginensis
Ascochyta gerberae
Ascochyta gladioli
Ascochyta mali
Ascochyta maydis
Ascochyta petuniae
Ascochyta sesami
Ascochyta sojae
Ascochyta sorghi
Ascochyta statures
Boeremia exigua
Boeremia lycopersici
Didymella arachidicola
 **Didymella eupatorii*
Didymella fabae
Didymella maydis
Didymella pinodella
Didymella pisi
Didymella pomorum
Epicoccum andropogonis
Epicoccum asterinum
Epicoccum draconis
Epicoccum nigrum
Epicoccum sorghinum
Leptosphaerulina crassiasca
Microsphaeropsis arundinis
 **Microsphaeropsis miconiae*
Microsphaeropsis tuisiensis
Nothophoma arachidis-hypogaeae
Nothophoma gossypicola
Peyronella obtusa
Phoma caricae-papayae
 **Phoma coffaeicida*
 **Phoma costarricensis*
Phoma herbarum
Phoma psidii
Phoma verbenaceae
Stagonosporopsis chrysanthemi
Stagonosporopsis crystalliniformis
Stagonosporopsis cucurbitacearum
Didymosphaeriaceae
Paraphaeosporia neglecta
 **Phaeodothis costaricensis*
Pseudopithomyces chartarum
Pseudopithomyces maydicus
Hermatomycetaceae
Hermatomyces tucumanensis
Hypsostromataceae
Hypsostroma saxicola
Leptosphaeriaceae
 **Leptosphaeria coffeicida*
Leptosphaeria culmifraga
Leptosphaeria maculans
Leptosphaeria pusilla
 **Leptosphaeria tonduzi*
Lizoniaceae
 **Lizonia opposita*
- Massariaceae**
 **Navicella costaricensis*
Massariaceae
Helminthosporium conspicuum
Helminthosporium glabroides
Helminthosporium gossypii
Helminthosporium mayaguezense
Helminthosporium sechiicola
Helminthosporium solani
Helminthosporium velutinum
Melanommataceae
Byssosphaeria jamaicana
Sporidesmiella hyalosperma
Mycoporaceae
Mycoporellum leucoplacum
Mycoporellum roseolum
Mycoporellum tantillum
Phaeosphaeriaceae
Eudarlucia australis
Eudarlucia caricis
 **Eudarlucia connata*
 **Metabotryon connatum*
Setophoma terrestris
Sphaerellopsis filum
Pleosporaceae
Alternaria alternata
Alternaria arborescens
Alternaria brassicae
Alternaria brassicicola
Alternaria cichorii
Alternaria citri
Alternaria cucurbitae
Alternaria dauci
Alternaria dianthi
Alternaria longipes
Alternaria mali
Alternaria padwickii
Alternaria panax
Alternaria passiflorae
Alternaria porri
Alternaria radicina
Alternaria ricini
Alternaria sesami
Alternaria solani
Alternaria sonchi
Alternaria tomata
Bipolaris cynodontis
Bipolaris melinidis
Bipolaris oryzae
Bipolaris sacchari
Bipolaris zeicola
Bipolaris cookei
Cochliobolus geniculatus
Cochliobolus heterostrophus
Cochliobolus setariae
Curvularia affinis
Curvularia brachyspora
Curvularia clavata
Curvularia crepinii
Curvularia cymbopogonis
Curvularia eragrostidis
Curvularia lunata
Curvularia oryzae
Curvularia pallescens
Curvularia ravenelii
Curvularia senegalensis
Curvularia spicifera
Curvularia trifolii
Curvularia tsudae
Exserohilum rostratum
Exserohilum turcicum
Pleospora bjoerlingii
- Stemphylium bolickii*
Stemphylium botryosum
Stemphylium congestum
Stemphylium cucurbitacearum
Stemphylium lycopersici
Stemphylium solani
Stemphylium sphaericum
Teretispora leucanthemii
Tetraplosphaeriaceae
Tetraploa aristata
Torulaceae
Dendryphion comosum
 **Dendryphion nodosum*
Dendryphion vinosum
Wicklowiaceae
Wicklowia aquatica
Family Incertae sedis
 **Berkleasmiium tropicale*
Ectophoma pomi
 **Leptothyrium costaricense*
Periconia atra
Periconia cookei
 **Periconia epilithographicola*
 **Periconia guazumae*
Periconia maculans
Remotididymella destructiva
Xenolophium pachythele
Strigulales
Strigulaceae
Dichoporis phaea
Dichoporis tenuis
Flagellostrigula laureriformis
 **Flavobathelium epiphyllum*
Phyllobathelium anomalum
Phyllobathelium chlorogastricum
Phyllobathelium epiphyllum
Phyllobathelium firmum
Phyllobathelium leguminosae
Phyllobathelium nigrum
Phyllobathelium thaxteri
Phyllocharis orbicularis
 **Phylloporis radiata*
Puiggariella nemathora
Racoplaca maculata
Strigula antillarum
Strigula concreta
Strigula elegans var. *elegans*
Strigula elegans var. *stellata*
Strigula janeirensis
Strigula macrocarpa
 **Strigula microspora*
Strigula minor
Strigula nemathora
Strigula nemathora var. *pulchella*
 **Strigula nigrocarpa*
Strigula nitidula
Strigula obducta
Strigula phyllogena
Strigula plana
Strigula platypoda
Strigula prasina
Strigula schizospora
Strigula smaragdula
Strigula subelegans
Strigula subtilissima
Strigula umbilicata
 **Strigula viridis*
 **Swinscowia amphora*
Swinscowia griseonitens
Swinscowia obtecta
Trypetheliales
Trypetheliaceae

- Aptrootia terricola*
**Architrypethelium hyalinum*
Architrypethelium nitens
Architrypethelium seminudum
Architrypethelium uberinum
Arthopyrenia borucana
**Arthopyrenia sublimitans*
Astrothelium aeneum
Astrothelium annulare
Astrothelium bicolor
Astrothelium buckii
Astrothelium cartilagineum
**Astrothelium cecidiogenum*
Astrothelium chapadense
Astrothelium cinnamomeum
Astrothelium crassum
Astrothelium degenerans
**Astrothelium effusum*
Astrothelium eustomum
Astrothelium feei
Astrothelium galbineum
Astrothelium gigantosporum
Astrothelium interjectum
**Astrothelium intermedium*
Astrothelium kunzei
Astrothelium leucothelium
Astrothelium macrocarpum
Astrothelium marcidum
Astrothelium megaspermum
Astrothelium neogalbineum
Astrothelium nitidiusculum
Astrothelium olivaceofuscum
Astrothelium papulosum
Astrothelium phlyctaena
Astrothelium porosum
Astrothelium puiggarii
Astrothelium pupula
**Astrothelium robustum*
Astrothelium sphaerioides
Astrothelium subaequans
Astrothelium subcatervarium
Astrothelium subclandestinum
Astrothelium subdiscretum
Astrothelium subdisjunctum
Astrothelium tuberculosum
Astrothelium versicolor
Bathelium lineare
Bathelium madrepuriforme
Bathelium mastoideum
Bathelium phaeomelodes
Bogoriella confluens
Bogoriella modesta
Bogoriella queenslandica
Bogoriella thelena
**Campylothelium tenue*
Constrictolumina cinchonae
Constrictolumina planorbis
Dictyomeridium amylosporum
Dictyomeridium proponens
Heufleria diplocarpa
Laurera dodgei
Laurera sepulta
Macroconstrictolumina lyrata
Nigrovothelium tropicum
Novomicrothelia oleosa
Polymeridium albidum
Polymeridium amylosporum
Polymeridium chioneum
Polymeridium contendens
**Polymeridium costaricense*
Polymeridium flavohecticum
Polymeridium pleurothecium
Polymeridium quinquesepatum
Polymeridium subcinereum
Polymeridium suffusum
Pseudobogoriella annonacea
Pseudobogoriella captiosa
Pseudobogoriella hemisphaerica
Pseudobogoriella leuckertii
Pseudobogoriella miculiformis
Pseudobogoriella punctata
Pseudobogoriella subfallens
Pseudopyrenula atroalba
Pseudopyrenula diluta
Pseudopyrenula endoxantha
**Pseudopyrenula erumpens*
Pseudopyrenula subgregaria
Pseudopyrenula subnudata
Pseudopyrenula subvelata
**Pseudopyrenula thallina*
Trypethelium eluteriae var. *citrinum*
Trypethelium eluteriae var. *eluteriae*
Trypethelium floridanum
Trypethelium mastoideum var. *macerum*
Trypethelium mastoideum var. *mastoideum*
Trypethelium ochroleucum
Trypethelium ochroleucum var. *ochroleucum*
Trypethelium ochroleucum var. *pallescens*
Trypethelium platystomum
Trypethelium subeluteriae
Trypethelium tricolor
Trypethelium variolosum
Tubeufiales
Tubeufiaceae
**Boerlagiomyces costaricensis*
**Byssocallis phoebes*
**Chaetocrea parasitica*
Helicoma fumosum
Helicoma pantoum
Helicoma recurvum
Helicomycetes roseus
Neohelicosporium aurantiellum
Neohelicosporium griseum
**Puttemansia aphanes*
**Puttemansia brachytricha*
Puttemansia lanosa
Tubeufia cylindrothecia
Tubeufia helicoma
Uredinophila tropicalis
Xenosporium berkeleyi
Venturiales
Venturiaceae
Anungitopsis triseptata
**Coleroa polylopha*
**Ectosticta costaricana*
**Pseudoparodiella vernoniae*
**Spilodochium vernoniae*
Venturia carpophila
Venturia inaequalis
Order Incertae sedis
Cookellaceae
**Myrianginella costaricensis*
Pycnoderma congestum
**Uleomyces comedens*
Uleomyces mirabilis
Englerulaceae
**Capnodiastrum tropicum*
**Questieriella quercina*
Rhytidenglerula cissi
**Sarcinella milleriae*
Schiffnerula compositarum
Euantennariaceae
**Euantennaria tropicicola*
Mycoporaceae
Mycoporum eschweileri
Mycoporum lacteum
Palawaniaceae
Palawania grandis
Paranectriellaceae
Paranectriella juruana
**Paranectriella meliolicola*
**Paranectriella miconiae*
Parodiellaceae
Parodiella hedysari
Parodiella perisporioides
Parodiella viridescens
Parodiopsidaceae
**Diblastospermella aequatorialis*
Dimeriella cordiae
Dimeriella cordicola
**Dimeriella corni*
Dimeriella erigeronicola
Dimeriella olyrae
**Dimerium consimile*
**Dimerium costaricense*
**Dimerium cyanomelum*
Dimerium imperspicuum
**Phaeodimeriella asperula*
**Phaeodimeriella exigua*
Phaeodimeriella guarapiensis
Perisporiopsidaceae
**Cicinnobella asperula*
**Cicinnobella consimilis*
**Cicinnobella costaricensis*
**Cicinnobella exigua*
Cicinnobella parodiellicola
Lasiositemma coronatum
**Perisporina dendritica*
**Perisporiopsis escharoides*
Perisporiopsis megalospora
Perisporiopsis melioloides
Polystomellaceae
**Parastigmatea polyadelpa*
**Polystomella costaricensis*
Protoscyphaceae
**Protoscypha pulla*
Pseudoperisporiaceae
**Aphanostigme solani*
**Chaetostigme caricae*
**Dimerina epidochica*
Dimerina mindanaensis
**Dimerina schmidtiana*
**Episoma parasiticum*
**Episphaerella dodonaeeae*
**Episphaerella trichophila*
**Eumela chiococcae*
**Nematostoma costaricana*
**Nematostoma costaricense*
Nematostoma occidentale
Phaeostigme picea
**Stigme costaricana*
Schizothyriaceae
**Endocykla phoebes*
**Metathyriella roupalae*
**Microthyriella costaricensis*
**Myriangiella roupalae*
**Plochmopeltis roupalae*
Schizothyrium discoideum
**Schizothyrium phoebes*
Seuratiaceae
Heterobotrys paradoxa
Seuratia millardetii
Toroaceae
Toroa dimerosporioides
Eurotiomycetes
Chaetothyriales

Chaetothyriaceae

**Chaetothyrium concinnum*
 **Chaetothyrium permixtum*
 **Merismella concinna*
 **Merismella gracilentia*
 **Merismella oligomera*
 **Merismella proxima*
Microalliumyces amadelphus
Phaeosaccardinula samoensis

Epibryaceae

Epibryon bryophilum
Epibryon deceptor
 **Epibryon filiforme*
Epibryon hepaticola
 **Epibryon semitectum*

Herpotrichiellaceae

Ardhachandra cristaspora
Exophiala calicioides
Fonsecaea pedrosoi
Metulocladosporella musae
Phialophora verrucosa
Rhinoclaadiella cristaspora
Thysanorea rousseliana

Lyrommataceae

Lyromma nectandrae
Lyromma ornatum
Lyromma palmae

Microtheliopsisaceae

Microtheliopsis uleana
 **Microtheliopsis winkleri*

Eurotiales**Aspergillaceae**

**Aspergillopsis tropicalis*
Aspergillus aculeatus
Aspergillus awamori
 **Aspergillus biplanus*
Aspergillus candidus
Aspergillus clavatus
Aspergillus conicus
 **Aspergillus costaricensis*
 **Aspergillus diversus*
 **Aspergillus ellipticus*
Aspergillus flavus
Aspergillus fumigatus
Aspergillus glaucus
 **Aspergillus granulatus*
Aspergillus janus
Aspergillus nidulans
Aspergillus niger
Aspergillus ochraceus
Aspergillus ostianus
Aspergillus parasiticus
Aspergillus phoenicis
Aspergillus sclerotiorum
Aspergillus sparsus
Aspergillus tamaritii
Aspergillus terreus
Aspergillus tubingensis
Aspergillus versicolor
Aspergillus violaceofuscus
Aspergillus westerdijkiae
 **Emericella heterothallica*
Eupenicillium tropicum
Hamigera avellanae
Paecilomyces divaricatus
Paecilomyces maximus
Paecilomyces tenuis
Paecilomyces varioti
Penicillium brevicompactum
Penicillium chrysogenum
Penicillium citrinum
 **Penicillium costaricense*

Penicillium daleae
Penicillium digitatum
Penicillium expansum
Penicillium gladioli
Penicillium glaucum
Penicillium griseofulvum
 **Penicillium guanacastense*
Penicillium italicum
 **Penicillium mallochii*
Penicillium miczynskii
Penicillium paxilli
Penicillium rolsfii
Penicillium rubens
Penicillium sclerotiorum
Penicillium simplicissimum
Penicillium solitum
Penicillium spathulatum
Penicillium tropicum
Penicillium vinaceum
Penicillium westlingii
Talaromyces aculeatus
Talaromyces amestolkiae
Talaromyces calidicanius
Talaromyces diversus
Talaromyces funiculosus
Talaromyces pinophilus
Talaromyces purpureogenus
Talaromyces stollii
Talaromyces verruculosus

Trichocomaceae

Trichocoma paradoxa

Family Incertae sedis

Kendrickiella phycomyces

Mycocaliciales**Mycocaliciaceae**

Chaenothecopsis debilis
Chaenothecopsis pusilla
 **Chaenothecopsis rubina*

Sphinctrinaceae

Sphinctrina tubaeformis

Onygenales**Arthrodermataceae**

Epidermophyton floccosum
Microsporum canis
Microsporum gypseum
Trichophyton ajelloi
Trichophyton mentagrophytes
Trichophyton rubrum
Trichophyton tonsurans
Trichophyton verrucosum

Phaeomoniellales**Celotheliaceae**

Celothelium aciculiferum
Celothelium chinchonarum
Celothelium dominicanum

Pyrenulales**Pyrenulaceae**

Anthracotheceum macrosporium
Anthracotheceum paraguayense
Anthracotheceum prasinum
 **Clypeopyrenis microsperma*
 **Clypeopyrenis porinoides*
 **Lithothelium fluorescens*
Lithothelium illotum
Lithothelium obiectum
 **Mazaediothecium album*
Pyrenula acutalis
Pyrenula acutispora
 **Pyrenula andina*
Pyrenula anomala
Pyrenula aspistea
Pyrenula astroidea

Pyrenula cocoes
Pyrenula concatervans
 **Pyrenula confinis*
Pyrenula corticata
 **Pyrenula costaricensis*
Pyrenula cryptothelia
Pyrenula cubana
Pyrenula cuneatostroma
Pyrenula dermatodes
Pyrenula duplicans
Pyrenula falsaria
Pyrenula globifera
Pyrenula laetior
Pyrenula lai
Pyrenula leucostoma
Pyrenula lineatostroma
Pyrenula luteopruinosa
Pyrenula macrocarpa
Pyrenula macularis
Pyrenula mamillana
Pyrenula marginatula
Pyrenula massariospora
Pyrenula mastophoroides
Pyrenula microcarpa
Pyrenula microtheca
 **Pyrenula minae*
 **Pyrenula montocensis*
Pyrenula mucosa
Pyrenula neofulva
Pyrenula nitidula
Pyrenula oleosa
Pyrenula papilligera
Pyrenula parvinuclea
Pyrenula praelucida
Pyrenula punctella
Pyrenula pyrenuloides
Pyrenula pyrgillospora
 **Pyrenula quassicola*
Pyrenula ravenelii
Pyrenula rockii
 **Pyrenula rubroanomala*
Pyrenula santensis
Pyrenula septicollaris
Pyrenula subcongruens
Pyrenula subferruginea
Pyrenula subgregantula
Pyrenula subpraelucida
 **Pyrenula subsoluta*
Pyrenula tenuisepta
Pyrenula thelomorpha
Pyrenula xyloides
Pyrgillus javanicus

Verrucariales**Verrucariaceae**

Agonimia foliacea
Agonimia opuntiella
Agonimia pacifica
Agonimia tristicula
Endocarpon pusillum
Flakea papillata
Melanotheca achariana
Normandina pulchella
Parmentaria chilensis
Phylloblastia amazonica
Phylloblastia borhidii
Phylloblastia septemseptata
 **Psoroglaena costaricensis*
Psoroglaena cubensis
Psoroglaena perminuta
Psoroglaena stigonemoides
Verrucaria omphalota
Verrucaria zonata

- Willeya diffractella*
Order Incertae sedis
Rhynchostomataceae
**Rhynchomeliola pusilla*
**Rhynchostoma biolleyana*
Laboulbeniomycetes
Herpomycetales
Herpomycetaceae
Herpomyces paranensis
Laboulbeniales
Laboulbeniaceae
Corethromyces bernardii
Diaphoromyces zirophori
**Diphymyces costaricensis*
Ecteinomyces trichopterophilus
Eucantharomyces egae
Gloeandromyces nycteriūidarum
**Hesperomyces coleomegillae*
Hesperomyces palustris
Kyphomyces platensis
Laboulbenia ecitonis
Laboulbenia funeralis
**Laboulbenia media*
Laboulbenia pheropsophi
Laboulbenia skelleyi
Nycteromyces streblidinus
**Prolixandromyces tenuis*
Rhachomyces longissimus
Stemmatomyces panamensis
Triceromyces hebri
Family Incertae sedis
**Rodaucea hermannii*
Lecanoromycetes
Baeomycetales
Baeomycetaceae
Baeomyces carneus
Baeomyces rufus
Parainoa subconcolor
Phyllobaeis erythrella
Phyllobaeis imbricata
Trapeliaceae
Placynthiella uliginosa
Trapelia coarctata
Trapeliopsis glaucolepidea
Trapeliopsis granulosa
Caliciales
Caliciaceae
Amandinea megaspora
Buellia aeruginascens
Buellia badia
Buellia demutans
Buellia dispersula
Buellia glaziouana
Buellia leptocline
Buellia parasema
Buellia pseudotetrapla
Buellia stellulata
Buellia versicolor
Buellia xanthinula
**Calicium constrictum*
Calicium glaucellum
Calicium hyperelloides
Calicium lenticulare
Calicium salicinum
**Chromofulvea omalia*
Cratiria aggregiens
Cratiria americana
Cratiria obscurior
Cratiria rutilans
Diplotomma alboatrum
Dirinaria aegialita
Dirinaria applanata
- Dirinaria picta*
Dirinaria purpurascens
Gassicurtia dodecaspora
**Gassicurtia pseudosubpulchella*
Gassicurtia rufofuscescens
Gassicurtia vaccinii
Hafellia parastata
Pyxine berteroaana
Pyxine brachyloba
Pyxine cocoes var. *cocoes* f. *cocoes*
Pyxine cocoes var. *cocoes* f. *isidiophora*
Pyxine coralligera
**Pyxine daedalea*
Pyxine obscurascens
Pyxine soreliata
Sculptolumina japonica
Sculptolumina serotina
Stigmatochroma epimartum
Stigmatochroma glaucothecum
Stigmatochroma metaleptodes
Physciaceae
Heterodermia albicans
Heterodermia barbifera
Heterodermia comosa
Heterodermia cubensis
Heterodermia diademata
Heterodermia flabellata
Heterodermia galactophylla
Heterodermia granulifera
Heterodermia hypoleuca
Heterodermia isidiophora
Heterodermia lamelligera
Heterodermia obscurata
Heterodermia podocarpa
Heterodermia speciosa
Heterodermia tropica
**Heterodermia urtasuni*
Hyperphyscia adglutinata
Leucodermia boryi
Leucodermia circinalis
Leucodermia leucomelos
Leucodermia lutescens
Leucodermia vulgaris
Phaeophyscia hispidula
Physcia alba
Physcia atrostriata
Physcia crispa
Physcia decorticata
Physcia erumpens
Physcia integrata
Physcia kalbii
Physcia krogiae
**Physcia laciniolata*
Physcia lopezii
Physcia obsessa
Physcia pachyphylla
Physcia sorediosa
Physcia undulata
Polyblastidium appendiculatum
Polyblastidium casarettianum
Polyblastidium japonicum
Polyblastidium magellanicum
Polyblastidium propaguliferum
Polyblastidium squamulosum
Rinodina rivularis
Rinodina stellulata
Graphidales
Gomphillaceae
**Actinoplaca gemmifera*
Actinoplaca strigulacea
Aderkomyces albostrigosus
Aderkomyces couepiae
- Aderkomyces dilatatus*
Aderkomyces fumosus
**Aderkomyces guatemalensis*
Aderkomyces heterellus
**Aderkomyces papilliferus*
**Aderkomyces purullhensis*
**Aderkomyces subalbostrigosus*
**Arthotheliopsis planicarpa*
**Arthotheliopsis serusiauxii*
Arthotheliopsis tricharioides
Asterothyrium argenteum
**Asterothyrium gyalideoides*
**Asterothyrium chroodisciforme*
Asterothyrium decipiens
Asterothyrium gigantosporum
**Asterothyrium gyalideoides*
Asterothyrium hedbergii
Asterothyrium leptosporum
Asterothyrium leucophthalmum
Asterothyrium longisporum
Asterothyrium microsporum
Asterothyrium monosporum
**Asterothyrium pallidum*
Asterothyrium pittieri
Asterothyrium rondoniense
Asterothyrium rotuliforme
**Asterothyrium septemseptatum*
**Asterothyrium tetrasporum*
**Asterothyrium uniseptatum*
Aulaxina dictyospora
**Aulaxina intermedia*
Aulaxina microphana
Aulaxina minuta
Aulaxina multiseptata
Aulaxina opegraphina
Aulaxina quadrangula
Aulaxina submyralis
Bullatina aspidota
Calenia aggregata
**Calenia areolata*
**Calenia corticola*
Calenia depressa
**Calenia dictyospora*
Calenia graphidea
**Calenia lobulata*
**Calenia lueckingii*
**Calenia minuta*
Calenia monospora
Calenia phyllogena
**Calenia rolandiana*
**Calenia solorinoides*
**Calenia subdepressa*
**Calenia submyralis*
Calenia thelotremella
Calenia triseptata
Caleniopsis laevigata
**Caleniopsis tetramera*
Echinoplaca atrofusca
Echinoplaca bispora
Echinoplaca diffluens
Echinoplaca epiphylla
Echinoplaca furcata
**Echinoplaca fusconitida*
Echinoplaca handelii
Echinoplaca hymenocarpoidea
Echinoplaca intercedens
Echinoplaca leucotrichoides
**Echinoplaca lucernifera*
**Echinoplaca marginata*
**Echinoplaca melanotrix*
Echinoplaca pellicula
Echinoplaca similis

- *Echinoplaca triseptata*
**Echinoplaca verrucifera*
**Echinoplaca wilsoniorum*
**Ferraroa hyalina*
Gomphillus ophiosporus
Gyalectidium barbatum
Gyalectidium catenulatum
Gyalectidium caucasicum
Gyalectidium ciliatum
**Gyalectidium denticulatum*
Gyalectidium eskucheii
Gyalectidium fantasticum
Gyalectidium filicinum
Gyalectidium imperfectum
**Gyalectidium laciniatum*
**Gyalectidium maracae*
Gyalectidium palmicola
Gyalectidium yahraiae
Gyalidea hyalinescens
**Gyalideopsis actinoplacoides*
**Gyalideopsis altamirensis*
Gyalideopsis applanata
Gyalideopsis buckii
Gyalideopsis capitata
**Gyalideopsis cochlearifer*
Gyalideopsis confluens
Gyalideopsis giganteoides
**Gyalideopsis intermedia*
Gyalideopsis laevigata
Gyalideopsis lambinonii
**Gyalideopsis macarthurii*
Gyalideopsis megalospora
**Gyalideopsis minutissima*
**Gyalideopsis montana*
Gyalideopsis napoensis
**Gyalideopsis pallida*
Gyalideopsis palmata
Gyalideopsis parvula
Gyalideopsis peruviana
**Gyalideopsis pseudoactinoplaca*
Gyalideopsis rubescens
**Gyalideopsis rubra*
Gyalideopsis vainioi
Gyalideopsis verruculosa
Gyalideopsis vulgaris
Gyalideopsis vulgaris f. albopruinosa
Gyalideopsis vulgaris f. vulgaris
**Gyalideopsis wesselsii*
**Jamesiella chaverriae*
**Paratracharia paradoxa*
Phyllogyalidea epiphylla
Psorotheciopsis albomaculans
Psorotheciopsis patellarioides
**Psorotheciopsis philippinensis*
Psorotheciopsis premeella
Rolueckia conspersa
Rubrotricha helminthospora
Tricharia amazonum
Tricharia carnea
Tricharia farinosa
Tricharia hyalina
Tricharia lancicarpa
Tricharia longispora
**Tricharia pseudosantessonii*
Tricharia santessoniana
Tricharia santessonii
Tricharia similis
Tricharia subhelminthospora
Tricharia urceolata
Tricharia vainioi
Lecanorales
Biatorrellaceae
Piccolia conspersa
Byssolomataceae
**Baflavia flavescens*
**Bapalmuia costaricensis*
**Bapalmuia lineata*
Bapalmuia nigrescens
Bapalmuia palmularis
Barubria fuscobrunnea
Brasilicia brasiliensis
Byssolecania deplanata
Byssolecania fumosonigrans
Byssolecania hymenocarpa
**Byssolecania pluriseptata*
Byssolecania variabilis
Byssolecania vezdae
Byssoloma absconditum
Byssoloma aurantiacum
**Byssoloma carneum*
Byssoloma chlorinum
Byssoloma discordans
Byssoloma fadenii
Byssoloma guttiferiae
Byssoloma leucoblepharum
Byssoloma lueckingii
Byssoloma marginatum
Byssoloma minutissimum
**Byssoloma multipunctatum*
Byssoloma sprucei
Byssoloma subdiscordans
Byssoloma subpolychromum
Byssoloma vanderystii
Byssoloma wettsteinii
Calopadia chacoensis
Calopadia editiae
Calopadia foliicola
Calopadia fusca
Calopadia isidiosa
Calopadia lecanorella
Calopadia perpallida
Calopadia phyllogena
Calopadia puiggarii
Calopadia subcoerulea
**Eugeniella ortizii*
**Fellhanera angustispora*
**Fellhanera avilezii*
**Fellhanera badimiooides*
Fellhanera bouteillei
Fellhanera buxi
**Fellhanera dictyospora*
**Fellhanera dispersa*
Fellhanera dominicana
Fellhanera elliotii
**Fellhanera emarginata*
Fellhanera farinosa
Fellhanera fuscata
Fellhanera lisowskii
**Fellhanera longispora*
Fellhanera misionensis
**Fellhanera montana*
**Fellhanera muhleii*
Fellhanera naevia
Fellhanera paradoxa
**Fellhanera pilomarginata*
**Fellhanera pilosa*
Fellhanera raphidophylli
Fellhanera rubida
Fellhanera santessonii
Fellhanera semecarpi
Fellhanera stanhopeae
Fellhanera subfuscata
Fellhanera sublecanorina
Fellhanera tricharioides
**Fellhanera tubulifera*
Fellhanera tuckeri
**Fellhanera verrucifera*
**Fellhanera viridis*
**Fellhanera winkleriana*
Lasioloma arachnoideum
Loflammia epiphylla
Loflammia gabrielis
Logilvia gilva
Micarea alabastrites
**Pseudocalopadia mira*
**Septotrapelia glauca*
**Sporopodium aeruginascens*
**Sporopodium antonianum*
Sporopodium aurantiacum
Sporopodium citrinum
Sporopodium leprieurii
**Sporopodium octosporum*
Sporopodium phyllocharis
Sporopodium phyllocharis var. flavithallinum
Sporopodium pilocarpoides
Sporopodium xantholeucum
Szczawinskia tsugae
**Tapellaria albomarginata*
Tapellaria bilimboides
**Tapellaria bilimboides var. major*
Tapellaria epiphylla
Tapellaria major
Tapellaria moellei
Tapellaria nana
Tapellaria nigrata
Tapellaria phyllophila
Tapellaria puiggarii
**Tapellariopsis octomera*
Catillariaceae
Catillaria endochroma
Catillaria fabacea
Catillaria leptoloma
Catillaria obtegens
Cladoniaceae
Cladia aggregata
Cladina arcuata
Cladonia aggregata
Cladonia aleuropoda
Cladonia andesita
Cladonia arbuscula
Cladonia arcuata
Cladonia calycantha
Cladonia cartilaginea
Cladonia ceratophylla
Cladonia chlorophaea
Cladonia chlorophaeoides
Cladonia coccifera
Cladonia confusa f. bicolor
Cladonia confusa f. confusa
Cladonia coniocraea
Cladonia corniculata
Cladonia corymbites
Cladonia corymbosula
Cladonia crispata
Cladonia crispatula
Cladonia dactylota
Cladonia degenerans
Cladonia didyma
Cladonia farinophylla
Cladonia fimbriata var. prolifera
Cladonia fimbriata var. simplex
Cladonia furcata
Cladonia granulosa
Cladonia grayii
Cladonia isabellina

- Cladonia lepidophora*
Cladonia macilenta
Cladonia macilentoides
Cladonia merochlorophaea
Cladonia mexicana
Cladonia microscypha
Cladonia nana
Cladonia novochlorophaea
Cladonia ochrochlora
Cladonia pulverulenta
Cladonia pyxidata
Cladonia ramulosa
Cladonia rappii
Cladonia scabriuscula
Cladonia scholanderi
Cladonia solida
Cladonia squamosa
Cladonia squamosa var. *squamosa*
Cladonia squamosa var. *subsquamosa*
Cladonia stenophyllodes
Cladonia subradiata
Cladonia subsquamosa
Cladonia subulata
Cladonia tachirae
Pilophorus cereolus
Dactylosporaceae
Pseudobactrodesmium longisporum
Haematommataceae
Haematomma accolens
Haematomma africanum
Haematomma americanum
Haematomma collatum
Haematomma flexuosum
Haematomma fluorescens var. *fluorescens*
 **Haematomma fluorescens* var. *longisporum*
Haematomma guyanense
Haematomma leprarioides
 **Haematomma nicoyense*
Haematomma persoonii
Haematomma puniceum
Haematomma rufidulum
Haematomma sorediatum
 **Haematomma staigeriae*
Haematomma sulphureum
Lecanoraceae
Glaucmaria carpinea
Lecanora achroa
Lecanora albella
Lecanora argentata
Lecanora campestris
Lecanora chlarotera
Lecanora cinereocarnea var. *cinereocarnea*
Lecanora cinereocarnea var. *lainea*
Lecanora flavidofusca
Lecanora horiza
Lecanora leproplaca
Lecanora leprosa
Lecanora neonashii
Lecanora praeferenda
Lecanora rhabdota
Lecanora subcrenulata
Lecanora subgranulata
Lecanora subimmersa
Lecanora subimmersa
Lecanora sublivida
Lecanora tropica
Lecanora virentiflavida
Lecanora xanthomelaniza
Malmideaceae
Malmidea amazonica
Malmidea aurigera
Malmidea furfurosa
Malmidea granifera
Malmidea piperis
Sprucideia penicillata
Parmeliaceae
Alectoria imshaugii
Alectoria ochroleuca
Alectoria sarmentosa
Anzia americana
Anzia leucobates
Anzia masonii
Anzia parasitica
Bryoria furcellata
Bulbothrix apophysata
Bulbothrix coronata
Bulbothrix fungicola
Bulbothrix goebelii
Bulbothrix klementii
Bulbothrix laevigatula
Bulbothrix suffixa
Bulbothrix ventricosa
Canoparmelia amazonica
Canoparmelia caroliniana
Canoparmelia texana
Crespoa carneoprunita
Crespoa scrobicularis
Eumitria baileyi
Everniastrum planum
Flavopunctelia flaventior
Hypogymnia physodes
Hypotrachyna andensis
Hypotrachyna anziaica
Hypotrachyna bogotensis
Hypotrachyna boquetensis
Hypotrachyna caraccensis
Hypotrachyna catawbiensis
 **Hypotrachyna chicitae*
Hypotrachyna chlorina
Hypotrachyna cirrhata
 **Hypotrachyna costaricensis*
Hypotrachyna crenata
Hypotrachyna croceopustulata
Hypotrachyna dactylifera
Hypotrachyna degelii
Hypotrachyna densirhizinata
Hypotrachyna dentella
Hypotrachyna ducalis
Hypotrachyna endochlora
Hypotrachyna ensifolia
Hypotrachyna everniastroides
Hypotrachyna exsplendens
Hypotrachyna flavida
Hypotrachyna formosana
Hypotrachyna fragilis
Hypotrachyna gigas
Hypotrachyna gondylophora
Hypotrachyna heterochroa
Hypotrachyna horrescens
Hypotrachyna imbricata
Hypotrachyna isidiocera
Hypotrachyna laevigata
Hypotrachyna lipidifera
Hypotrachyna lopezii
 **Hypotrachyna lueckingii*
Hypotrachyna mexicana
Hypotrachyna microblasta
Hypotrachyna minarum
Hypotrachyna neodissecta
 **Hypotrachyna norlopezii*
Hypotrachyna partita
Hypotrachyna peruviana
Hypotrachyna physcioides
Hypotrachyna producta
Hypotrachyna prolongata
Hypotrachyna protenta
 **Hypotrachyna protoboliviana*
Hypotrachyna pseudosinuosa
Hypotrachyna pulvinata
Hypotrachyna reducens
Hypotrachyna rockii
 **Hypotrachyna sanjosensis*
Hypotrachyna sinuosa
Hypotrachyna sorochaila
Hypotrachyna spumosa
Hypotrachyna subfatiscens
Hypotrachyna thysanota
Hypotrachyna vexans
Imshaugia angustior
Imshaugia venezolana
 **Menegazzia neotropica* var. *rotundicarpa*
Neoprotoparmelia brasiliensis
Oropogon americanus
Oropogon atranorinus
Oropogon barbaticus
Oropogon bicolor
 **Oropogon colibor*
Oropogon diffractaicus
Oropogon fissuratus
Oropogon formosanus
Oropogon granulatus
Oropogon halei
Oropogon lopezii
Oropogon lorobic
Oropogon loxensis
Oropogon sperlingii
 **Oropogon striatulus*
Parmelia acanthifolia
Parmelia hababiana
Parmelia hookeri
Parmelinella salacinifera
Parmotrema aberrans
Parmotrema affluens
Parmotrema arnoldii
Parmotrema cetratum
Parmotrema commensuratum
Parmotrema conformatum
Parmotrema crinitum
Parmotrema cristiferum
Parmotrema crocoides
Parmotrema dilatatum
Parmotrema ecliatum
Parmotrema endosulphureum
Parmotrema eurysacum
 **Parmotrema expansum*
Parmotrema flavescens
Parmotrema flavotinctum
Parmotrema fractum
Parmotrema grayanum
Parmotrema haitiense
Parmotrema latissimum
Parmotrema madagascariaceum
Parmotrema mellissii
Parmotrema michauxianum
Parmotrema neotropicum
Parmotrema peralbidum
Parmotrema perlutum
Parmotrema praesorediosum
Parmotrema rampoddense
Parmotrema reticulatum
Parmotrema rimulosum
Parmotrema robustum
Parmotrema rubificiens
Parmotrema sancti
Parmotrema simulans
Parmotrema stippeum

- Parmotrema subsidiosum*
Parmotrema subsumptum
Parmotrema sulphuratum
Parmotrema tinctorum
Parmotrema xanthinum
Parmotrema zollingeri
Parmotremopsis antillensis
Pseudevernia consocians
Pseudoparmelia amazonica
Pseudoparmelia caroliniana
Pseudoparmelia cubensis
Punctelia borrieri
Punctelia rudecta
Punctelia stictica
Punctelia subrudecta
Relicina abstrusa
Relicina limbata
Remototrachyna rhabdiformis
Usnea acanthella
Usnea articulata var. *asperula*
Usnea barbata var. *rubiginea*
Usnea ceratina
Usnea cornuta
Usnea dasypogoides var. *dasypodoides*
Usnea dasypogoides var. *exasperata*
Usnea durietzii
Usnea florida
Usnea jelskii
Usnea longissima
Usnea mirabilis
Usnea rubicunda
Usnea tenuis
Xanthoparmelia conspersa f. *conspersa*
Xanthoparmelia conspersa f. *isidiata*
Xanthoparmelia subramigera
Psilolechiaceae
Psilolechia lucida
Ramalinaceae
**Aciculopsora salmonea*
Auriculora byssomorpha
Bacidia artyoides
Bacidia consimilis
**Bacidia corallifera*
Bacidia costaricensis
Bacidia fusconigrescens
Bacidia granulifera
Bacidia heterochroa
Bacidia hostheleoides
Bacidia laurocerasi
Bacidia leptosporella
Bacidia lutea
Bacidia luteola
Bacidia lutescens
Bacidia millegrana
Bacidia palmularis
Bacidia pseudohyphophorifera
Bacidia psychotriae
Bacidia rosella
Bacidia subpulchra
Bacidia trachonella
Bacidia tuckermanii
Bacidia vezdana
Bacidina apiahica
Bacidina arvidssonii
Bacidina canariensis
Bacidina defecta
Bacidina hypophylla
Bacidina mirabilis
Bacidina pallidocarnea
Bacidina pseudohyphophorifera
Bacidina scutellifera
Badimia dimidiata
Badimia galbinea
**Badimia montoyana*
Badimia pallidula
Badimia stanhopeae
Badimia tuckermanii
**Badimia vezdana*
Bilimbia tricholoma
Crocynia pyxinoides
Eschatogonia prolifera
Lopezaria versicolor
**Lueckingia polyspora*
Parallopsora leucophyllina
Phyllopsora buettneri var. *glauca*
Phyllopsora chlorophaea
Phyllopsora confusa
Phyllopsora corallina
Phyllopsora corallina var. *santensis*
Phyllopsora fendleri
Phyllopsora furfuracea
Phyllopsora gossypina
Phyllopsora intermediella
Phyllopsora isidiotyta
Phyllopsora parvifolia var. *parvifolia*
Phyllopsora parvifoliella
Phyllopsora purpureascens
Phyllopsora rappiana
Physcidia wrightii
Ramalina alludens
Ramalina anceps
Ramalina celastri
Ramalina cochlearis
Ramalina complanata
Ramalina dendriscooides
Ramalina sorediantha
Ramalina subcalicaris
Ramalina tenuissima
Wolseleyidea ochroxantha
Ramboldiaceae
Ramboldia elabens
Ramboldia heterocarpa
Ramboldia russula
Sphaerophoraceae
Bunodophoron melanocarpum
Stereocaulaceae
Lepraria albicans
Lepraria arbuscula
Stereocaulon atlanticum
Stereocaulon claviceps
Stereocaulon cornutum
Stereocaulon crambidiocephalum
Stereocaulon delisei
**Stereocaulon didymicum*
Stereocaulon meyeri
Stereocaulon microcarpum
**Stereocaulon obesum*
Stereocaulon pityrizans
Stereocaulon ramulosum
Stereocaulon strictum var. *compressum*
Stereocaulon strictum var. *dstrictum*
Stereocaulon tomentosum
Stereocaulon vesuvianum
Stereocaulon cornutum var. *corallizans*
Tephromelataceae
Mycoblastus sanguinarius
Tephromela atra
Lecideales
Lecideaceae
Lecidea impressa f. *coeruleascens*
Lecidea impressa var. *angulosa*
Lecidea impressa var. *impressa*
Lecidea lapicida
Lecidea miniata
Lecidea piperis var. *erythroplaca*
Lecidea pseudomelana
Lecidea subaequata
Lecidea subemersa
Ostropales
Coenogoniaceae
Coenogonium aciculatum
Coenogonium bacilliferum
**Coenogonium barbatum*
**Coenogonium byssothallinum*
Coenogonium ciliatum
Coenogonium confervoides
Coenogonium congensense
Coenogonium depressum
Coenogonium dialeptizum
Coenogonium dilucidum
Coenogonium disjunctum
Coenogonium eximium
Coenogonium fallaciosum
Coenogonium flavicans
Coenogonium geralense
Coenogonium heterotrichum
Coenogonium hypophyllum
Coenogonium implexum
Coenogonium interplexum
Coenogonium interponendum
Coenogonium interpositum
Coenogonium isidiatum
**Coenogonium isidiferum*
Coenogonium isidiosum
**Coenogonium kalbii*
Coenogonium lepriurii
Coenogonium linkii
Coenogonium lisowskii
**Coenogonium luteocitrinum*
Coenogonium luteum
**Coenogonium magdalenae*
Coenogonium minimum
Coenogonium moniliforme
Coenogonium nepalense
Coenogonium pannosum
Coenogonium pusillum
Coenogonium roumeguerianum
**Coenogonium saepincola*
Coenogonium siquirrense f. *denticulatum*
Coenogonium stenosporum
**Coenogonium strigosum*
Coenogonium subdentatum
Coenogonium subdilutum
Coenogonium subluteum
Coenogonium subvirescens
**Coenogonium subzonatum*
Coenogonium tuckermanii
Coenogonium vezdanum
**Coenogonium wernerhuberi*
Coenogonium zonatum
Dimerella citrina
Dimerella epiphylla
Dimerella lisowskii
Dimerella usambarensis
Graphidaceae
Acanthothecis hololeuroides
Acanthothecis pepliphora
**Acanthotrema bicellulare*
Acanthotrema brasilianum
**Acanthotrema kalbii*
Allographa acharii
Allographa adpressa
**Allographa altamirensis*
Allographa aquilonia
**Allographa argentata*
Allographa balbisii

- *Allographa bettinae*
Allographa carassensis
Allographa chlorocarpa
Allographa chrysocarpa
Allographa cinerea
Allographa cleistoblephara
Allographa consanguinea
Allographa farinulenta
**Allographa firferi*
Allographa flavens
**Allographa flavoaltamirensis*
**Allographa flavominiata*
**Allographa fourmieri*
**Allographa gomezii*
**Allographa gregmuelleri*
Allographa illinata
Allographa ingarum
**Allographa inspersostictica*
Allographa inturgescens
Allographa leprographa
Allographa longula
Allographa lumbricina
Allographa macella
Allographa miniata
**Allographa mirabilis*
Allographa multisulcata
Allographa nuda
**Allographa nudaeformis*
Allographa ochracea
Allographa ovata
Allographa pavoniana
Allographa phaeospora
**Allographa pittieri*
Allographa plurispora
**Allographa pseudocinerea*
Allographa rhizicola
Allographa rimulosa
Allographa ruiziana
Allographa rustica
Allographa sauroidea
**Allographa seminuda*
Allographa sitiana
Allographa striatula
**Allographa subflexibilis*
**Allographa subruiziana*
**Allographa subturgidula*
Allographa triphora
Allographa tumidula
Allographa vestitoides
Ampliotrema amplius
**Ampliotrema cocosense*
**Ampliotrema dactylizum*
Ampliotrema discolor
Ampliotrema lepadinoides
Ampliotrema palaeoamplius
Ampliotrema panamense
**Anomomorpha tuberculata*
Asteristion platycarpoides
Asteristion platycarpum
Astrochapsa astroidea
Astrochapsa lassae
Astrochapsa meridensis
Astrochapsa platycarpella
Carbacanthographis chionophora
Chapsa albida
Chapsa alborosella
Chapsa chionostoma
Chapsa cinchonarum
**Chapsa defecta*
**Chapsa defectosorediata*
Chapsa discoides
Chapsa dissuta
**Chapsa farinosa*
Chapsa hiata
Chapsa meridensis
Chapsa neei
**Chapsa perdissuta*
Chapsa referta
**Chapsa sublilacina*
**Chapsa thalotrema*
Chroodiscus argillaceus
Chroodiscus australiensis
Chroodiscus coccineus
Chroodiscus mirificus
Chroodiscus neotropicus
**Chroodiscus submuralis*
**Clandestinotrema analorenae*
Clandestinotrema antoninii
Clandestinotrema cathomalizans
Clandestinotrema clandestinum
Clandestinotrema erumpens
Clandestinotrema leucomelaenum
Clandestinotrema pauperius
Clandestinotrema stylothecium
Clandestinotrema tenue
Cruentotrema cruentatum
Cryptoschizotrema cryptotrema
Cyclographina hologlauca
Diorygma confluens
Diorygma junghuhni
Diorygma poitaei
Diorygma pruinsum
Diorygma reniforme
Diploschistes actinostomus
Diploschistes bartlettii
Diploschistes cinereocaesius
Diploschistes diacapsis
Diploschistes muscorum
Diploschistes scruposus
Dyplolabia afzelii
**Enigmotrema rubrum*
Fibrillithecis confusa
Fibrillithecis insignis
Fibrillithecis pachystoma
Fissurina adscribens
Fissurina cingalina
Fissurina dumastii
Fissurina dumastioides
**Fissurina subcorallina*
Glaucotrema costaricense
Glaucotrema glaucophaenum
Glyphis cicatricosa
Glyphis confluens f. analoga
Glyphis confluens f. confluens
Glyphis cribrosa
Glyphis favulosa var. intermedia
Glyphis scyphulifera
Glyphis triseptata
Graphina acharii var. vestita
**Graphina acromelaena*
Graphina anguina
Graphina antillarum
Graphina collatinensis
Graphina dimidiata
Graphina hiascens
Graphina incrustans
**Graphina interstes*
Graphina marcescens
Graphina obtectula
Graphina parilis
Graphina platycarpa
**Graphina robusta*
Graphina sophistica
Graphina vermicula
Graphina vestitoides
Graphina virginea
Graphis analoga
Graphis anfractuosa
Graphis anguilliformis
Graphis antillarum
Graphis assimilis
Graphis bipartita
Graphis caesiella
Graphis caesiocarpa
Graphis caribica
Graphis chlorotica
Graphis chondroplaca
Graphis dendrogramma
Graphis dichotoma
Graphis disserpens
Graphis dracaenae
Graphis dupaxana
Graphis duplicata
Graphis duplicata var. duplicata
Graphis duplicata var. sublaevis
**Graphis duplicatoinpersa*
Graphis elegans
Graphis elongatoradians
Graphis emersa
Graphis flexibilis
Graphis furcata
Graphis geraensis
Graphis glaucescens
Graphis glaucocaesia
Graphis gracilis
Graphis granulosa
Graphis haleana
Graphis hyphosa
**Graphis hypocrellina*
Graphis insulana
Graphis leptocarpa
Graphis leptoclada
Graphis leuconephala
Graphis librata
Graphis lineola
**Graphis litoralis*
Graphis lucifica
Graphis marginata
Graphis mexicana
Graphis myrtacea
Graphis nuda
**Graphis oryzaecarpa*
Graphis oxyclada
**Graphis paradisserpens*
**Graphis paraserpens*
Graphis parilis
Graphis perstriatula
Graphis plagiocarpa
Graphis platycarpella
Graphis proserpens
**Graphis pseudoserpens*
Graphis puiggarii
Graphis rockii
Graphis schiffneri
Graphis scripta
Graphis seminuda var. seminuda
Graphis seminuda var. sublaevis
Graphis stenotera
Graphis subchrysocarpa
Graphis subcontorta
Graphis subhiascens
Graphis submarginata
Graphis subrufula
**Graphis superpecta*
Graphis symplecta
**Graphis syzygii*

- Graphis tenella*
Graphis tenellula
 **Graphis tenoriensis*
Graphis triticea
Graphis virescens
Graphis vittata
Graphis xylophaga
 **Gyrotrema aurantiacum*
 **Gyrotrema papillatum*
 **Gyrotrema wirthii*
Leiorreuma exaltatum
Leiorreuma sericeum
Leptotrema compunctum var. *purpuratum*
 **Leucodecton album*
Leucodecton bisporum
Leucodecton compunctellum
Leucodecton compunctum
Leucodecton fissurinum
Leucodecton glaucescens
Leucodecton occultum
Leucodecton sordidescens
Leucodecton subcompunctum
Melanotrema platystomum
 **Myriotrema aggregans*
Myriotrema barroense
Myriotrema calvescens
 **Myriotrema clandestinoides*
Myriotrema clandestinum
 **Myriotrema classicum*
Myriotrema compunctum
Myriotrema concretum
Myriotrema congestum
 **Myriotrema frondosolucens*
Myriotrema hartii
Myriotrema microporum
Myriotrema minutulum
Myriotrema myrioporoides
Myriotrema myriotremoides
Myriotrema neofrondosum
Myriotrema olivaceum
Myriotrema plurifarium
Myriotrema protocetraricum
Myriotrema reclusum
Myriotrema rugiferum
Myriotrema subconforme
Myriotrema subcostaricense
Myriotrema terebratulum
Myriotrema thailandicum
Myriotrema urceolare
Myriotrema viridialbum
Nadvornikia expallescens
Nadvornikia hawaiiensis
Nitidochapsa lepreurii
Ocellularia alba
 **Ocellularia albobullata*
Ocellularia albocincta
Ocellularia antillensis
Ocellularia ascidioidea
 **Ocellularia auratipruinosa*
Ocellularia aurulenta
Ocellularia bahiana
Ocellularia cavata
Ocellularia chiriquiensis
Ocellularia cinchonarum
 **Ocellularia cocosensis*
Ocellularia comparabilis
Ocellularia conformis
Ocellularia conglomerata
 **Ocellularia cryptica*
Ocellularia diptotrema
Ocellularia dolichotata
Ocellularia domingensis
Ocellularia fecunda
 **Ocellularia flavoperforata*
 **Ocellularia gerardoii*
 **Ocellularia globifera*
 **Ocellularia inspersata*
 **Ocellularia inspersula*
Ocellularia interposita
Ocellularia inturgescens
 **Ocellularia isohypocrellina*
 **Ocellularia laevigatula*
Ocellularia laeviuscula
 **Ocellularia laeviusculoides*
Ocellularia landronii
Ocellularia mauritiana
Ocellularia maxima
Ocellularia mordenii
Ocellularia obturascens
Ocellularia papillata
Ocellularia perforata
 **Ocellularia phlyctellacea*
Ocellularia pluriporoides
Ocellularia praestans
 **Ocellularia praestantoides*
 **Ocellularia pseudopyrenuloides*
 **Ocellularia psorbarroensis*
Ocellularia pyrenuloides
Ocellularia rhodostroma
Ocellularia ripleyi
 **Ocellularia rufocincta*
Ocellularia stictica
Ocellularia subpraestans
 **Ocellularia subpyrenuloides*
 **Ocellularia supergracilis*
Ocellularia terebrata
 **Ocellularia terrabensis*
 **Ocellularia umbilicata*
Ocellularia vezdana
Ocellularia violacea
Ocellularia xanthostroma
 **Ocellularia zamorana*
Pallidogramme chrysenteron
Phaeographina caesiopruinosa
Phaeographina scalpturata var. *dissimilis*
Phaeographina scalpturata var. *scalpturata*
Phaeographina strigops
Phaeographis asteroides
Phaeographis caesiodisca
Phaeographis caestoradians
Phaeographis concinna
Phaeographis dendritica var. *abbreviata*
Phaeographis dendritica var. *dendritica*
Phaeographis haematites var. *brachycarpa*
Phaeographis haematites var. *haematite*
Phaeographis inconspicua
Phaeographis inusta
Phaeographis leiogrammodes
Phaeographis lindigiana
Phaeographis lobata
Phaeographis lyellii
Phaeographis punctiformis
Phaeographis rhodoplaca
Phaeographis simpliciuscula
Phaeographis spondaica
Phaeographis subtigrina
Phaeotrema isidiiferum
Platygramme praestans
Platythecium allosporium
Platythecium graminis
Platythecium pyrrochroum
Pseudochapsa dilatata
Pseudochapsa phlyctidioides
Pseudochapsa pseudoschizostoma
Pseudotopeliopsis laceratula
Pycnotrema pycnoporellum
Redingeria glyphica
Redingeria microspora
Reimmitzia santensis
Rhabdodiscus crassus
Rhabdodiscus emersus
Rhabdodiscus granulosus
Rhabdodiscus isidiifer
Rhabdodiscus lankaensis
Rhabdodiscus subcavatus
Rhabdodiscus subemersus
Sanguinotrema wightii
Sarcographa caesia
Sarcographa cinchonarum
Sarcographa feii
Sarcographa heteroclitia
Sarcographa intricans
Sarcographa labyrinthica var. *labyrinthica*
Sarcographa labyrinthica var. *maculiformis*
Sarcographa medusulina
Sarcographa ramificans
Sarcographa tricosia
 **Schistophoron aurantiacum*
 **Schistophoron variabile*
Schizotrema guadeloupense
Siegobolus anamorphaeoides
Siegobolus auberianus
Siegobolus fissus
Siegobolus metaphoricus
Siegobolus percolumellatus
Siegobolus radians
Siegobolus schizostomus
Siegobolus wrightii
 **Thallolooma astroideum*
Thallolooma buriticum
Thelotrema adjectum
Thelotrema conglomeratum
 **Thelotrema gomezianum*
Thelotrema lacteum
Thelotrema lepadinum
Thelotrema lepadodes
Thelotrema monosporum
Thelotrema pachysporum
Thelotrema porinoides
 **Thelotrema submyriocarpum*
Thelotrema subtile
Thelotrema suecicum
 **Thelotrema velatum*
 **Thelotrema wilsoniorum*
Wirthiotrema desquamans
Wirthiotrema duplomarginatum
Wirthiotrema glaucopallens
Wirthiotrema trypaneoides
Phlyctidaceae
Phlyctella andensis
Phlyctidia brasiliensis
Phlyctis boliviensis
Phlyctis subregularis
Porinaceae
Clathroporina isidiifera
Clathroporina mastoidea
 **Flabelloporina squamulifera*
Myeloconis fecunda
Porina africana
Porina alba
Porina albidia
 **Porina andreana*
Porina aspera
Porina atriceps
 **Porina atropunctata*
 **Porina barvica*

- Porina cubana*
Porina curtula
Porina distans
Porina dolichophora
Porina eminentior
Porina epimelaena
Porina epiphylla
Porina exasperatula
**Porina flavopapillata*
Porina fulvella
**Porina fusca*
Porina guianensis
Porina imitatrix
Porina karnatakensis
Porina leptosperma
Porina leptospermoides
Porina limbulata
Porina lucida
Porina lucida var. lucida
**Porina mirabilis*
**Porina moralesiae*
Porina nilgiriensis
Porina nitens
Porina nucula
Porina nuculastrum
Porina ornata
Porina pallidochlorina
Porina papillifera
Porina peraffinis
Porina pichinchensis
**Porina pilifera*
Porina pseudoapplanata
Porina radiata
Porina repanda
Porina rubescens
Porina rubrosphaera
Porina rudiucula
Porina rufula
Porina simulans
**Porina subepiphylla*
Porina subepiphylla var. dubepiphylla
Porina subinterstes
Porina tetracerae
Porina tetramera
Porina tijucana
Porina tonduziana
Porina verruculosa
**Porina vezdae*
Pseudosagedia atrocoerulea
**Pseudosagedia laticarpa*
Pseudosagedia nitidula
Pseudosagedia thaxteri
Pseudosagedia umbilicata
Trichothelium akeassii
Trichothelium alboatrum
**Trichothelium album*
Trichothelium amazonense
Trichothelium annulatum
**Trichothelium argenteum*
Trichothelium asplundii
Trichothelium bipindense
Trichothelium brasiliense
**Trichothelium chlorinum*
Trichothelium daryi
**Trichothelium echinocarpum*
**Trichothelium epiphyllum var. minuntum*
Trichothelium horridulum
Trichothelium javanicum
Trichothelium juruense
**Trichothelium longisporum*
**Trichothelium mirum*
**Trichothelium montanum f. latisporum*
Trichothelium montanum f. montanum
Trichothelium pallescens
**Trichothelium pallidisetum*
**Trichothelium poeltii*
Trichothelium porinoides
**Trichothelium rubescens*
**Trichothelium sipmanii*
**Trichothelium sipmanii f. multiseptatum*
Trichothelium sipmanii f. sipmanii
Trichothelium ulei
**Trichothelium wirthii*
Stictidaceae
Absconditella delutula
Diderma radiatum
Thelenellaceae
**Aspidothelium arachnoideum*
**Aspidothelium glabrum*
Aspidothelium ornatum
**Aspidothelium papillicarpum*
Aspidothelium scutelliscarpum
Aspidothelium trichothelioides
Julella geminella
Microglaena saxicola
Thelenella brasiliensis
Thelenella cinerascens
Thelenella fugiens
Thelenella geminipara
Peltigerales
Coccocarpiaceae
Coccocarpia adnata
Coccocarpia dissecta
Coccocarpia domingensis
Coccocarpia epiphylla
Coccocarpia erythrocardia
Coccocarpia erythroxyli
Coccocarpia filiformis
**Coccocarpia gallaicoi*
Coccocarpia glaucina
Coccocarpia guimarana
Coccocarpia imbricascens
**Coccocarpia microphyllina*
**Coccocarpia neglecta*
Coccocarpia palmicola
Coccocarpia pellita
**Coccocarpia prostrata*
Coccocarpia stellata
**Coccocarpia tenuissima*
Collemataceae
Collema callibotrys var. coccophyllizum
Collema conglomeratum var. crassiusculum
Collema furfuraceum var. furfuraceum
Collema glaucophthalmum var. glaucophthalmum
Collema implicatum
Collema leptaleum var. biliosum
Collema leptaleum var. leptalaeum
Collema nigrescens
Collema pulchellum var. leucopeplum
Leptogium andinum
Leptogium austroamericanum
Leptogium azureum
Leptogium bullatum
Leptogium burgessii
Leptogium chloromelum
Leptogium coralloideum
Leptogium cyanescens
Leptogium denticulatum
Leptogium diaphanum
Leptogium digitatum
Leptogium foveolatum
Leptogium furfuraceum
Leptogium granadilla
Leptogium hibernicum
Leptogium inflexum var. inflexum
Leptogium juressianum
Leptogium laceroides
Leptogium mandonii
Leptogium marginellum
Leptogium microstictum
Leptogium moluccanum
Leptogium nylanderii
Leptogium olivaceum
Leptogium olivaceum var. granulosum
Leptogium olivaceum var. olivaceum
Leptogium papillosum
Leptogium phyllocarpum
Leptogium phyllocarpum var. campestre
Leptogium phyllocarpum var. macrocarpum
Leptogium phyllocarpum var. phyllocarpum
Leptogium punctulatum
Leptogium resupinans
Leptogium reticulatum
Leptogium simplicius var. pichneoides
Leptogium simplicius var. simplicius
**Leptogium standleyi*
Leptogium stipitatum
Leptogium tremelloides
Leptogium tuckermanii
Leptogium vesiculosum var. vesiculosum
Lobariaceae
Lobaria albida
Lobaria deplanata
Lobaria pulmonaria
Lobaria submultiseriata
**Lobariella coralophora*
Lobariella crenulata
Lobariella exornata
Lobariella pallida
Lobariella pallidocrenulata
**Lobariella papillifera*
**Lobariella rugulosa*
**Lobariella spathulifera*
**Lobariella subcrenolata*
**Lobariella subexornata*
Pseudocyphellaria aurata
Pseudocyphellaria citrina
Pseudocyphellaria crocata
Pseudocyphellaria dozyana
Pseudocyphellaria mougeotiana var. aurigera
Pseudocyphellaria sandwicensis
Pseudocyphellaria xanthosticta
Ricasolia amplissima
Ricasolia quercizans
Sticta cometiella
Sticta damaecornis
Sticta ferax
Sticta filicinella
Sticta fuliginosa
Sticta gyalocarpa
Sticta howei
Sticta humboldtii
Sticta isidioidichotoma
Sticta laciniata
Sticta laciniosa
Sticta laselvae
Sticta macrophylla
Sticta peruviana
Sticta rufa f. hypogymna
Sticta rufa f. rufa
Sticta tomentosa
Sticta weigeli
Yoshimuriella carassensis
Yoshimuriella corrosa
Yoshimuriella denudata

- Yoshimuriella dissecta*
Yoshimuriella fendleri
Yoshimuriella subdissecta
Nephromataceae
Nephroma helveticum
Pannariaceae
Erioderma barbellatum
Erioderma chilense
Erioderma gloriosum
Erioderma granulatum
Erioderma marcellii
Erioderma mollissimum
Erioderma physcioides
Erioderma sorediatum
Erioderma verruculosum
Erioderma wrightii
Leioderma sorediatum
Lepidocollema stylophorum
Leptogidium dendriscum
Nebularia incrassata
Pannaria andina
Pannaria caesiocinerea
Pannaria conoplea
Pannaria isidioides
**Pannaria isidioides var. pulvinata*
Pannaria mosenii
Pannaria prolificans
Pannaria radiata
Pannaria rubiginosa
Pannaria tavaresii
Pannaria vainioi
Parmeliella clavulifera
**Parmeliella isidiopannosa*
Parmeliella miradorensis
Parmeliella pannosa
**Parmeliella pannosa var. coralloidea*
Parmeliella stylophora
Physma byrsaeum
Physma pruinosum
Peltigeraceae
Emmanuelia erosa
Emmanuelia patinifera
Peltigera austroamericana
Peltigera collina
Peltigera didactyla
Peltigera dolichorhiza
Peltigera laciniata
Peltigera praetextata
Peltigera pulverulenta
Peltigera soredians
Peltigera ulcerata
Placynthiaceae
Placynthium nigrum
Pertusariales
Coccotremataceae
Parasiphula complanata
Icmadophilaceae
Dibaeis absoluta
Dibaeis columbina
Dibaeis globulifera
Dibaeis holstii
Icmadophila adversum
Icmadophila ericetorum
Siphula ceratites
Siphula decumbens
Siphula fastigiata
Siphula pteruloides
Thamnolia vermicularis
Ochrolechiaceae
Ochrolechia havaiensis
Ochrolechia pallescens
Pertusariaceae
Pertusaria apiculata
Pertusaria borealis
Pertusaria copiosa
Pertusaria lepida
Pertusaria leucothallina
Pertusaria mesotropa
Pertusaria pertusa
Pertusaria pustulata
Pertusaria tetrathalamia
Pertusaria texana
Pertusaria torulosa
**Phyllophiale fusca*
Phyllophiale viridis
Segestria octomera
Segestria rubentior
Varicellariaceae
Varicellaria culbersonii
Varicellaria lactea
Varicellaria velata
Rhizocarpales
Rhizocarpaceae
Epilichen scabrosus
Rhizocarpon geographicum var. atrovirens
Rhizocarpon obscuratum
Teloschistales
Brigantiaeaceae
Brigantiaea leucoxantha
Letrouitiaceae
Letrouitia domingensis
Letrouitia flavidula
**Letrouitia spiralis*
Letrouitia vulpina
Megalosporaceae
Megaloblastenia marginiflexa var. dimota
Megalospora admixta
Megalospora sulphurata subsp. sulphurata
Megalospora sulphurata var. nigricans
Megalospora tuberculosa
Sipmaniella sulfureofusca
Teloschistaceae
Blastenia tonduziana
Callospisma aurantiacum var. diffractum
Callospisma cinnabarinum f. isidiosum
Callospisma immersum
Callospisma subsquamosum
**Callospisma tetramerum*
Caloplaca aphanotripta
Flavoplaca citrina
Huneckia pollinii
Seawardiella lobulata
Teloschistes exilis
Teloschistes flavicans
Xanthoria elegans
Family Incertae sedis
Malcolmiella psychotrioides
Umbilicariales
Fuscideaceae
Fuscidea recensa
Ophioparmaceae
Hypocenomyce scalaris
Umbilicariaceae
Umbilicaria leprosa
Order Incertae sedis
Arthrorhaphidaceae
Arthrorhaphis alpina
Leotiomyces
Chaetomellales
Chaetomellaceae
Chaetomella raphigera
**Hainesia aurantii*
Helotiales
Bloxamiaceae
Bloxamia leucophthalma
Cenangiaceae
Clithris platyplacum
Chlorociboriaceae
Chlorociboria aeruginascens
Chlorociboria aeruginosa
Dermateaceae
**Dermatella mirabilis*
Drepanopezizaceae
Gloeosporium orbiculare
Erysiphaceae
Erysiphe buhrii
Erysiphe diffusa
Erysiphe necator
Erysiphe polygoni
Erysiphe quercicola
Fibroidium tingitaninum
Golovinomyces chrysanthemi
Golovinomyces lycopersici
Leveillula taurica
Oidium bixae
Oidium caricae-papayae
Oidium cococarum
Oidium mangiferae
Oidium manihotis
**Ovulariopsis farinosa*
Podospaera fuliginea
Podospaera leucotricha
Pseudoidium caricae
Pseudoidium hortensiae
Pseudoidium poinsettiae
Gelatinodiscaceae
Ascocoryne sarcoides
Helotiaceae
Bisporella citrina
Gloeotinia temulenta
Hyaloscyphaceae
Dematioscypha catenata
Hyaloscypha hepaticicola
Lachnaceae
**Belonidium spilogenum*
Erioscyphella abnormis
Erioscyphella brasiliensis
Lachnum apalum
Mollisiaceae
Trimmatostroma cordae
Pezizellaceae
Chalara brachyspora
Chalara cylindrosperma
Ploettnerulaceae
Cylindrosporium angustifoliae
Cylindrosporium bambusae
Pyrenopeziza brassicae
Sclerotiniaceae
Botryotinia squamosa
Botrytis allii
Botrytis cinerea
Martininia panamaensis
Monilinia fructigena
Sclerotinia minor
Sclerotinia sclerotiorum
Stromatinia cepivora
Vibrisseaceae
**Pocillum concinnum*
Family Incertae sedis
**Bioscypha cyatheae*
Dactylaria acerosa
Dactylaria chrysoesperma
Dactylaria curvispora
Dactylaria fusiformis
Dactylaria humicola
Dactylaria obscuriseptata

- *Pezolepis denigrata*
Phaeofabraea lachnoides
**Pseudospiropes costaricensis*
Scytalidium lignicola
Scytalidium sphaerosporum
Strossmayeria bakeriana
Tetracladium breve
Tetracladium maxilliforme
Tetracladium setigerum
**Triposporium aurantii*
Leotiales
Leotiaceae
Leotia lubrica
Tympanidaceae
**Pleurophomella mirabilis*
Marthamycetales
Marthamycetaceae
Marthamyces quadrifidus
Phacidiales
Helicogoniaceae
Callorhiza herpotricha
Phacidiaceae
Strasseria geniculata
Rhytismatales
Rhytismataceae
Cerion leucophaeum
Coccomyces clusiae
**Lophodermium andropogonis*
Lophodermium arundinaceum
Lichinomycetes
Lichinales
Lichinaceae
Ephebe lanata
**Lempholemma dichotomum*
Lempholemma oblique
Leprocollema novocaledonianum
Thermutis velutina

Orbiliomycetes
Orbiliales
Orbiliaceae
Arthrobotrys megalosporus
Arthrobotrys sinensis
Dicranidion fragile
Orbilia aureocrenulata
Orbilia gaillardii
Trinacrium tropicale
Pezizomycetes
Pezizales
Ascobolaceae
Ascobolus carbonarius
Ascobolus furfuraceus
Ascobolus immersus
Saccobolus versicolor
Ascodesmidaceae
Lasiobolus papillatus
Chorioactidaceae
Desmazierella acicola
Discinaceae
**Gyromitra chirripenensis*
Gyromitra esculenta
Gyromitra infula
Glaziellaceae
Glaziella aurantiaca
Helvellaceae
Helvella albella
Helvella crispa
Helvella fibrosa
Helvella lactea
Helvella lacunosa
Helvella latispora

Helvella macropus
Helvella pezizoides
Helvella solitaria
Morchellaceae
Morchella elata
Morchella esculenta
**Morchella herediana*
Verpa conica
Otideaceae
Otidea alutacea
Otidea bufonia
Otidea onotica
Pezizaceae
Adelphella babingtonii
Iodophanus carneus
Pachyella clypeata
Peziza atrovinosa
Pyronemataceae
Acervus flavidus
Aleuria aurantia
Anthracobia melaloma
Cheilymenia coprinaria
Cheilymenia fimicola
Cheilymenia granulata
Cheilymenia theleboloides
Humaria hemisphaerica
Melastiza rubra
Octosporella epiphylla
**Octosporella radulae*
Plicaria trachycarpa
Pyronema omphalodes
Scutellinia asperrima
Scutellinia balansae
Scutellinia blumenaviensis
Scutellinia crinita
Scutellinia cubensis
Scutellinia erinaceus
Scutellinia heimii
Scutellinia inexpectata
Scutellinia kerguelensis
Scutellinia nigrohirtula
Scutellinia patagonica
Scutellinia pennsylvanica
Scutellinia scutellata
Scutellinia setosa
Scutellinia setosissima
Scutellinia umbrorum
Sarcoscyphaceae
Aurophora dochmia
Cookeina colensoi
Cookeina speciosa
Cookeina sulcipes
Cookeina tricholoma
Cookeina venezuelae
**Geodina guanacastensis*
**Nanoscypha macrospora*
**Nanoscypha pulchra*
**Nanoscypha tetraspora*
**Phillipsia costaricensis*
Phillipsia crispata
Phillipsia domingensis
Phillipsia hartmannii
**Phillipsia lutea*
Phillipsia olivacea
**Phillipsia rugospora*
Pithya cupressina
Pithya vulgaris
Sarcoscypha occidentalis
Sarcosomataceae
Plectania rhytidia
**Pseudoplectania carranzae*
Wynneaceae
Wynnea americana
Wynnea gigantea
Family Incertae sedis
**Coprotus marginatus*
Psilopezia nummularia
Psilopezia juruensis
Order Incertae sedis
Pseudombrophilaceae
Pseudombrophila hepatica
Saccharomycetes
Saccharomycetales
Debaryomycetaceae
Meyerozyma guilliermondii
Dipodascaceae
Dipodascus geotrichum
Yarrowia lipolytica
Eremotheciaceae
Eremothecium coryli
Lipomycetaceae
**Myxozyma neotropica*
Metschnikowiaceae
Clavispora lusitaniae
**Metschnikowia colocasiae*
**Metschnikowia dekortorum*
Metschnikowia hawaiiiana
Metschnikowia koreensis
**Metschnikowia lochheadii*
Metschnikowia rancensis
**Metschnikowia santaceciliae*
**Metschnikowia similis*
Saccharomycetaceae
Debaryomyces hansenii
Lodderomyces elongisporus
Ogataea falcaomoraisii
Schwannomyces polymorphus
Trichomonascaceae
Wickerhamiella parazyza
Trigonopsidaceae
**Tortispora cuajiniquilana*
**Tortispora sangerardonensis*
Family Incertae sedis
Candida albicans
Candida boidinii
**Candida galis*
Candida intermedia
Candida leandrae
Candida metapsilosis
**Candida ortonii*
Candida quercitrusa
Candida saopaulonensis
Hyphopichia burtonii
Kodamaea ohmeri
Starmerella apicola
Starmerella bombicola
**Starmerella roubikii*
**Starmerella vitae*
Sordariomycetes
Amphisphaeriales
Amphisphaeriaceae
Beltraniella portoricensis
Melioliphila adiantii
Melioliphila volutella
Microdochium albescens
Microdochium bolleyi
Microdochium maydis
Microdochium musae
Pestalotiopsidaceae
Ciliochorella mangiferae
Neopestalotiopsis clavispora
Neopestalotiopsis rosae
Pestalotia longisetula
Pestalotia theobromae

- Pestalotiopsis batatas*
Pestalotiopsis coffeae
Pestalotiopsis finerea
Pestalotiopsis gossypii
Pestalotiopsis gracilis
Pestalotiopsis guepinii
Pestalotiopsis mangiferae
Pestalotiopsis microspora
Pestalotiopsis neglecta
Pestalotiopsis paeonicola
Pestalotiopsis palmarum
Pestalotiopsis papposa
Pestalotiopsis psidii
Pestalotiopsis subcuticularis
Pestalotiopsis sydowiana
Pestalotiopsis vismiae
Pseudopestalotiopsis theae
Seiridium anceps
Seiridium cardinale
Sporocadaceae
Coryneopsis microsticta
Amplistromatales
Amplistromataceae
**Amplistroma hallingii*
**Amplistroma ravum*
Annulatascales
Annulatasceae
Annulusmagnus triseptatus
Ayria nubispora
Cyanoannulus petersenii
Longicollum biappendiculatum
Pseudoannulatascus biatriisporus
Torrentispora biatriispora
Torrentispora crassiparietis
**Torrentispora pilosa*
**Verticicola ascoliberatus*
Boliniales
Boliniaceae
**Apiocamarops pulvinata*
Chaetosphaeriales
Chaetosphaeriaceae
Arcuatospora novae-zelandiae
Catenularia cubensis
Chaetoseptoria wellmanii
Chaetosphaeria capitata
Chaetosphaeria chalaroides
Chaetosphaeria chlorotunicata
**Chaetosphaeria conirostris*
Chaetosphaeria cylindrospora
Chaetosphaeria innumera
**Chaetosphaeria lapaziana*
Chaetosphaeria lignomollis
Chaetosphaeria longiseta
Chaetosphaeria meliolicola
Chaetosphaeria raciborskii
**Chaetosphaeria rubicunda*
Chaetosphaeria tropicalis
Chaetosphaeria vermicularioides
Chloridium chloroconium
Chloridium phaeosporum var. *cubense*
**Codinaea delicata*
Craspedodidymum cubense
Craspedodidymum proliferans
Cylindrotrichum oligospermum
Dictyochaeta gamundii
Dictyochaeta parva
Miyoshiella triseptata
**Paragaemannomyces lapazianus*
Paragaemannomyces raciborskii
Paragaemannomyces rubicundus
Phaeostalagmus altissimus
Phaeostalagmus cyclosporus
Sporoschisma hemipsilum
Sporoschisma nigroseptatum
Striatosphaeria codinaeaphora
Thozetella radicata
Coniochaetales
Coniochaetaceae
**Coniochaeta cipronana*
Cordanales
Cordanaceae
Cordana abramovii
Cordana crassa
Coronophorales
Bertiaceae
Bertia didyma
**Bertia orbis*
Bertia tropicalis
Chaetosphaerellaceae
Chaetosphaerella phaeostroma
Crassochaeta nigrita
Nitschkiaceae
Fracchiacea broomeana
Nitschkia acanthostroma
Nitschkia collapsa
Scortechiniaceae
**Pseudocryptosphaerella costaricensis*
Diaporthales
Apharknessiaceae
Apharknessia insueta
Cryphonectriaceae
Chrysosporthe cubensis
Diaporthaceae
Diaporthe amygdali
Diaporthe anacardii
Diaporthe annonacearum
Diaporthe caricae-papayae
Diaporthe citri
Diaporthe cucurbitae
Diaporthe neoviticola
Diaporthe phaseolorum
Diaporthe pierocarpi
Diaporthe tulliensis
**Mazzantia arundinellae*
Phomoposis longicolla
Phomopsis asparagi
**Phomopsis bicincta*
**Phomopsis machaeriticola*
Phomopsis mangiferae
Phomopsis obscurans
Phomopsis orchidophila
Phomopsis oryzae-sativae
Phomopsis rubiseda
Phomopsis vexans
Erythroglloeaceae
**Erythroglloeum hymenaeae*
Gnomoniaceae
**Laestadia coffeicola*
**Laestadia linearis*
**Phylloporthe vernoniae*
Valsaceae
Cytospora sacchari
Family Incertae sedis
Botryodiplodia circinans
Botryodiplodia palmarum
Botryodiplodia pandani
**Pachytrype rimosa*
Pseudothis machaerii
Stenocarpella macrospora
Stenocarpella maydis
Melanconidaceae
**Plagiostigme couraliae*
Glomerellales
Glomerellaceae
Colletotrichum acutatum
Colletotrichum anthurii
Colletotrichum boninense
Colletotrichum brevisporum
Colletotrichum caricae
Colletotrichum circinans
Colletotrichum coccoades
Colletotrichum coffeanum
**Colletotrichum costaricense*
Colletotrichum crassipes
Colletotrichum dematium
Colletotrichum elasticae
Colletotrichum falcatum
**Colletotrichum filicis*
Colletotrichum fragariae
Colletotrichum fructicola
**Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*
Colletotrichum graminicola
Colletotrichum guajavae
Colletotrichum higginsianum
Colletotrichum kahawae
Colletotrichum karsti
Colletotrichum lindemuthianum
Colletotrichum lupini
Colletotrichum magnum
Colletotrichum manihotis
Colletotrichum musae
Colletotrichum nymphaeae
**Colletotrichum radicis*
Colletotrichum sansevieriae
Colletotrichum tabacum
Colletotrichum theobromicola
Colletotrichum trifolii
Colletotrichum tropicale
Colletotrichum truncatum
Colletotrichum zingiberis
**Haplothecium dioscorea*
Plectosphaerellaceae
Musicillium theobromae
Verticillium albo-atrum
Hypocreales
Bionectriaceae
**Anthonectria mammispora*
Bionectria lasiacidis
Bionectria setosa
Bionectria byssicola
Bionectria grammicospora
Bionectria ochroleuca
Bionectria pityrodes
Bionectria sporodochialis
**Bryocentria aequinoctialis*
Bryocentria cyanodesma
Bryocentria gynophila
**Bryocentria manubriata*
**Bryocentria merospora*
**Bryocentria perianthiicola*
**Bryonectria calopoda*
**Bryonectria clandestina*
**Bryonectria cyclopoda*
**Bryonectria lobopoda*
Clonostachys cylindrospora
Clonostachys rosea
Clonostachys tonduzii
**Dendrodochium gouaniae*
Dimerosporiella pipericola
Nectriopsis oropensoides
Ochronectria calami
Peristomialis berkeleyi
Protocreopsis fusigera
Protocreopsis pertusa
Septofusidium variabilis
Clavicipitaceae

- *Aciculosporium monostipum*
Aschersonia basicystis
Aschersonia cubensis
Aschersonia goldiana
Aschersonia placentia
Aschersonia aleyrodis
Aschersonia incrassata
Aschersonia parasitica
**Aschersonia pittieri*
Aschersonia turbinata
Balansia strangulans
**Balansia chusqueicola*
Balansia claviceps
Balansia discoidea
Claviceps paspali
Claviceps ranunculoides
Epichloe bertonii
**Harposporium fuscum*
Harposporium peltatum
**Hyperdermium pulvinatum*
Hypocrella andropogonis
Hypocrella citrina
Hypocrella disciformis
Hypocrella viridans
Linearistroma lineare
Marquandomyces marquandii
Metarhizium anisopliae
Metarhizium owariense
Moelleriella basicystis
Moelleriella epidendri
Moelleriella epiphylla
Moelleriella libera
Moelleriella macrostroma
Moelleriella ochracea
Moelleriella phyllogena
Moelleriella rhombispora
Moelleriella turbinata
Moelleriella zhongdongii
Myriogenospora atramentosa
Nigelia martialis
Ustilaginoidea dichromenae
Ustilaginoidea ochracea
Cordycipitaceae
Beauveria bassiana
Cordyceps brasiliensis
Cordyceps militaris
Cordyceps pittieri
Cordyceps polyarthra
Cordyceps puiggarii
Cordyceps tenuipes
Simplicilliumlanosoniveum
Hypocreaceae
Acrostalagmus albus
Acrostalagmus annulatus
**Hypocrea nigrovirens*
Hypocrea substipitata
**Hypocrea tuberosa*
Hypocreopsis macrostoma
Hypomyces aurantius
Hypomyces rosellus
Hypomyces subiculosus
Protocrea pallida
Sarawakus lycogaloides
Sphaerostilbella penicillioidea
Trichoderma albofulvum
Trichoderma asperellum
Trichoderma atroviride
Trichoderma brevicompactum
**Trichoderma chlorosporum*
Trichoderma citrinellum
**Trichoderma costaricense*
Trichoderma deliquescens
Trichoderma eucorticioides
**Trichoderma flaviconidium*
Trichoderma hamatum
Trichoderma harzianum
Trichoderma koningii
Trichoderma koningiopsis
Trichoderma latizonatum
Trichoderma lixii
Trichoderma orientale
Trichoderma patella
Trichoderma patellotropicum
Trichoderma pinnatum
Trichoderma poronioideum
**Trichoderma pseudocandidum*
Trichoderma reesei
Trichoderma spirale
**Trichoderma turrialbense*
Trichoderma virens
Trichoderma virescentiflavum
Trichoderma viride
Trichothecium crotocinigenum
Trichothecium roseum
Ijuhyaceae
Ijuhya parilis
Nectriaceae
Albonectria rigidiuscula
Bisifusarium domesticum
Bisifusarium lunatum
Calonectria colhoumii
Calonectria humicola
Calonectria hurae
Calonectria ilicicola
Calonectria inconspicua
**Calonectria jimenezii*
Calonectria kyotensis
Calonectria morgani
Calonectria pyrochroa
Calonectria spathiphylli
Calostilbe striispora
Chaetopsina polyblastia
Cinnamomeonectria cinnamomea
Corallomycetella elegans
Corallomycetella repens
Corallonectria jatrophae
**Cosmospora clavi*
Cosmospora flammea
Cosmospora micropedis
Cosmospora stilbellae
Cosmospora viliuscula
**Cylindrocarpon ianthothele*
Cylindrocarpon lichenicola
**Cylindrocarpon musae*
Cylindrocladiella parva
Dialonectria episphaeria
Fusarium ananatum
Fusarium anisophilum
Fusarium borneense
**Fusarium camptoceras*
**Fusarium concentricum*
Fusarium equiseti
Fusarium falciforme
Fusarium fujikuroi
Fusarium graminearum
Fusarium hainanense
Fusarium heterosporum
Fusarium incarnatum
Fusarium lateritium
Fusarium longipes
Fusarium moniliforme
Fusarium neocosmoporiellum
Fusarium oxysporum
Fusarium polyphialidicum
Fusarium proliferatum
Fusarium roseum
Fusarium sacchari
Fusarium solani
Fusarium temperatum
Fusarium verticillioidea
Hydropisphaera suffulta
**Lisea tonduzi*
Macronectria jungneri
Macronectria neotropicalis
Mariannaea elegans
Microcera larvarum
Nalanthamala olivacea
Nalanthamala vermoeseni
**Nectria brenesii*
**Nectria contraria*
Nectria foliicola
Nectria fusispora
Nectria gracilipes
**Nectria lankesteri*
Nectria mammoidea var. minor
Nectria peziza
**Nectria prodigiosa*
**Nectria pseudotrichia*
**Nectria sanramonensis*
Nectria tucumanensis
**Nectria turrialbae*
Nectria aurantiicola
Neonectria ditissima
Ophionectria trichospora
Penicillifer bipapillatus
Penicillifer macrosporus
Pseudocosmospora vilior
**Thelonectria cidaria*
Thelonectria coronata
Thelonectria diademata
Thelonectria discophora
Thelonectria elata
**Thelonectria ianthina*
Thelonectria lucida
**Thelonectria purpurea*
Thelonectria stemmata
Thelonectria veuillotiana
Tubercularia agaves
Tubercularia lateritia
**Volutella uredinophila*
Volutellonectria consors
Niessliaceae
Valetoniella crucipila
Ophiocordycipitaceae
Hirsutella citrififormis
Hirsutella jonesii
Hirsutella nodulosa
Hirsutella thompsonii
Ophiocordyceps australis
Ophiocordyceps dipterigena
Ophiocordyceps kniphosoides
Ophiocordyceps melolonthae
Ophiocordyceps myrmecophila
Ophiocordyceps nutans
Polycephalomyces tomentosus
Purpureocillium atypicola
Purpureocillium lilacinum
Purpureocillium takamizusanense
Tolypocladium capitatum
Tolypocladium ophioglossoides
Stachybotryaceae
Albosynnema elegans
Inaequalispora prestonii
**Myrothecium miconiae*
**Myxospora theatro*
Paramyrothecium roridum

- Stachybotrys chartarum*
Stachybotrys cylindrosporus
Stachybotrys echinatus
Stachybotrys kampalensis
Stachybotrys nephrosporus
Stachybotrys parvisporus
Stachybotrys reniformis
Striaticonidium cinctum
Family Incertae sedis
Acremonium murorum
Acremonium polychromum
Acremonium zonatum
Acremonium vitis
Cephalosporium carpogenum
Cephalosporium cinnamomeum
**Geosmithia cnesini*
**Geosmithia eupagioceri*
**Geosmithia microcorthyli*
**Geosmithia rufescens*
**Gyonectria intraspora*
**Hyalopus tumefaciens*
Ilyonectria destructans
Ilyonectria radicecola
Munkia martyris
Neomunkia sydowii
Pseudomeliola styracum
Rugonectria rugulosa
Sarocladium implicatum
Sarocladium oryzae
Sarocladium strictum
Sarocladium terricola
**Scopinella musciformis*
**Ticonectria perianthii*
**Ticonectria testudinea*
Jobellisiales
Jobelliaceae
Jobellisia barrii
Jobellisia fraterna
- Magnaporthales**
Magnaporthaceae
**Clasterosporium roupalae*
**Muraeriata collapsa*
Mycocleptodiscus terrestris
Nakataea oryzae
Ophioceraeae
Ophioceras castillensis
Ophioceras dolichostomum
Pyriculariaceae
Neocordana musae
Proxypyricularia zingiberis
Pyricularia grisea
Pyricularia oryzae
Melanosporales
Ceratostomataceae
Auerswaldia fiebrigii
Microthecium brevirostre
Meliolales
Meliolaceae
Amazonia asterinoides
Appendiculella larviformis
Appendiculella calostroma
Appendiculella compositarum
Appendiculella sororcula
**Asteridiella adelphica*
Asteridiella agauriae
**Asteridiella amoena*
Asteridiella anastomosans
Asteridiella anguriae
**Asteridiella calva*
**Asteridiella casimiroae*
Asteridiella guatemalensis
- Asteridiella manca*
Asteridiella melastomatacearum
**Asteridiella nigra*
Asteridiella pentaclethrae
**Asteridiella stigmaphylli*
Asteridiella symphoniae
**Asteridiella trachylaena*
Irenina hyptidicola
Irenopsis conostegiae
**Irenopsis costaricensis*
**Irenopsis cupaniicola*
**Irenopsis malpighiae*
Irenopsis moelleriana
Irenopsis pteridicola
**Irenopsis ramonensis*
Irenopsis solani
Irenopsis tenuissima
Irenopsis toruloidea
Irenopsis aciculosa
Meliola ambigua
Meliola amphigena
Meliola amphitricha
Meliola anacardi
Meliola anceps
Meliola aristolochiae
Meliola bicornis
**Meliola brachycera*
**Meliola calatheae*
**Meliola calatheicola*
**Meliola campylopoda*
**Meliola capensis*
Meliola caymanensis
**Meliola cestricola*
**Meliola chelonanthi*
**Meliola cladophaga*
Meliola clavulata var. *batatae*
**Meliola columnae*
**Meliola conica*
Meliola conigera
**Meliola convallata*
**Meliola crotonicola*
**Meliola dicranochaeta*
**Meliola drepanochaeta*
Meliola durantae var. *lippiae*
Meliola elaeidis
**Meliola eupla*
Meliola flacourtiacearum
Meliola furcata
Meliola gesneriae
**Meliola hispida*
**Meliola isothea*
Meliola lisianthi
Meliola longistipitata var. *wakefieldii*
**Meliola macropoda*
**Meliola magna*
Meliola malacotricha
Meliola malanae
Meliola mangiferae
**Meliola marantacearum*
**Meliola mataybae*
Meliola mayaguesiana
Meliola merrillii
**Meliola modesta*
Meliola mollinediae
Meliola myrsinacearum
Meliola niessiana
Meliola oteroana
**Meliola ouroupariae*
Meliola panici
Meliola panici var. *lasiacidis*
Meliola panici var. *olyrae*
Meliola patouillardii
- Meliola paullinae*
**Meliola phoebes*
**Meliola picramniae*
**Meliola polyodonta*
Meliola psidii
Meliola psychotriae
Meliola scabriseta var. *calopogonii*
Meliola serjaniae
**Meliola siparunae*
**Meliola solanicola*
**Meliola styracearum*
**Meliola sydowii*
**Meliola tabernaemontanae* var. *escharoide*
Meliola trichostroma
**Meliola unctiricha*
**Meliola varicuspis*
**Meliola xenoderma*
**Meliola aterrima*
**Meliola tonduzii*
**Ticomycetes psychotriae*
Microascales
Ceratocystidaceae
Berkeleyomyces basicola
Ceratocystis cacaofunesta
Ceratocystis fimbriata
Ceratocystis paradoxa
Huntia moniliformis
Halosphaeriaceae
Ascosacculus aquaticus
Ascosacculus heteroguttulatus
Cirrenalia palmicola
Luttrellia guttulata
Microasceae
Graphium eumorphum
**Graphium scolytodis*
Microascus brevicaulis
Myrmecridiales
Family Incertae sedis
Myrmecridium schulzeri
Ophiostomatales
Kathistaceae
Termitaria coronata
Ophiostomataceae
**Knoxdaviesia cecropiae*
**Knoxdaviesia scolytodis*
**Leptographium costaricense*
**Raffaelea scolytodis*
Sporothrix schenckii
Parasymptodiellales
Parasymptodiellaceae
Parasymptodiella laxa
Family Incertae sedis
Hawksworthiomyces lignivorus
Phyllachorales
Phyllachoraceae
**Camarotella costaricensis*
**Catacauma contractum*
**Catacauma costaricense*
Catacauma zanthoxyli
**Coccodiella chamaedoreae*
**Coccodiella melastomatum*
**Coccodiella neurophila*
**Coccodiella minuta*
Coccostroma peribebuyense
Coccostromopsis diplothemii
Diatractium ingae
Dothidina fiebrigii
Endodothella vismiae
**Linochora costaricensis*
**Lohwagia verruciformis*
**Ophiodothella galophila*
Ophiodothella panamensis

- Phyllachora acaciae* subsp. *acaciae*
 **Phyllachora advena*
Phyllachora ambrosiae
Phyllachora antheophorae
Phyllachora applanata
 **Phyllachora atro-maculans*
 **Phyllachora baphispora*
 **Phyllachora canavaliae*
 **Phyllachora casimiroae*
 **Phyllachora ciferrii*
Phyllachora conica
 **Phyllachora copeyensis*
 **Phyllachora costaericae*
 **Phyllachora costaricensis*
Phyllachora crotonis
 **Phyllachora deviata*
Phyllachora dolichogena subsp. *phaseoli*
Phyllachora dolichogena
Phyllachora explanata
Phyllachora gentilis
Phyllachora gouaniae
Phyllachora graminis
Phyllachora gratissima
 **Phyllachora greciana*
 **Phyllachora guanacastica*
 **Phyllachora lasiacis*
 **Phyllachora icacoreae*
 **Phyllachora ingicola*
 **Phyllachora kyllingae*
Phyllachora lactea
 **Phyllachora lamprothea*
 **Phyllachora leptasca*
Phyllachora machaeriticola
 **Phyllachora malvavisci*
 **Phyllachora mauriae*
Phyllachora maydis
 **Phyllachora meibomiae*
 **Phyllachora miconiicola*
 **Phyllachora miconiiphila*
 **Phyllachora microchita*
 **Phyllachora micropeltoidea*
Phyllachora minutissima
Phyllachora nitens subsp. *galactiae*
Phyllachora ocoteicola
Phyllachora oplismeni
 **Phyllachora paspalicola*
 **Phyllachora paullinae*
 **Phyllachora peregrina*
 **Phyllachora phoebes*
Phyllachora phylloplaca
 **Phyllachora pittieri*
 **Phyllachora ramonensis*
Phyllachora rhopalina
 **Phyllachora rimulosa*
Phyllachora scleriae
Phyllachora setariicola
 **Phyllachora simabae-cedronis*
Phyllachora sphaerosperma
 **Phyllachora stena*
 **Phyllachora stenocarpa*
 **Phyllachora tonduzii*
Phyllachora tragiae
 **Phyllachora trophis*
Phyllachora tupi
 **Phyllachora urvilleana*
 **Phyllachora veraguensis*
 **Phyllachora vismiae*
Phyllachora weirii
Phyllachora winteri
Phyllachora yapensis subsp. *pongamiae*
Polystigma pusillum
 **Puiggarina costaricensis*
 **Scolecocoida costaricensis*
Sphaerodothis circumscripta
Sphaerodothis densa
Sphaerodothis pirifera
Trabutia querci
 **Trabutia quercus*
 **Trabutia xylosmae*
Telimenaceae
Telimena acalyphae
 **Telimena amphibola*
Telimena balansae
 **Telimena bicincta*
 **Telimena bromeliae*
Telimena canafistulae
Telimena engleri
Telimena galavisii
 **Telimena hydrangeae*
 **Telimena insueta*
 **Telimena miravallensis*
 **Telimena picramniae*
 **Telimena protii*
 **Telimena rinoreae*
Telimena rubefaciens
Telimena ruelliae
 **Telimena semialarii*
Telimena tenuis
Telimena ulei
Pleurotheciales
Pleurotheciaceae
Pleurothecium recurvatum
Sordariales
Beltraniaceae
 **Beltrania maxima*
Beltrania querna
Beltrania rhombica
 **Hemibeltrania ovalispora*
 **Parabeltrania persianiae*
Chaetomiaceae
Humicola brevis
Trichocladium macrosporum
Helminthosphaeriaceae
Helminthosphaeria plumbea
 **Helminthosphaeria tomaculum*
Hilberina robusta
Spadicoides stoveri
Lasiosphaeriaceae
 **Lasiosphaeria miniovina*
 **Lasiosphaeria ovina*
 **Lasiosphaeria tuberculosa*
Schizothecium fimicola
Lasiosphaeridaceae
Lasiosphaeria hirsuta
Leptosporaceae
Leptospora gregaria
Neoschizotheciaceae
Cercophora atropurpurea
 **Cercophora costaricensis*
 **Cercophora macrocarpa*
Cercophora mirabilis
Cercophora striata
Echria macrotheca
Podosporaceae
Podospora bulbillosa
Sordariaceae
Neurospora crassa
Neurospora sitophila
Sordaria fimicola
Sordaria tomento-alba
Family Incertae sedis
Arnium olerum
Brachysporiella gayana
Brachysporiella pulchra
Brachysporiella setosa
Togniniales
Togniniaceae
Phaeoacremonium inflatipes
Phaeoacremonium parasiticum
Trichosphaeriales
Trichosphaeriaceae
 **Schweinitziella palmigena*
Schweinitziella perpusilla
Vermiculariopsiales
Vermiculariopsiaceae
Vermiculariopsiella pediculata
Xylariales
Cainiaceae
 **Seynesia costaricensis*
Vesiculozygosporium echinosporum
Diatrypaceae
Diatrype disciformis
Diatrype phaselinoides
Diatrype prominens
Diatrype stigma
Diatrypella pulvinata
Eutypa flavovirens
Eutypella portoricencis
Eutypella prunastris
Peroneutypa curvispora
Peroneutypa obesa
Peroneutypa scoparia
Phaeoisaria bambusae
Phaeoisaria clematidis
Graphostromataceae
Biscogniauxia atropunctata
Biscogniauxia capnodes
 **Camillea coroniformis*
 **Camillea heterostoma*
 **Camillea labiatirima*
Camillea leprieurii
 **Camillea obularia*
Hypoxylaceae
Daldinia childiae
Daldinia concentrica
Daldinia eschscholtzii
Entonaema cinnabarinum
Entonaema liquescens
 **Hypoxylon anomalum*
Hypoxylon bovei var. *microsporum*
 **Hypoxylon inconspicuum*
Hypoxylon lienhwacheense
Hypoxylon melanaspis
 **Hypoxylon subalbum*
Hypoxylon theissenii
Phylacia sagraeana
Thamnomycetes rostratus
Thamnomycetes fuciformis
Microdochiaceae
Idriella angustispora
Idriella lunata
Idriella mycophila
Xylariaceae
Anthostomella keissleri
Dematophora arcuata
Dematophora bunodes
Dematophora pepo
Kretzschmaria clavus
 **Kretzschmaria varians*
Kretzschmaria culmorum
Leprieuria bacillum
 **Nemania chestersii* var. *submicrospora*
 **Nemania costaricensis*
Nemania serpens
 **Occultitheca costaricensis*

- *Ophiorosellinia costaricensis*
**Paramphisphaeria costaricensis*
**Plectosphaera ingae*
**Plectosphaera quadraspora*
Poronia pileiformis
Rosellinia amblystoma
Stilbohypoxylon elaeicola
Stilbohypoxylon quisquiliarum
Vrikshopama swetasakha
Xylaria allantoides
Xylaria anisopleura
Xylaria arbuscula
Xylaria badia
Xylaria coccophora
**Xylaria coremifera*
Xylaria cubensis
Xylaria curta
Xylaria fockei
Xylaria grammica
Xylaria hypoxylon
Xylaria multiplex
Xylaria polymorpha
Xylaria telfairii
**Xylaria umbonata*
Xylospora comosa
Zygosporiaceae
Zygosporium oscheoides
Zygosporium gibbum
Family Incertae sedis
Gloeocercospora sorghi
Order Incertae sedis
Apiosporaceae
Apiospora camptospora
Arthrinium arundinis
Arthrinium phaeospermum
Papularia bambusina
Lentomitellaceae
Lentomitella tropica

Pseudohalonectriaceae
Pseudohalonectria lignicola
Class Incertae sedis
Cryptomycina filicina
Ellisembia bambusicola
Endophragmiella angustispora
Endophragmiella biseptata
Endophragmiella pallescens
Erythromada lanciospora
Lasiosphaeriella nitida
Lasiosphaeriella noonae-daniae
**Mirannulata costaricensis*
Mirannulata samuelsii
Mycomedusiospora flavida
Nigrospora oryzae
Nigrospora sacchari
**Phyllocelis clibadii*
**Phyllocelis oyedaeae*
Rimaconus jamaicensis
Selenosporella curvispora
Spinulosphaeria thaxteri
Stilbella aciculosa
Stilbella minutissima
**Stilbella proliferans*
Stromatographium stromaticum
Taphrinomycetes
Taphrinales
Protomycetaceae
**Buerenia myrrhidendri*
Taphrinaceae
**Taphrina tonduziana*
Pezizomycotina Incertae sedis
**Achoropeltis modesta*

Acrodontium crateriforme
Acrosporium piperis
Actinocladium rhodosporum
Actinodochium concinnum
**Annellophora solani*
Arachnophora polyradiata
Bahusutrabeja angularis
Belemnospora navicularis
Beltraniopsis asperisetifera
Brachydesmiella biseptata
**Bullimyces aurisporus*
**Bullimyces communis*
**Bullimyces costaricensis*
Cacumisporium capitulatum
Cacumisporium pleuroconidiophorum
Camposporidium hughesii
Camptomeris leucaenae
**Camptomeris calliandrae*
Canalisporium pallidum
Canalisporium pulchrum
Ceratosporella deviata
**Clypeolum exiguum*
Condylospora flexuosa
Corynesporopsis isabellae
Cryptophiala udagawae
**Cyclostomella oncophora*
Dendrosporium lobatum
Denticularia mangiferae
**Elachopeltis phoebae*
Exserticlava vasiformis
Fumago vagans
Fusichalara dimorphospora
**Fusisporella vexans*
**Gangliostilbe costaricensis*
Goidanichiella barronii
Gyothrix flagella
**Gyothrix flexuosa*
Gyothrix microsperma
**Gyothrix pupulinii*
Haplobasidium musae
**Haplolepis polyadelpha*
**Heteroseptata bacillospora*
**Hydromeliitis pulchella*
**Hyperus costaricensis*
Korunomyces prostratus
Leptodiscella africana
Melanocephala triseptata
Microxyphiella trichostoma
Minimelanolocus subulifer
Monodictys paradoxa
Monodictys putredinis
Neoplaconema napelli
**Nyctalospora compacta*
Ochroconis crassihumicola
Orphanocoela maydis
**Peltistroma disciforme*
Perisporium bromeliae
**Perizomella inquinans*
Phaeocandelabrum callisporum
**Phragmopeltis blechni*
Phragmopeltis callista
Phragmopeltis phoebes
**Piricauda longispora*
**Pirozynskiella costaricensis*
**Plectopeltis egenula*
**Plenotrichum mirabile*
Pleurotheciopsis bramleyi
Pleurotheciopsis sylvestris
Poroisariopsis armillata
**Poroisariopsis inornata*
Pseudodiplodia cryptica
Pseudoepicoccum tectonae

**Pycnidiostroma eugeniae*
Radulidium subulatum
**Rhizomorpha sphaerocrystalligera*
**Riomyces rotundus*
Sarcopodium flocculentum
Sarcopodium mammiforme
Sarcopodium vanillae
**Scleromeris guazumae*
Scolecobasidium constrictum
Scolecobasidium humicola
Scolecobasidium tropicum
Solheimia costispora
Solosympodiella clavata
Speirospora hyalospora
Spiropes dorycarpus
Spiropes melanoplaca
Spiropes penicillium
Stachylidium bicolor
Staphylotrichum coccosporum
Staphylotrichum longicolle
**Stigmopeltella costaricana*
**Stigmopeltis phoebe*
**Stigmopeltis roupalae*
**Subulispora spinosa*
**Sympodiophora tenuis*
Tetracoccosporium paxianum
**Ticogloea guttulata*
**Ticosynnema carranzae*
**Trichodochium disseminatum*
Virgatospora echinofibrosa
Xepicula leucotricha
Vezdaeaceae
Vezdaea stipitata
Thelocarpales
Thelocarpaceae
Thelocarpon laureri
Wiesneriomycetales
Wiesneriomycetaceae
Wiesneriomyces laurinus
BASIDIOMYCOTA
Agaricomycetes
Agaricales
Agaricaceae
Agaricus arvensis
Agaricus campestris
Agaricus delicatulus
Agaricus endoxanthus
Agaricus ochraceosquamulosus
Agaricus piperatus
Agaricus sylvaticus
Chlamydopus meyenianus
Chlorophyllum molybdites
Chlorophyllum morgani
Coprinus comatus
**Cystolepiota cinereofusca*
Cystolepiota hemisclera
Lepiota besseyi
**Lepiota gomezii*
Lepiota gracilis
Lepiota nigropunctata
Lepiota rimosa
Leucoagaricus rubrotinctus
Leucoagaricus sulphurellus
Leucocoprinus bakeri
Leucocoprinus birnbaumii
Leucocoprinus cepistipes
Leucocoprinus fragilissimus
Macrolepiota excoriata
Macrolepiota mastoidea
Macrolepiota procera
**Microspallioia cinerabomeopallida*
Rugosospora pseudorubiginosa

- Tulostoma dumeticola*
Tulostoma fimbriatum
**Tulostoma matae*
Amanitaceae
Amanita abrupta
Amanita antillana
Amanita arocheae
Amanita bisporigera
Amanita brunneolocularis
Amanita brunnescens
Amanita caesarea
Amanita ceciliae
Amanita citrina
Amanita colombiana
**Amanita conara*
**Amanita costaricensis*
Amanita flavoconia var. *inquinata*
Amanita fuligineodisca
**Amanita garabitoana*
Amanita gemmata
Amanita muscaria
Amanita pantherina
Amanita phalloides
Amanita polypyrans
Amanita rubescens
Amanita sororcula
Amanita vaginata
Amanita virosa
Amanita xyliniinvola
**Catatrama costaricensis*
Callistosporiaceae
Callistosporium praemultifolium
Macrocybe titans
Clavariaceae
Camarophyllopsis dennisiana
Clavaria acuta
**Clavaria barbensis*
Clavaria fragilis
**Clavaria tortuosa*
Clavulinopsis fusiformis
Clavulinopsis laeticolor
**Ramariopsis costaricensis*
Clitocybaceae
Clitocybe microspora
Clitocybe smaragdina
Collybia nivea
Collybia purpurea
Collybia micheliana
Cortinariaceae
**Aureonarius aurantiobrunneus*
Calonarius arcuatorum
**Calonarius jardinensis*
**Cortinarius aureopigmentatus*
Cortinarius bolaris
Cortinarius caperatus
**Cortinarius carranzae*
**Cortinarius cartagoensis*
Cortinarius colombianus
Cortinarius corrugatus
**Cortinarius costaricensis*
**Cortinarius hallingii*
Cortinarius iodes
Cortinarius marylandensis
**Cortinarius matae*
**Cortinarius neotropicus*
**Cortinarius palatinus*
Cortinarius panamaensis
**Cortinarius quercoarmillatus*
**Cortinarius savegrensis*
**Cortinarius sericeolazulinus*
Cortinarius violaceus
Phlegmacium glaucopus
Pyrrhoglossum lilaceipes
Pyrrhoglossum pyrrom
**Thaxterogaster comarostaphylidis*
**Thaxterogaster comparioides*
**Thaxterogaster ovreboi*
Thaxterogaster purpurascens
Crepidotaceae
Crepidotus crocophyllus
Crepidotus martinii
Pleuroflammula squarrulosa
Cyphellaceae
**Campanophyllum proboscideum*
Cystostereaceae
Cystostereum australe
Cystostereum murrayi
Entolomataceae
**Clitopilus densifolius*
**Clitopilus eccentricus*
**Clitopilus griseobrunneus*
**Clitopilus hobsonii*
Clitopilus incarnatus
Clitopilus incrustatus
Clitopilus prunulus
Clitopilus pseudonitellinus
Clitopilus rhodotrama
**Clitopilus umbrosus*
**Clitopilus angustisporus*
Entoloma aprile
Entoloma ferreri
Entoloma murrayi
Entoloma murrillii
Entoloma quadratum
Entoloma squamifolium
Entoloma styloporum
**Rhodocybe mellea*
Galeropsidaceae
Panaeolus antillarum
Panaeolus cyanescens
Panaeolus papilionaceus
Panaeolus semiovatus
Hydnangiaceae
Laccaria amethystina
Laccaria gomezii
Laccaria laccata
Laccaria ohiensis
Laccaria proxima
Laccaria trichodermophora
Hygrophoraceae
**Acantholichen pannariodes*
**Acantholichen sorediatus*
Cora arachnoidea
**Cora arborescens*
Cora aspera
**Cora barbulata*
Cora ciferrii
Cora glabrata
**Cora gomeziana*
**Cora haledana*
**Cora hawksworthiana*
**Cora hymenocarpa*
**Cora imi*
**Cora minor*
**Cora palustris*
**Cora paraminor*
**Cora smaragdina*
Cora soredavidia
**Cora terrestris*
**Cora viliewoa*
**Corella melvinii*
Cuphophyllum pratensis
**Cyphellostereum phyllogenum*
**Dictyonema aeruginosulum*
**Dictyonema gomezianum*
**Dictyonema hernandezii*
Dictyonema irpicinum f. *laudateum*
Dictyonema irrigatum
Dictyonema phyllogenum
Dictyonema phyllophilum
Dictyonema sericeum
Dictyonema sericeum f. *phyllophilum*
Dictyonema sericeum var. *sericeum*
Dictyonema thelephora
Gliophorus laetus
Hygrocybe cantharellus
Hygrocybe conica
Hygrocybe hondurensis
Hygrocybe miniata
Hygrocybe subminiata
Hygrophorus penarius
Hygrophorus russula
Hygrophorus sordidus
Hymenogastereae
Flammula ricensis
**Gymnopilus crassitunicatus*
**Gymnopilus pachycystis*
Gymnopilus robustus
Gymnopilus rugulosus
Gymnopilus subtropicus
Hebeloma gomezii
Naucoria aureobrunnea
Phaeocollybia ambigua
Phaeocollybia caudata
**Phaeocollybia longistipitata*
Phaeocollybia oligoporpa
Phaeocollybia pseudolugubris
Phaeocollybia quercetorum
Phaeocollybia singularis
**Phaeocollybia subarduennensis*
Pseudoheleomyces paludosus
Psilocybe atlantis
Psilocybe aztecorum var. *aztecorum*
**Psilocybe bipileurocystidiata*
Psilocybe cubensis
Psilocybe fagicola
Psilocybe mexicana
Psilocybe muscorum
Psilocybe neoxalapensis
Psilocybe plutonia
**Psilocybe rolfsingeri*
Psilocybe yungensis
Psilocybe zapotecoantillarum
Inocybaceae
Inocybe hystrix
Inocybe plocamophora
Inosperma calamistratum
Inocybe hystrix
Pseudosperma notodryinum
Pseudosperma tropicale
Lycoperdaceae
Apioperdon pyriforme
Bovista aestivalis
Bovista cunninghamii
Bovista dominicensis
Bovista fusca
Bovista longispora
Bovista nigrescens
Bovista plumbea
Bovista sclerocystis
Bovistella atrobrunnea
Bovistella radicata
Calvatia bicolor
Calvatia candida var. *rubro-flava*
Calvatia craniformis
Calvatia cyathiformis

Calvatia gigantea
Calvatia rugosa
 **Calvatia sporocristata*
Lycoperdon atropurpureum
Lycoperdon compactum
 **Lycoperdon costaricense*
Lycoperdon dermoxanthum
Lycoperdon echinatum
Lycoperdon endotephrum
Lycoperdon epixylon
Lycoperdon excipuliforme
Lycoperdon eximium
Lycoperdon fuligineum
Lycoperdon juruense
Lycoperdon muscorum
Lycoperdon nigrescens
Lycoperdon perlatum
Lycoperdon pratense
Lycoperdon pusillum
Lycoperdon pyriforme
Lycoperdon subincarnatum
Lycoperdon umbrinum
Lycoperdon velutinum
Morganella afra
Morganella costaricensis
Morganella fuliginea
Morganella samoensis
Morganella velutina
Vascellum floridanum
Vascellum intermedium
Vascellum texense
Lyophyllaceae
Asterophora lycoperdoides
Asterophora parasitica
Calocybe africana
Lyophyllum decastes
Ossicaulis lignatilis
Termitomyces albidus
 **Termitomyces dominicalensis*
Marasmiaceae
Chaetocalathus columellifer
Chaetocalathus liliputianus
Crinipellis eggersii
Marasmius atrorubens
Marasmius bellus
Marasmius berteroi
 **Marasmius cenospilus*
 **Marasmius centroamericanus*
Marasmius cladophyllus
Marasmius cohaerens
 **Marasmius costaricensis*
Marasmius crinis-equi
Marasmius digilii
Marasmius floriceps
 **Marasmius gomezii*
Marasmius guyanensis
Marasmius haematocephalus
Marasmius heliomyces
Marasmius hendecaphyllus
Marasmius jalapensis
Marasmius leoninus
Marasmius leveilleanus
Marasmius nigrobrunneus
Marasmius oreades
Marasmius pallescens
Marasmius pallipes
Marasmius perlongispermus
Marasmius pseudoniveoaffinis
Marasmius pseudoniveus var. *pseudoniveus*
 **Marasmius rotaliformis*
Marasmius rotuloides
Marasmius setulosifolius

Marasmius spicullosus
Marasmius splitgerberi
Marasmius truncorum var. *ramorum*
 **Metacampanella costaricensis*
Moniliophthora roreri
Tetrapyrgos atrocyanea
Tetrapyrgos longicystidiata
Tetrapyrgos nigripes
Mycenaceae
Decapitatus flavidus
Favolaschia sprucei
Filoboletus clypeatus
Filoboletus gracilis
 **Hemimycena guanacastensis*
Hiatula ciliatula
Hiatula crenulata
Hydropus angustispermus
Hydropus gomezii
Hydropus hydrophoroides
Hydropus mycenoides
Hydropus nigrita
Hydropus nigromarginatus
Hydropus subcartilagineus
Mycena alphiophora
Mycena aurantiomarginata
 **Mycena castaneostipitata*
Mycena citricolor
 **Mycena costaricensis*
 **Mycena cyanosyringea*
 **Mycena gomezii*
 **Mycena griseoradiata*
Mycena holoporphyrha
Mycena margarita
Mycena parabolica
Mycena plectophylla
Mycena pura
 **Mycena seclusa*
Mycena theobromicola
Panellus luteus
Panellus pusillus
Xeromphalina kauffmanii
Xeromphalina tenuipes
Omphalotaceae
Collybiopsis luxurians
 **Collybiopsis mesoamericana*
 **Collybiopsis parvula*
Collybiopsis subcyathiformis
Collybiopsis subpruinosa
Collybiopsis bififormis
Gymnopus coracicolor
Gymnopus dryophilus
Gymnopus hondurensis
Gymnopus impudicus
Gymnopus lachnophyllus
Gymnopus lodgeae
Gymnopus macropus
Gymnopus montagnei
Gymnopus nubicola
 **Gymnopus omphalodes*
 **Gymnopus pseudolodgeae*
 **Gymnopus pyracanthoides*
Gymnopus spongiosus
 **Lentinula aciculospora*
Lentinula boryana
Lentinula raphanica
Lentinula detonsa
Marasmiellus albofuscus
 **Marasmiellus alnicola*
 **Marasmiellus cocosensis*
Marasmiellus collybioides
Marasmiellus cubensis
 **Marasmiellus cylindricus*

Marasmiellus distantifolius
Marasmiellus echinocephalus
Marasmiellus guadelupensis
Marasmiellus neotropicus
Marasmiellus paspali var. *americanus*
Marasmiellus pernambucensis
Marasmiellus pseudomphalodes
Marasmiellus stenophylloides
Marasmiellus troyanus
Marasmiellus volvatus
Paragymnopus foliiphilus var. *costarricensis*
 **Rhodocollybia amica*
 **Rhodocollybia dotae*
 **Rhodocollybia lignitilis*
Rhodocollybia monticola
 **Rhodocollybia pandipes*
Rhodocollybia popayanica
Rhodocollybia proluxa
 **Rhodocollybia tablensis*
Rhodocollybia steffeni
Phyllostoidaceae
Phyllostopsis nidulans
Physalacriaceae
Armillaria mellea
Armillaria puggarii
Armillariella affinis
Cyptotrama asprata
Cystoderma amianthinum
Dactylosporina steffeni
Desarmillaria tabescens
Hymenopellis radicata
Oudemansia platensis
Oudemansiella canarii
Physalacria clusiae
Strobilurus conigenoides
 **Xerula hispida*
Pleurotaceae
Hohenbuehelia carlothornii
Hohenbuehelia leptospora
Hohenbuehelia nigra
Hohenbuehelia petaloides
Hohenbuehelia robusta
Hohenbuehelia tylospora
Nematoctonus angustatus
Nematoctonus geogenius
Nematoctonus pachysporus
Nothopanus hygrophanus
Pleurotus djamor
Pleurotus dryinus
Pleurotus ostreatus
Pluteaceae
Pluteus cervinus
Pluteus pulverulentus
Pluteus rubrotomentosus
Pluteus spinulosus
Pluteus yungensis
Volvariella bakeri
Volvariella bombycina
Volvariella diplasia
Volvariella pseudovolvacea
Volvariella pusilla
Volvariella volvacea
Volvopluteus gloiocephalus
Psathyrellaceae
Coprinellus disseminatus
Coprinellus micaceus
Psathyra bulbillosa
Psathyra epibates
Psathyrella cloverae
 **Psathyrella piveae*
 **Psathyrella striatoannulata*
Tulosesus hastens

Pterulaceae**Pterula pterulicoides***Schizophyllaceae***Porodisculus pendulus**Schizophyllum commune***Stephanosporaceae***Lindtneria trachyspora***Strophariaceae***Deconica montana**Hypholoma capnoides**Hypholoma fasciculare**Hypholoma lateritium**Leratiomyces squamosus**Pholiota cubensis***Pholiota irazuensis***Tricholomataceae***Aspropaxillus giganteus**Aspropaxillus lepistoides**Leucopaxillus gentianeus**Leucopaxillus gracillimus***Tricholoma atratum***Tricholoma cacumense**Tricholoma caligatum**Tricholoma columbetta***Tricholoma costaricense**Tricholoma equestre***Tricholoma felschii***Tricholoma luteopallidum**Tricholoma palustre**Tricholoma portentosum**Tricholoma roseoacervum**Tricholoma saponaceum**Tricholoma stans***Tricholoma talamancense***Tubariaceae****Phaeomarasmius littoralis***Tubaria bispora***Typhulaceae***Sclerotium coffeicola**Typhula juncea**Amylocorticiales***Amylocorticaceae***Anomoloma myceliosum***Family Incertae sedis***Clitocybula azurea**Clitocybula familia**Crucibulum laeve**Cyathus africanus**Cyathus berkeleyanus**Cyathus canna**Cyathus earlei**Cyathus gayanus**Cyathus helenae***Cyathus julietae**Cyathus limbatus**Cyathus montagnei**Cyathus novae-zeelandiae**Cyathus olla**Cyathus pallidus**Cyathus poeppigii**Cyathus setosus**Cyathus stercoreus**Cyathus striatus***Cyathus tenuicorticalis**Cyathus intermedius**Cystodermella cristallifera**Fistulina hepatica***Gerronema costaricense**Gerronema retiarium**Gerronema strombodes**Lactocollybia aequatorialis**Lactocollybia epia**Lepista nuda**Lepista subisabellina***Lepistella ocula**Lycogalopsis solmsii**Megacollybia platyphylla**Megacollybia rodmani**Melanoleuca grammopodia***Melanomphalia leucocephala**Omphalina incarnata**Panaeolina foenisecii**Pilosace hololepis**Pseudofistulina radicata***Ripartitella alba**Ripartites tricholoma**Squamanita umbonata**Tricholomopsis humboldtii**Tricholomopsis rutilans**Tricholomopsis totilivida***Tricholomopsis violaceum**Trogia cantharelloides**Trogia papyracea***Atheliales****Atheliaceae***Athelia rolfsii***Auriculariales****Auriculariaceae***Amphistereum leveilleanum**Auricularia delicata**Auricularia fuscouscinea**Auricularia mesenterica**Auricularia nigricans***Auricularia rosea**Auricularia auricula-judae***Auricularia subglabra**Eichleriella shearii**Elmerina caryae**Exidiopsis effusa**Exidiopsis galzinii**Exidiopsis mucedinea**Heterochaete andina**Heterochaete hirneoloides***Heterochaete vitrea***Hyaloriaceae****Myxarium mesonucleatum**Myxarium nucleatum***Myxarium subsphaerosporum***Family Incertae sedis***Basidiodendron eyrei**Basidiodendron rimosum**Ductifera pululahuana**Guepinia fissa**Protomerulius brachysporus**Protomerulius brasiliensis**Protomerulius substuppeus**Pseudohydnum gelatinosum var. paucidentata**Stypella crystallina**Stypella subgelatinosa***Boletales****Boletaceae***Aureoboletus auriporus**Aureoboletus flaviporus**Aureoboletus innixus**Aureoboletus subacidus**Austroboletus gracilis**Austroboletus neotropicalis**Austroboletus subvirens**Boletellus ananas**Boletellus chrysenteroides**Boletellus coccineus**Boletellus fibuliger**Boletellus jalapensis**Boletus brasiliensis**Boletus bulbosus**Boletus lignatilis**Boletus luridus***Boletus lychnipes***Boletus neoregius***Boletus quercophilus**Boletus variipes**Boletus vermiculosus**Butyriboletus regius**Caloboletus firmus***Chalciporus austrorubinellus***Chalciporus chontae**Chalciporus piperatoides**Chalciporus piperatus***Erythrophylloporus aurantiacus**Exsudoporus frostii***Harrya atriceps***Harrya chromipes**Heimioporus ivoryi**Heimioporus japonicus**Imleria badia***Imleria heteroderma***Lanmaoa flavorubra**Leccinellum gongosiceps***Leccinum monticola***Leccinum neotropicalis**Leccinum scabrum***Leccinum tablanse***Leccinum talamancanum**Neoboletus praestigiator***Phylloporus alborufus**Phylloporus bellus**Phylloporus caballeroi***Phylloporus centroamericanus***Phylloporus guanacastensis**Phylloporus phaeoxanthus**Phylloporus purpureus***Phylloporus phaeoxanthus var. phaeoxanthus**Pseudoboletus parasiticus**Pulveroboletus atkinsonianus**Pulveroboletus ravenelii***Pulveroboletus rolfeanus***Retiboletus flavoniger**Retiboletus ornatipes**Retiboletus retipes**Rugiboletus andinus**Strobilomyces ananiceps**Strobilomyces confusus**Strobilomyces strobilaceus**Suillellus luridus**Sutorius eximius***Tylopilus alkalixanthus**Tylopilus ballouii***Tylopilus bulbosus***Tylopilus gomezii**Tylopilus griseocarpus**Tylopilus lividobrunneus***Tylopilus montanus**Tylopilus obscurus**Tylopilus oradivensis**Tylopilus violatinctus***Veloporphyrellus pantoleucus**Xanthoconium stramineum**Xerocomellus chrysenteron**Xerocomellus zelleri**Xerocomus ferrugineus**Xerocomus phaeocephalus**Xerocomus subtomentosus***Boletinellaceae***Boletinellus exiguus**Boletinellus monticola**Phylloporus fibulatus*

Calostomataceae

Calostoma cinnabarinum
Calostoma lutescens
Calostoma ravenelii

Diplocystidiaceae

Astraeus hygrometricus

Gyroporaceae

Gyroporus castaneus
**Gyroporus paralongicystidiatus*
Gyroporus subalbellus

Hygrophoropsidaceae

Hygrophoropsis aurantiaca
Hygrophoropsis kivuensis

Paxillaceae

Alpova diplophloeus
Melanogaster variegatus

Sclerodermataceae

Pisolithus arhizus
Scleroderma arenicola
Scleroderma areolatum
Scleroderma bovista
Scleroderma cepa
Scleroderma hypogaeum
Scleroderma lycoperdoides
Scleroderma sinnamartense
Scleroderma verrucosum
Veligaster nitidum

Serpulaceae

**Serpula costaricensis*

Cantharellales**Aphelariaceae**

Aphelaria tropica

Botryobasidiaceae

Botryobasidium laeve
**Botryobasidium parmastoi*

Ceratobasidiaceae

Rhizoctonia solani

Hydnaceae

**Cantharellus atrolilacinus*
Cantharellus cibarius
Cantharellus lateritius
Clavulina castaneipes
Craterellus boyacensis
Craterellus cornucopioides
Craterellus ignicolor
Gloeomucro chlorinus
Hydnum repandum
Hydnum umbilicatum
**Multiclavula ichtthyiformis*

Corticiales**Corticaceae**

Corticium koleroga
Necator salmonicolor

Geastrales**Geastraceae**

Cycloderma indicum
**Geastrum albonigrum*
Geastrum badium
Geastrum corollinum
Geastrum coronatum
**Geastrum fimbriatum* var. *pseudohieronimii*
Geastrum hariotii
Geastrum javanicum
Geastrum kollabae
Geastrum lageniforme
Geastrum minimum
Geastrum mirabile
Geastrum morganii
Geastrum pectinatum
Geastrum rufescens
Geastrum saccatum
Geastrum schweinitzii

Geastrum smardae

Geastrum striatum

Geastrum subiculolum

Geastrum triplex

**Geastrum brunneocapillatum*

**Myriostoma aerolatum*

Sphaerobolus stellatus

Gloeophyllales**Gloeophyllaceae**

Boreostereum vibrans
Gloeophyllum striatum
Osmoporus mexicanus

Gomphales**Clavariadelphaceae**

Beenakia informis
Clavariadelphus americanus

Gomphaceae

Phaeoclavulina cyanocephala
Phaeoclavulina zippelii
**Ramaria gracilispora*
**Ramaria isaaci*

Lentariaceae

**Lentaria caribbeana*
Lentaria surculus

Hymenochaetales**Hymenochaetaceae**

Coltricia cinnamomea
Coltricia focicola
Coltricia fonsecoensis
Coltricia montagnei
Coltricia perennis
**Fomitiporella coruscans*
Fomitiporella micropora
Fomitiporia apiahyna
Fomitiporia pseudopunctata
Fomitiporia punctata
Fomitiporia robusta
**Fulvifomes centroamericanus*
**Fulvifomes costaricensis*
**Fulvifomes durissimus*
**Fulvifomes inermis*
**Fulvifomes jouzaai*
Fulvifomes luteoumbrianus
**Fulvifomes membranaceus*
**Fulvifomes merrillii*
**Fulvifomes rhytiphloeus*
Fuscoporia altocedronensis
Fuscoporia callimorpha
**Fuscoporia centroamericana*
Fuscoporia chrysea
Fuscoporia contigua
**Fuscoporia costaricana*
Fuscoporia ferruginosa
Fuscoporia flavomarginata
**Fuscoporia latispora*
Fuscoporia longisetulosa
Fuscoporia rhabarbarina
**Fuscoporia roseocinerea*
Fuscoporia undulata
Fuscoporia caymanensis
**Fuscoporia griseopora*
**Fuscoporia lutea*
Hydnoporia lenta

Hymenochaete escobarii

Hymenochaete iodina

Hymenochaete microcycla

Hymenochaete resupinata

Inocutis dryophila

Inocutis porrecta

**Inonotus adnatus*

Inonotus calcitratus

Inonotus crociticinctus

**Inonotus fimbriatus*

Inonotus fulvomelleus

**Inonotus gracilis*

Inonotus luteoumbrianus

**Inonotus marginatus*

Inonotus pachyphloeus

**Inonotus papyrinus*

Inonotus patouillardii

Inonotus pertenuis

Inonotus portoricensis

Inonotus pseudoglomeratus

Inonotus rickii

Inonotus splitgerberi

Inonotus tropicalis

**Inonotus xanthoporus*

**Inonotus costaricensis*

**Inonotus dentiporus*

Neomensularia crociticincta

Phellinidium ruftinctum

Phellinus allardii

Phellinus fastuosus

Phellinus ferrugineovelutinus

Phellinus gilvus

Phellinus grenadensis

Phellinus griseoporus

Phellinus melanodermus

Phellinus neoxotius

Phellinus nilgheriensis

Phellinus rimosus

Phellinus sancti-georgii

Phellinus sarcites

Phellinus setulosus

Phellinus shaferi

Phellinus sublamaensis

Phellinus swieteniae

**Phellinus turbinatus*

Phellinus amazonicus

Phylloporia capucina

Phylloporia chrysites

Phylloporia fruticum

Phylloporia pectinata

Phylloporia spathulata

Phylloporia verae-crucis

Pyrrhoderma noxium

Pyrrhoderma yunnanense

Tropicoporus cubensis

Tropicoporus dependens

**Tropicoporus guanacastensis*

Tropicoporus linteus

Tropicoporus melleoporus

Tropicoporus pseudolinteus

Tropicoporus caryophylleus

Tropicoporus detonsus

**Tropicoporus lopezii*

Hyphodontiaceae

Hyphodontia barba-jovis

Hyphodontia curvispora

Kneiffiella abdita

Oxyporaceae

Oxyporus lacera

Oxyporus latemarginatus

Oxyporus similis

Rickenellaceae

Cotylidia aurantiaca

Cotylidia pusiola

Resinicium saccharicola

Schizoporaceae

Echinoporia aculeifera

Fibrodontia brevidens

Fibrodontia gossypina

Lyomyces griseliniae

Schizopora paradoxa

- Xylodon flaviporus*
Family Incertae sedis
Nigrohirschioporus sector
Pallidohirschioporus biformis
Sidera lenis
Sidera lowei
 **Trichaptum album*
 **Trichaptum bulbocystidiatum*
Trichaptum byssogenum
Trichaptum fumosoavellaneum
Trichaptum perrottetii
 **Trichaptum agricola*
 **Trichaptum confertum*
Nigrofomitaceae
Melanoporella carbonacea
Nigrofomes melanoporus
Hysterangiales
Phallogastraceae
Phallogaster saccatus
Protuberia jamaicensis
Protuberia maracuja
Lepidostromatales
Lepidostromataceae
Lepidostroma calocerum
Phallales
Phallaceae
Aseroë rubra
Clathrus chrysomycelinus
Clathrus columnatus
Laternea pusilla
Laternea triscapa
 **Ligiella rodrigueziana*
 **Linderia pereximia*
Mutinus bambusinus
Mutinus caninus
Mutinus xyloigenus
 **Neolysurus arcipulvinus*
 **Phallus atrovolutus*
Phallus duplicatus
Phallus hadriani
Phallus impudicus
Phallus indusiatus
Phallus ravenelii
Staheliomyces cinctus
Xylophallus xyloigenus
Polyporales
Cerrenaceae
Cerrena caperata
Cerrena hydroides
Cerrena unicolor
Dacryobolaceae
Postia caesioflava
Postia ceriflua
 **Postia tephroleuca*
Spongiporus floriformis
Fibroporiaceae
Fibroporia radiculosa
Fibroporia vaillantii
Fomitopsidaceae
Antrodia albida
Antrodia favescens
Brunneoporus malicola
Buglossoporus americanus
Daedalea aethalodes
Daedalea dochmia
 **Daedalea hydroides*
Daedalea microsticta
Daedalea quercina
Fomitopsis lignea
Fomitopsis palustris
Phaeodaedalea incerta
Ranadivia modesta
- Ranadivia stereoides*
Rhodofomitopsis cupreorosea
Rhodofomitopsis feei
Wolfiporia cocos
Ganodermataceae
Cristataspora coffeata
Sanguinoderma rude
Gelatoporiaceae
Cinereomyces dilutabilis
Obba rivulosa
Grifolaceae
Aegis luteocontexta
Hyphodermataceae
Hyphoderma rimosum
Incrustoporiaceae
Skeletocutis albomarginata
Skeletocutis niveicolor
Skeletocutis roseola
 **Tyromyces albus*
Tyromyces chioneus
 **Tyromyces cinnamomeus*
 **Tyromyces duplexus*
Tyromyces fumidiceps
Tyromyces galactinus
Tyromyces hypocitrinus
Tyromyces leucomallus
 **Tyromyces navarroi*
Tyromyces xuchilensis
Irpiciaceae
 **Byssomerulius corium*
Ceriporia alachuana
 **Ceriporia citrina*
Ceriporia ferrugineocincta
 **Ceriporia incrustata*
 **Ceriporia microspora*
 **Ceriporia ochracea*
Ceriporia purpurea
Ceriporia reticulata
Ceriporia spissa
Ceriporia viridans
Ceriporia xylostromatoides
Flavodon flavus
 **Gloeoporus longisporus*
Gloeoporus thelephoroides
Hydnopolyporus fimbriatus
Hydnopolyporus palmatus f. *palmatus*
Hydnopolyporus palmatus f. *warmingii*
Irpex lacteus
Phanerochaetella xerophila
Trametopsis cervina
Vitreoporus dichrous
Ischnodermataceae
Ischnoderma resinatum
Laetiporaceae
Laetiporus persicinus
Laetiporus sulphureus
 **Laetiporus lobatus*
Phaeolus schweinitzii
Meripilaceae
Rigidoporus biokoensis
Rigidoporus lineatus
Rigidoporus microporus
 **Rigidoporus mutabilis*
Rigidoporus sanguinolentus
Rigidoporus ulmarius
Rigidoporus undatus
Rigidoporus vinctus
Meruliaceae
 **Ceriporiopsis costaricensis*
Ceriporiopsis flavilutea
Ceriporiopsis mucida
Ceriporiopsis umbrinescens
- Geesterania carneola*
Irpiciporus pachyodon
Mycoacia aurea
Mycoacia badia
Pappia fissilis
Physisporinus vitreus
Spongipellis caseosus
Panaceae
Cymatoderma africanum
Cymatoderma caperatum
Cymatoderma dendriticum
Phanerochaetaceae
 **Bjerkandera adusta*
 **Bjerkandera fumosa*
Bjerkandera centroamericana
Bjerkandera mikrofumosa
Hapalopilus albocitrinus
 **Hapalopilus tropicus*
Phanerochaete australis
Rhizochaete radicata
Podocyphaceae
Abortiporus biennis
Polyporaceae
Abundisporus fuscopurpureus
Abundisporus roseoalbus
Amauroderma boleticeum
Amauroderma camerarium
Amauroderma exile
Amauroderma nutans
Amauroderma omphalodes
Amauroderma praetervisum
Amauroderma schomburgkii
Amauroderma trichodermatum
Bresadolia craterella
Bresadolia uda
Cellulariella acuta
Ceriporus cavernulosus
 **Ceriporus parvisporus*
Ceriporus scutellatus
Ceriporus squamosus
Ceriporus varius
Coriolopsis brunneoleuca
Coriolopsis byrsina
Cubamyces lactineus
Cubamyces menziesii
Dentocorticium portoricense
 **Dichomitus costaricensis*
Earliella scabrosa
Echinochaete brachypora
Epithele nikau
Favolus grammocephalus
Favolus tenuiculus
Fomes extensus
Fomes fasciatus
Fomes meliae
Fomes pseudosenex
Fomitella supina
Foraminispora rugosa
Funalia floccosa
Funalia sanguinaria
Ganoderma amazonense
Ganoderma applanatum
Ganoderma australe
Ganoderma curtisii
Ganoderma ecuadorensis
Ganoderma oerstedii
Ganoderma orbiforme
Ganoderma parvulum
Grammothele aurantiaca
Grammothele fuligo
Grammothele lacticolor
Grammothele lineata

- Grammothele subargentea*
Haddowia longipes
Haddowia neurospora
Hexagonia cucullata
Hexagonia glabra
Hexagonia unicolor
Lentinus arcularius
Lentinus brumalis
**Lentinus crinitus*
Lentinus substrictus
Lentinus tricholoma
Lenzites betulinus
Megasporoporia setulosa
Microporellus dealbatus
Microporellus holotephrus
Microporellus obovatus
Navisporus floccosus
Pachykytospora alabamiae
Pachykytospora papyracea
Perenniporia aurantiaca
Perenniporia cremeopora
Perenniporia inflexibilis
Perenniporia martia
Perenniporia medulla-panis
Perenniporia ohioensis
Perenniporia roseoisabellina
Perenniporia subacida
**Perenniporia subovoidea*
Perenniporiella micropora
Perenniporiella tepeitensis
Phaeotrametes decipiens
Picipes badius
Picipes dictyopus
Picipes virgatus
Podofomes mollis
Podofomes stereoides
Polyporus guianensis
Polyporus impolitus
Polyporus leprieurii
Polyporus maculosus
Polyporus philippinensis
Polyporus tuberaster
**Polyporus laetiporoides*
Porogramme albocincta
Porogramme graphica
Porogramme lateritia
Pseudofavolus miquelii
Pycnoporus sanguineus
Pyrofomes fulvourbrinus
Pyrofomes lateritius
Royoporus spatulatus
Tinctoporellus epimiltinus
**Tomophagus colossus*
**Trametes brunnea*
Trametes cingulata
Trametes cubensis
**Trametes cystidiata*
Trametes ectypa
Trametes elegans
Trametes hirsuta
Trametes maxima
Trametes membranacea
Trametes meyenii
Trametes nivosa
Trametes ochracea
Trametes pavonia
Trametes polyzona
Trametes pubescens
Trametes roseola
Trametes varians
Trametes variegata
Trametes versicolor
- Trametes villosa*
Truncospora detrita
Truncospora livida
Truncospora ochroleuca
Truncospora tephropora
Yuchengia narymica
Sarcoporiaceae
**Sarcoporia neotropica*
Steccherinaceae
Antrodiella multipileata
Antrodiella murrillii
Antrodiella semisupina
Antrodiella versicutis
Butyrea luteoalba
Cabalodontia albofibrillosa
Flabellophora parva
Flaviporus brownii
Flaviporus hydrophilus
Flaviporus liebmannii
**Flaviporus tenuis*
**Junghuhnia neotropica*
Junghuhnia nitida
Junghuhnia sobria
Junghuhnia subundata
Lamelloporus americanus
Loweomyces fractipes
Loweomyces subgiganteus
Nigroporus durus
Nigroporus rigidus
Nigroporus vinosus
Steccherinum semisupiniforme
Trullella duracina
Xanthoporus peckianus
Family Incertae sedis
Cystidiopostia hibernica
**Diplomitoporus costaricensis*
Diplomitoporus stramineus
**Globuliclopsis lindbladii*
**Henningsia ater*
Henningsia brasiliensis
Hypochnicium stratosum
Inflatostereum glabrum
Piptoporellus soloniensis
Rickiopora latemarginata
Russulales
Albatrellaceae
**Polyporoletus neotropicus*
Auriscalpiaceae
**Artomyces costaricensis*
Artomyces pyxidatus
**Artomyces stephenii*
**Auriscalpium gilbertsonii*
Auriscalpium villipes
Lentinellus castoreus
Lentinellus cochleatus
Lentinellus ursinus
Bondarzewiaceae
Amylosporus bracei
Amylosporus campbellii
**Amylosporus efibulatus*
Bondarzewia berkeleyi
Stecchericum seriatum
Wrightoporia avellanea
Echinodontiaceae
Larssoniporia tropicalis
Hericiaceae
Hericium americanum
Hericium erinaceus
Russulaceae
Lactarius atroviridis
Lactarius aurantiacus
Lactarius camphoratus
- Lactarius chrysorheus*
Lactarius costaricensis
Lactarius deliciosus
Lactarius gerardii
Lactarius gerardii var. *subrubescens*
Lactarius peckii
Lactarius psammicola
Lactarius rimosellus
Lactarius rubidus
Lactarius subpalustris
Lactifluus deceptivus
Lactifluus gerardii
Lactifluus hallingii
Lactifluus indigo
Lactifluus luteolus
Lactifluus vellereus
Lactifluus veraecrucis
Multifurca furcata
**Multifurca mesoamericana*
Russula acrifolia
**Russula atroamethystina*
Russula atropurpurea
**Russula austromontana*
Russula brevipes
Russula burlinghamiae
**Russula cartaginis*
Russula chamaeleontina
Russula chloroides
Russula compacta
Russula costaricensis
**Russula crucensis*
Russula cyanoxantha
Russula delica
Russula emetica
**Russula eperythra*
Russula flavida
Russula foetens
Russula fragilis
Russula fragrans
Russula fuegiana
**Russula gomezii*
Russula laccata
Russula laurocerasi
Russula leguminosarum
Russula lepidiformis
Russula lividirosea var. *austropurpurea*
Russula metachromatica
Russula mexicana
Russula minutula
**Russula mitissima*
Russula nigricans
Russula nobilis
Russula nothofaginea
Russula pectinata
**Russula pluteoides*
Russula polyphylla
Russula puiggarii
Russula purpureonigra
**Russula quercophila*
Russula raoultii
Russula rhodomelanea
**Russula rolfeana*
Russula rosea
**Russula sancti-ramonensis*
**Russula subcrustosa*
Russula subdepallens
Russula subpusilla
**Russula thapsina*
Russula varicolor
Russula vesicatoria
Russula virescens
Russula viscida

- Russula xerampelina*
Zelleromyces scissilis
Stereaceae
Aleurodiscus croceus
Megalocystidium chelidonium
Stereum ostrea
Xylobolus principis
Family Incertae sedis
Polypus dispansus
Sebacinales
Sebacinaceae
Chaetospermum carneum
Efibulobasidium albescens
Sebacina candida
Sebacina confusa
Sebacina epigaea
Sebacina incrustans
Stereopsidales
Stereopsidaceae
**Stereopsis albida*
Stereopsis hiscens
Stereopsis radicans
Thelephorales
Bankeraceae
Boletopsis grisea
Thelephoraceae
**Odontia duemmeri*
Trechisporales
Hydnodontaceae
Hydnodon thelephorus
Litschauerella abietis
Subulicystidium boidinii
Subulicystidium brachysporum
Subulicystidium cochleum
Subulicystidium fusisporum
**Subulicystidium grandisporum*
Subulicystidium inornatum
Subulicystidium longisporum
Subulicystidium meridense
Subulicystidium naviculatum
Subulicystidium obtusisporum
Subulicystidium perlongisporum
Subulicystidium robustius
Trechispora candidissima
Trechispora dimitica
Trechispora mollusca
Trechispora regularis
Tubulicium dussii
**Tubulicium ramonense*
Tubulicium vermiculare
Tubulicium vermiferum
Tremellodendropsidales
Tremellodendropsidaceae
Tremellodendropsis flagelliformis var. *ovalispora*
Atractiellomycetes
Atractiellales
Phleogenaceae
Helicogloea aurea
Phleogena faginea
**Saccosoma sphaerosporum*
Cryptomycocolacomycetes
Cryptomycocolacales
Cryptomycocolacaceae
**Cryptomycocolax abnorme*
Cystobasidiomycetes
Cyphobasidiales
Cyphobasidiaceae
Cyphobasidium usneicola
Cystobasidiales
Cystobasidiaceae
Occultifur internus
Dacrymycetes
Dacrymycetales
Dacrymycetaceae
Calocera cornea
Dacrymyces involutus
Dacrymyces pulchrus
Dacryopinax elegans
**Dacryopinax primogenitus*
Dacryopinax spathularia
Order Incertae sedis
Dacryonaemataceae
Dacryonaema rufum
Entorrhizomycetes
Entorrhizales
Entorrhizaceae
Juncorrhiza aschersoniana
Juncorrhiza casparyana
Exobasidiomycetes
Doassansiales
Rhamphosporaceae
Rhamphospora nymphaeae
Entylomatales
Entylomataceae
Eballistra oryzae
Entyloma australe
Entyloma bidentis
**Entyloma browalliae*
Entyloma compositarum
Entyloma costaricense
Entyloma dahliae
**Entyloma deliliae*
Entyloma diastatae
**Entyloma doebbeleri*
Entyloma ecuadorensis
Entyloma galinsogae
Entyloma guaraniticum
Entyloma lobeliae
Entyloma microsporum
Entyloma petunia
Entylomella chrysanthemi
Erratomyces patelii
Exobasidiales
Brachybasidiaceae
Kordyana tradescantiae
Cryptobasidiaceae
**Clinoconidium bullatum*
Climoconidium farinosum
Drepanoconis larviformis
**Phacellula gouaniae*
Exobasidiaceae
Exobasidium arctostaphyli
Exobasidium disterigmaticola
Exobasidium emeritense
Exobasidium escalloniae
Exobasidium flos-cavendishiae
Exobasidium gaylussaciae
Exobasidium pernettyae
Exobasidium poasanum
Exobasidium rhododendri
Exobasidium sphyrospermi
Exobasidium talamancense
Exobasidium vaccinii
Microstromatales
Microstromataceae
Microstroma pithecellobii
Microstroma pithecolobii
Tilletiales
Tilletiaceae
Conidiosporomyces ayresii
Conidiosporomyces ayresii
Tilletia oplismeni-cristati
Microbotryomycetes
Microbotryales
Microbotryaceae
Sphacelotheca hydropiperis
Ustilentylomataceae
Aurantiosporium subnitens
Microbotryozyma collariae
Sporidiobolales
Sporidiobolaceae
Rhodotorula babjevae
Rhodotorula mucilaginoso
Sporobolomyces carnicolor
Pucciniomycetes
Helicobasidiales
Helicobasidiaceae
**Tuberculina costaricana*
Pucciniales
Chaconiaceae
Chaconia ingae
Maravalia pressa
Maravalia pura
Maravalia utriculata
Olivea tectonae
Coleosporiaceae
Coleosporium anceps
Coleosporium dahliae
Coleosporium elephantopidis
Coleosporium eupatorii
Coleosporium ipomoeae
Coleosporium paraphysatum
Coleosporium plumeriae
Coleosporium verbesinae
Coleosporium viburni
Cronartiaceae
Cronartium coleosporioides
Cronartium quercuum
Cronartium wilsonianum
Crossosporaceae
Neoolivea tectonae
Melampsoraceae
Melampsora larici-populina
Mikronegeriaceae
Chrysocelis lupini
Milesinaceae
Milesia cupheae
Milesina australis
Milesina blechni
Neophysopeleaceae
Neophysopele ampelopsidis
Neophysopele uva
Neophysopele vitis
Phakopsoraceae
Angiopsora lenticularis
Cerotelium fici
Cerotelium malvicola
Crossospora piperis
Crossospora byrsonimae
Phakopsora burserae
Phakopsora crotonis
Phakopsora cupheae
Phakopsora fenestrata
Phakopsora jatrophicola
Phakopsora meibomia
Phakopsora neocheimoliae
Phakopsora pachyrhizi
Phakopsora diehlii
Phragmidaceae
Gerwasia pittieriana
Gerwasia rubi
Kuehneola loeseneriana
Mainsia rubi
Phragmidium mucronatum
Pucciniaceae
Aecidium abscedens

<i>Aecidium albicans</i>	<i>Puccinia hieracii</i>	<i>Puccinia trachytela</i>
<i>Aecidium ampliatum</i>	<i>Puccinia hodgsoniana</i>	<i>Puccinia urbaniana</i>
<i>Aecidium cissi</i>	<i>Puccinia holwayula</i>	<i>Puccinia variana</i>
<i>Aecidium lantanae</i>	<i>Puccinia huberi</i>	<i>Puccinia venustula</i>
<i>Aecidium monticola</i>	<i>Puccinia hydrocotyles</i>	<i>Puccinia vernoniae-mollis</i>
<i>Aecidium poasense</i>	<i>Puccinia hypoxidis</i>	<i>Puccinia violae</i>
<i>Aecidium tenerius</i>	<i>Puccinia hyptidis</i>	<i>Puccinia vulcanicola</i>
<i>Aecidium tubulosum</i>	<i>Puccinia hyptidis-mutabilis</i>	<i>Puccinia gymnomolomiae</i>
<i>Aecidium verbenae</i>	<i>Puccinia idonea</i>	<i>Puccinia impedita</i>
<i>Argomyces vernoniae</i>	<i>Puccinia impressa</i>	<i>Puccinia medellinensis</i>
<i>Chrysella mikaniae</i>	<i>Puccinia inaequata</i>	<i>Puccinia praealta</i>
<i>Chrysocyclus cestri</i>	<i>Puccinia inaudita</i>	<i>Sphenospora smilacina</i>
<i>Dicaeoma arundinellae</i>	<i>Puccinia inclita</i>	<i>Uredo campeliae</i>
<i>Endophyllum circumscriptum</i>	<i>Puccinia incondita</i>	<i>Uredo cupheicola</i>
<i>Endophyllum guttatum</i>	<i>Puccinia inermis</i>	<i>Uredo cupressicola</i>
<i>Endophyllum pumilio</i>	<i>Puccinia investita</i>	<i>Uredo cyathulae</i>
<i>Endophyllum stachytarphetae</i>	<i>Puccinia jaliscensis</i>	<i>Uredo cyclanthacearum</i>
<i>Polioma pallidissima</i>	<i>Puccinia jambosae</i>	<i>Uredo hameliae</i>
<i>Puccinia abrepta</i>	<i>Puccinia kellermanii</i>	<i>Uredo hypoxidis</i>
<i>Puccinia absicca</i>	<i>Puccinia kuehnii</i>	<i>Uredo jucunda</i>
<i>Puccinia acnisti</i>	<i>Puccinia kyllingae-brevifoliae</i>	<i>Uredo mauriae</i>
<i>Puccinia aemulans</i>	<i>Puccinia lantanae</i>	<i>Uredo monochaeti</i>
<i>Puccinia ametableta</i>	<i>Puccinia lateritia</i>	<i>Uredo nidularii</i>
<i>Puccinia anodae</i>	<i>Puccinia leonotidicola</i>	<i>Uredo ramonensis</i>
<i>Puccinia arechavaletae</i>	<i>Puccinia levis</i>	<i>Uredo recondita</i>
<i>Puccinia boliviana</i>	<i>Puccinia liabi</i>	<i>Uredo retalhuleuensis</i>
<i>Puccinia bomareae</i>	<i>Puccinia liberta</i>	<i>Uredo roupalae</i>
<i>Puccinia brachytela</i>	<i>Puccinia lithospermi</i>	<i>Uredo rubescens</i>
<i>Puccinia caleae</i>	<i>Puccinia macra</i>	<i>Uredo santa-rosensis</i>
<i>Puccinia caleae var. caleae</i>	<i>Puccinia melampodii</i>	<i>Uredo semidiscifera</i>
<i>Puccinia caleae var. cuernavacae</i>	<i>Puccinia melanocephala</i>	<i>Uredo suspecta</i>
<i>Puccinia californica</i>	<i>Puccinia mitrata</i>	<i>Uredo tillandsiae</i>
<i>Puccinia canaliculata</i>	<i>Puccinia mitrata var. basiporula</i>	<i>Uredo torulini</i>
<i>Puccinia caricina</i>	<i>Puccinia mogiphans</i>	<i>Uredo trichiliae</i>
<i>Puccinia cenchri</i>	<i>Puccinia mutisiae</i>	<i>Uromyces aphelandrae</i>
<i>Puccinia chrysanthemi</i>	<i>Puccinia neorotundata</i>	<i>Uromyces appendiculatus</i>
<i>Puccinia cnici-oleracei</i>	<i>Puccinia nesodes</i>	<i>Uromyces bidenticola</i>
<i>Puccinia cognata</i>	<i>Puccinia oaxacana</i>	<i>Uromyces bidentis</i>
<i>Puccinia conoclinii</i>	<i>Puccinia oxalidis</i>	<i>Uromyces celosiae</i>
<i>Puccinia consobrina</i>	<i>Puccinia oyedaeae</i>	<i>Uromyces cestri</i>
<i>Puccinia conyzella</i>	<i>Puccinia pallidissima</i>	<i>Uromyces cestri var. maculans</i>
<i>Puccinia cordiae</i>	<i>Puccinia pallor</i>	<i>Uromyces cologaniae</i>
<i>Puccinia coronata</i>	<i>Puccinia paspali</i>	<i>Uromyces columbianus</i>
<i>Puccinia crassipes</i>	<i>Puccinia paulensis</i>	<i>Uromyces commelinae</i>
<i>Puccinia cupheae</i>	<i>Puccinia paupercula</i>	<i>Uromyces costaricensis</i>
<i>Puccinia cynodontis</i>	<i>Puccinia pelargonii-zonalis</i>	<i>Uromyces cucullatus</i>
<i>Puccinia cyperi</i>	<i>Puccinia peperomiae</i>	<i>Uromyces cystopiformis</i>
<i>Puccinia cyperi-tagetiformis</i>	<i>Puccinia phyllostachydis</i>	<i>Uromyces decoratus</i>
<i>Puccinia detonsa</i>	<i>Puccinia pittieriana</i>	<i>Uromyces doebbeleri</i>
<i>Puccinia dioicae</i>	<i>Puccinia polygoni-amphibii</i>	<i>Uromyces dolicholi</i>
<i>Puccinia discreta</i>	<i>Puccinia posadensis</i>	<i>Uromyces eragrostidis</i>
<i>Puccinia diutina</i>	<i>Puccinia proba</i>	<i>Uromyces euphorbiae</i>
<i>Puccinia dochmia</i>	<i>Puccinia psidii</i>	<i>Uromyces flectens</i>
<i>Puccinia doloris</i>	<i>Puccinia punctata</i>	<i>Uromyces guatemalensis</i>
<i>Puccinia dolosa</i>	<i>Puccinia purpurea</i>	<i>Uromyces hariotianus</i>
<i>Puccinia eleocharidis</i>	<i>Puccinia ruelliae</i>	<i>Uromyces hedysari-paniculati</i>
<i>Puccinia elephantopi-spicati</i>	<i>Puccinia ruelliae-bourgaei</i>	<i>Uromyces hellerianus</i>
<i>Puccinia elytrariae</i>	<i>Puccinia sarachae</i>	<i>Uromyces ictericus</i>
<i>Puccinia enceliae var. aemulans</i>	<i>Puccinia scleriae</i>	<i>Uromyces indigoferae</i>
<i>Puccinia enceliae var. enceliae</i>	<i>Puccinia spagazziniana</i>	<i>Uromyces induratus</i>
<i>Puccinia enixa</i>	<i>Puccinia spagazzinii</i>	<i>Uromyces infarctus</i>
<i>Puccinia exornata</i>	<i>Puccinia sphenospora</i>	<i>Uromyces marginatus</i>
<i>Puccinia ferox</i>	<i>Puccinia subaquila</i>	<i>Uromyces mexicanus</i>
<i>Puccinia fidelis</i>	<i>Puccinia subcoronata</i>	<i>Uromyces montanoae</i>
<i>Puccinia filopes</i>	<i>Puccinia substrata</i>	<i>Uromyces myrsines</i>
<i>Puccinia fuchsiae</i>	<i>Puccinia synedrella</i>	<i>Uromyces novissimus</i>
<i>Puccinia fumosa</i>	<i>Puccinia tageticola</i>	<i>Uromyces oberwinklerianus</i>
<i>Puccinia gnaphalii</i>	<i>Puccinia taraxaci</i>	<i>Uromyces poliotelis</i>
<i>Puccinia gouaniae</i>	<i>Puccinia thalia</i>	<i>Uromyces proeminens</i>
<i>Puccinia graminis</i>	<i>Puccinia tithoniae</i>	<i>Uromyces salmeae</i>
<i>Puccinia heliconiae</i>	<i>Puccinia tolimensis</i>	<i>Uromyces setariae-italicae</i>
<i>Puccinia heterospora</i>	<i>Puccinia tonduziana</i>	<i>Uromyces spagazzinii</i>

- Uromyces trifolii-repentis*
Pucciniastraceae
Melampsoridium hiratsukanum
Pucciniastrum epilobii
Uredinopsis pteridis
Puccinosiraceae
Alveolaria cordiae
Cionothrix nudicolla
Cionothrix praelonga
Dietelia portoricensis
Puccinosira brickelliae
Puccinosira cumminsiana
Puccinosira pallidula
Raveneliaceae
**Cystomyces costaricensis*
Dicheirinia binata
Kernkampella appendiculata
Ravenelia corbula
Ravenelia echinata
Ravenelia expansa
Ravenelia havanensis
Ravenelia hernandezii
Ravenelia hieronymi
Ravenelia humphreyana
Ravenelia lagerheimiana
Ravenelia lonchocarpicola var. *mera*
Ravenelia lonchocarpicola var. *robusta*
Ravenelia mainsiana
Ravenelia mimosae-albidae
Ravenelia mimosae-sensitivae
Ravenelia spinulosa var. *spinulosa*
Ravenelia whetzelii
Ypsilospora tucumanensis
Skierkaceae
Skierka holwayi
Sphaerophragmiaceae
Austropuccinia psidii
Tranzscheliaceae
Tranzschelia discolor
Uropyxidaceae
Dasyspora gregaria
Dipyxis mexicana
Porotenus depallens
Porotenus elatipes
Porotenus permagnus
Prospodium abortivum
Prospodium amphiphilii
Prospodium appendiculatum
Prospodium couraliae
Prospodium kisimovae
Prospodium lippiae
Prospodium pithecocetii
Prospodium tuberculatum
Uropyxis crotalariae
Uropyxis diphysae
Family Incertae sedis
Desmella aneimiae
Desmella gymnogrammes
Desmosorus oncidii
Hemileia vastatrix
**Uraecium guanacastense*
Septodasidiales
Septobasidiaceae
Septobasidium gomezii
Septobasidium wilsonianum
Tremellomycetes
Tremellales
Bulleribasidiaceae
Hannaella luteola
Hannaella zeae
Vishniacozyma carnescens
Rhynchogastremaceae
- Papiliotrema flavescens*
Papiliotrema nemorosa
Tremellaceae
Tremella armeniaca
Tremella coalescens
Tremella fibulifera
Tremella fuciformis
Tremella lilacea
Tremella lutescens
Tremella mesenterica
Tremella nigrifacta
Tremella roseolutescens
Tremella rufolutea
Trimorphomycetaceae
Saitozyma podzolica
Family Incertae sedis
Sirobasidium minutum
Ustilaginomycetes
Urocystidiales
Doassansiopsidaceae
Doassansiopsis limnochardidis
**Doassansiopsis ticonis*
Glomosporiaceae
Thecaphora haumani
Thecaphora pustulata
Thecaphora smallanthii
Mycosyringaceae
Mycosyrinx cissi
Urocystidaceae
Urocystis ranunculi
Ustilaginales
Anthracoideaceae
**Anthracoida altiphila*
Anthracoida uleana
Cintractia axicola
Cintractia limitata
Farysia chardoniana
**Farysia corniculata*
Leucocintractia leucoderma
Leucocintractia scleriae
**Moreaua rhynchosporae-cephalotis*
Pilocintractia fimbriatylidicola
Trichocintractia utriculicola
Ustanciosporium montagnei
Ustilaginaceae
Melanopsichium pennsylvanicum
Microbotryum tenuisporum
**Pattersoniomyces tillandsiae*
Pseudozyma hubeiensis
Sporisorium cruentum
Sporisorium culmiperdum
Sporisorium holwayi
Sporisorium reilianum
Sporisorium scitamineum
Sporisorium sorghi
Sporisorium veracruzianum
Ustanciosporium montagnei
Ustilago affinis
Ustilago eriochloae
Ustilago ixophori
Ustilago maydis
Ustilago schroeteriana
Ustilago striiformis
BLASTOCLADIOMYCOTA
Blastocladiomycetes
Blastocladales
Blastocladiaceae
Allomyces arbusculus
**Microallomyces dendroideus*
CHYTRIDIOMYCOTA
Chytridiomycetes
Chytridiales
- Chytridiaceae**
Chytridium decipiens
Synchytriaceae
Miyabella aecidioides
**Synchytrium boerhaaviae*
Rhizophydiomycetes
Rhizophydiales
Family Incertae sedis
Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis
ENTOMOPHTHOROMYCOTA
Entomophthoromycetes
Entomophthorales
Ancylistaceae
Conidiobolus coronatus
GLOMEROMYCOTA
Glomeromycetes
Archaeosporales
Ambisporaceae
Ambispora jimgerdemannii
Ambispora leptoticha
Diversisporales
Acaulosporaceae
Acaulospora appendicula
Acaulospora bireticulata
Acaulospora colombiana
Acaulospora denticulata
Acaulospora elegans
Acaulospora excavata
Acaulospora foveata
Acaulospora longula
Acaulospora mellea
Acaulospora morrowiae
Acaulospora rehmsii
Acaulospora rugosa
Acaulospora scrobiculata
Acaulospora spinosa
**Acaulospora tuberculata*
Acaulospora tuberculata
Acaulospora laevis
Acaulospora spinosissima
Diversisporaceae
Sieverdingia tortuosa
Gigasporaceae
Cetraspora pellucida
Dentiscutata heterogama
Dentiscutata nigra
Dentiscutata scutata
Gigaspora gigantea
Gigaspora ramisporophora
Gigaspora margarita
Racocetra castanea
Racocetra coralloidea
Scutellospora calospora
Entrophosporales
Entrophosporaceae
Entrophospora colombiana
Entrophospora infrequens
Entrophospora lutea
Glomerales
Claroideoglomeraceae
Claroideoglomerus etunicatum
Glomeraceae
Funneliformis monosporus
Funneliformis geosporus
Funneliformis mosseae
Glomus albidum
Glomus brohultii
Glomus clarum
Glomus clavisorum
Glomus coremioides
Glomus dominikii
Glomus fasciculatum

Glomus fulvum
Glomus geosporum
Glomus globiferum
Glomus maculosum
Glomus microaggregatum
Glomus microcarpum
Glomus mosseae
Glomus rubiforme
Glomus versiforme
Glomus macrocarpum
Glomus taiwanense
Rhizophagus aggregatus
Rhizophagus clarus
Rhizophagus manihotis
Paraglomerales
Paraglomeraceae
Paraglomerus occultum
MUCOROMYCOTA
Kickxellomycetes
Harpellales

Harpellaceae
**Harpella tica*
Stachylina grandispora
Stachylina nana
**Stachylina paludosa*
Stachylina penetralis
Legeriomycetaceae
**Genistellospora guanacastensis*
Genistellospora homothallica
**Genistellospora nubila*
**Genistellospora tepidaria*
**Graminelloides biconica*
**Pennella montana*
Pennella simulii
Simuliumyces microsporus
**Smittium annulatum*
Smittium culicis
**Smittium culicisoides*
Smittium culisetae
**Smittium dipterorum*

**Smittium fasciculatum*
**Smittium parvum*
**Smittium phytotelmatum*
**Spartiella animae*
Mucoromycetes
Mucorales
Choanephoraceae
Choanephora cucurbitarum
Cunninghamellaceae
Cunninghamella echinulata
Cunninghamella elegans
Mucoraceae
Mucor hiemalis
Mucor plumbeus
Umbelopsidomycetes
Umbelopsidales
Umbelopsidaceae
Umbelopsis vinacea

Discussion

Knowledge of fungal diversity in Costa Rica is uneven across different systematic and ecological groups. The relatively high species counts in certain groups are largely the result of contributions from individual experts, particularly in areas such as lichenized fungi (Ostropales and Lecanorales), ectomycorrhizal fungi (Agaricales, Boletales, Russulales), wood-decaying fungi (Polyporales and Hymenochaetales), and specific groups of plant parasitic fungi (Mycosphaerellales, Meliolales, Phyllachorales, and Pucciniales). These biases significantly influence the relative size of taxonomic groups, resulting in an overrepresentation of certain groups in our dataset.

In checklists, the available information on the biodiversity of a given group of organisms is summarized for a given area; however, it should always be cautiously used. For instance, this checklist includes many long-forgotten names referring to poorly understood taxa, often only known from the type collection, which need critical revision. Also, not all literature records can be accepted uncritically, as taxon circumscriptions often vary among authors, and recent revisions have shown that what was once considered a single taxon may represent multiple distinct taxa of the same rank. On several occasions, we were forced to make difficult decisions when addressing these topics. Furthermore, the reliability of identifications varies across sources, and it is impossible to directly verify all records cited in the literature. Despite these challenges, including these names in the checklist is valuable, as it draws attention to potentially valid taxa, often from long-forgotten papers, allowing specialists to reevaluate them.

Until now, Costa Rica has lacked a taxonomically validated checklist of fungi. This work provides a solid, verifiable foundation on which future knowledge can be built. We hope it will become an essential resource for accessing nearly two centuries of accumulated information on Costa Rican fungi, supporting specimen revisions, the critical reassessment of poorly known taxa, and encouraging further exploration of under-researched areas. However, this checklist is not static; it is a dynamic project that will require ongoing updates as research advances. Contributions from the broader scientific community are not only welcome but crucial for its continued improvement and refinement.

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Supplementary Material

Supplementary Material 1. Taxonomic specialists and the groups they reviewed for this work.

Supplementary Material 2. References to literature containing records of fungi in Costa Rica that are cited in the Excel file.

Supplementary Material 3. List of excluded or doubtful taxa.